

IN WHAT WAYS CAN AN INCREASED UNDERSTANDING OF CHILDREN'S
EXPERIENCES OF THE JOURNEY BEFORE, DURING AND AFTER RESIDENTIAL CARE
HELP US TO DEVELOP POLICY AND PRACTICE THAT SUPPORTS MORE EFFECTIVE
TRANSITIONS TO ADULTHOOD IN SCOTLAND

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CONTENTS	2
Abstract	6
Acknowledgements	7
Chapter One: An Introduction to the Research Journey	8
1.1 The Personal	8
1.2 The Professional	12
1.3 The Political	13
1.4 The Research Problem	15
Chapter Two: The Sociology and Psychology of Being a Child	16
2.1 Introduction	16
2.2 What is a Child	16
2.3 Historical and Sociological Perceptions of Childhood	17
2.4 The Psychology of Being a Child	20
2.5 The Potential Impact of Negative Early Adverse Life Experiences	24
2.6 The Impact of Trauma	25
2.7 Summary	28
Chapter Three: The Social Policy Context	30
3.1 Introduction	30
3.2 The Legacy: The Poor Law	30
3.3 The New Poor Law	33
3.4 Philanthropy and Institutional Child Care	35
3.5 An Early Review for Children and Young People Living Away from Home	36
3.6 Kilbrandon and Beyond	37
3.7 The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC)	39
3.8 Summary	41
Chapter Four: Residential Child Care and Life After Care	42
4.1 Introduction	42
4.2 Corporate Parenting	42
4.3 Age and 'Looked After' Status	42
4.4 Looked After Statistics in Scotland	44
4.5 Who Provides Residential Care and What are The Financial Implications	45

4.6 The Regulation of Residential Placements	46
4.7 The Purpose and Provision of Residential Child Care for Children and Young People	46
4.8 Leaving Residential Care	50
4.9 Emerging Adulthood	51
4.10 Summary	53
Chapter Five: Ethics and Methodology	54
5.1 Introduction	54
5.2 Ethics	54
5.3 Recruitment	55
5.4 Ethical Approval	59
5.5 Methodology	62
5.6 The Participant Demographic	63
5.7 Research Approaches	64
5.8 Theoretical Framework	65
5.9 Reflections	66
5.10 Tacit Knowledge	67
5.11 Reflexivity	68
5.12 Emic-etic perspective	69
5.13 Power Differentials Between the Researcher and Participants	70
5.14 Rationale for the Study and Research Questions	71
5.15 Interview Participants: Group Composition	73
Chart One: Interview participants questionnaire demographic data	74
5.16 Interview Summaries	75
5.17 Summary	77
Chapter Six: Early Life Experiences of Family and State Support	78
6.1 Introduction	78
6.2 Family Ideology and Composition	78
Chart Two: Family composition	79
6.3 Economic Circumstances and Family Monitoring and Surveillance	80

Chart Three: Brothers and sisters living in the household	82
6.4 Early Life Experiences	83
6.5 Adversity in Childhood	87
6.6 The Relationship with State Systems	92
6.7 Foster Care and Brothers and Sisters	96
6.8 Conclusion	102
Chapter Seven: The Complexities of the Group Living Experience	105
7.1 Introduction	105
7.2 Urban Myths	105
7.3 The Formal Admission Process	106
7.4 Feeling Like a Failure	109
7.5 Placement Stability	110
7.6 Placement Bureaucracy and Being Institutionalised	115
7.7 Lost Childhoods	117
7.8 The Stigma	118
7.9 Support Network	121
7.10 Experiences: The Good and the Bad	123
7.11 Relationships with Other Professionals	125
7.12 Relationships with Family - Parental and Sibling Contact	126
7.13 The Extended Family	130
7.14 Conclusion	131
Chapter Eight: From State Care to Living More Independently	133
8.1 Introduction	133
8.2 The Reality of Leaving Care and Not Home	134
8.3 Preparation and Planning for Moving On	136
8.4 The Transition Process	142
8.5 Educational and Employment Achievements Post Care	146
8.6 Personal Achievements After Care	150
8.7 Emotional Wellbeing	153
8.8 Feeling Safe and Secure	155
8.9 After Care Support	156
8.10 Preparedness for Adulthood; Emerging Adulthood	160

8.11 Conclusion	166
Chapter Nine: Conclusion and Recommendations	170
9.1 Introduction	170
9.2 The Scottish Context	171
9.3 Participants Early Experiences of Poverty and Adversity	172
9.4 Attachments and separations: Young people's experience of being rejected	174
9.5 The Importance of Supportive Sustained Social Networks	176
9.6 Alternative to Family Placements: Residential Care	180
9.7 The Residential Effect	184
9.8 Leaving Care and Living More Independently	186
9.9 Measures of Success	189
9.10 Emerging Adulthood and Preparedness for Adulthood	190
9.11 My Original Contribution to Knowledge	192
9.12 Future Research	193
Bibliography	195
Appendices	
Appendix 1 Information Sheet	230
Appendix 2 Gatekeeper Letter	231
Appendix 3 Poster	232
Appendix 4 Participant Letter	233
Appendix 5 Interview Schedule	235
Appendix 6 Consent Form	236
Appendix 7 Questionnaire	237
Appendix 8 Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs)	238

ABSTRACT

It is widely recognised that residential care experienced young people have poorer outcomes than their peers within the general population (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014; Scottish Government, 2021; Ward and Stein, 2021). They are more likely to leave home early, have lower educational attainment, poorer mental health, and wellbeing and to become homeless (Stein, 2006; McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014; Care Review, 2020). With the increased risks associated with COVID-19 care experienced young people are also increasingly more likely to suffer from premature death (Goodwin, 2021). Leaving-care expectations continue to be influenced by age rather than stage.

Research in this field is impacted by recruitment difficulties in part due to a lack of national data collection on destinations. Young people were recruited through an advocacy agency that provides both in-care and post-care support. The study reflects demographic information gathered from a short questionnaire and individual semi-structured interviews with thirteen residential care experienced young people aged 18 – 29 years old.

Researchers highlight that leaving-care research suffers from a lack of theoretical frameworks (Stein, 2006; Pinkerton, 2020; Urquhart-Stewart and Wylie, 2021). This study uses social constructionism as a framework to deconstruct the experiences of the group. It shows that for many young people residential placements are successful and these resources should be promoted as an alternative to family living. Whilst positive attachment relationships are crucial for success, success is not measured consistently among state agents and the young people who experience services. Being alive, not repeating familial patterns and having structure is how young people measured success whereas professionals continue to use traditional markers.

This study adds to the body of knowledge by taking a holistic approach to the care experience of children. It provides both practitioner and academic insight as the researcher has worked throughout the PhD in the field of study.

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I would also like to thank my family and friends, for their patience in what has been a long six years. Without their unwavering support and sustenance this work would have been more challenging. Ultimately however, I was motivated to complete this PhD by the young people I interviewed. During the times when I considered whether the additional work while holding down a demanding full-time job was worth it, I just reminded myself of the alternative. That I did not write this piece and the stories that had been shared would be untold. It was inconceivable to me, so I hope that I have done these young people justice.

This PhD is dedicated to my granddaughter Ruby Isabella Keen. I hope that she will follow in my footsteps.

CHAPTER ONE: AN INTRODUCTION TO THE RESEARCH JOURNEY

It is beyond a doubt that all our knowledge begins with experience.

Immanuel Kant

1.1 The Personal

It is difficult to begin a work of this magnitude without setting the scene of how I have arrived at this point. I grew up the second of three sisters in a large textile industrial locale in the West of Scotland where I was very aware of myself as part of one of two mixed race families in a place that had the largest town population in the land. Both families had heritage in different islands in the West Indies. Although I experienced racist taunts from other children due to my Scottish and Bajan roots it was not until I was asked what nationality I was by my headmaster in primary school that I started to see myself as different, although it took me several years to really think about what that actually meant. I have no doubt this was not his intention, and he may have been asked to complete a statistical report, but that conversation remains one of my childhood memories and was my first experience of being categorised into a box. I believe that this is an experience that is shared by many care experienced young people who can spend much, if not all, of their lives challenging societies stereotypes of them. In 2017, the Scottish MP for Glasgow East was believed to be looking to pass a private bill so that 'care experienced' individuals could be included in The Equality Act 2010 as a protected group (Kevin, Interview five). I have been unable to ascertain whether a formal proposal has been made, but in January 2018 the Scottish Liberal Democrat MSP marked the year of Young People by calling for care experience to be a protected characteristic considering that they have the poorest outcomes of any demographic group (Bell, 2018). When I was growing up this was something associated with being black.

The 2011 census reflects that the population of Scotland comprised of 4% (210,996) minority ethnic groups with an estimated population of 5,295,403 in total (Scotland Census, 2011). City population statistics for March of the same year had my town consisting of 76,834 people (www.citypopulation.co.uk). In April 2011, the STV news stated Scotland's population was the highest it had been since 1977 with the rise resulting from "births outstripping deaths and immigration exceeding emigration" (STV News: 27th April 2011, p.1). I was aged 14 years in 1977 and this is when I first remember questioning who I was and where I had come from. This was against a backdrop of experiencing bigotry from my closely related indigenous family

whilst we had no contact with my father's side of the family who we believed to be deceased. I sought a sense of identity from black American history and great orators such as Martin Luther King and Malcolm X as well as Nelson Mandela and Ghandhi, due to the absence of anyone of note within Britain and television programmes that appeared to mock people of colour such as 'Love Thy Neighbour' (1972 - 1976) and 'It Ain't Half Hot Mum' (1974 - 1981). I felt a sense of isolation and of being different but I was grateful as I knew there were people worse off than me. I wonder how similar this is for young people who are supported to embrace their care identity, sometimes by advocacy organisations, but see their lives depicted in television programmes such as 'Tracy Beaker' (2002) and 'Tracy Beaker Returns' (2010) or 'The Three Girls' (2017) which looks at the lives of children and young people living in local authority care or who are known to social work services. We see nothing that reflects the longer-term impact that life experiences have when youngsters transition from adolescence to adulthood.

On reflection, as an optimistic youngster I did not dwell on my experiences, and I appreciated life. I felt growing up I had a lot of inner strength, despite feelings of isolation, and I thought about what it must be like for others without this. I can reflect that this optimism was linked to my personality and my ability to bounce back, sometimes referred to as resilience. This study will explore these features when discussing young people's own life experiences.

Growing up I was often threatened that if I did not behave, I would be sent to the local residential school. At the time I had no idea that it was solely for boys and that I would end up working there for most of my adult life. I also did not consider that these threats were intrinsic to an association between bad behaviour and institutional care and a move between the private sphere of home and the public sphere of the residential or children's home. As a rebellious child these threats were frequent and although they did not come to anything, at the age of 14 years old I knew I wanted to work in social work. My choice of residential care may have been influenced by a school friend who lived in a children's home and struggled with her mental health, but it may also have been triggered by a fascination of what this fabled place was like and my love of the Victorian writer Dickens who depicted institutional care. I wanted to engage with those individuals who may have felt marginalised in society, those who others may have given up on or who had limited external resources to rely on. I had individuals at key points in my life who believed in me and helped me to have an inner self belief, something

I imagined that these young people needed. It would take me another 20 years to realise my ambition as like many others my life path did not quite turn out as I had hoped or planned.

Bronfenbrenner (1979) asserts we all need someone who is crazy about us, and I was fortunate in that in most parts of my life that has been the case for me, whether it be a family member, extended family, social network or friends, there was always someone who had faith in me even when I did not necessarily have this in myself. I grew up in what could be described as a happy family. I have many fond memories of my childhood; we were well cared for, had 'All mod cons', annual holidays and we were outwardly very respectable. I spent many years trying to convince my parents to adopt or foster a mixed-race little brother unsuccessfully, in a bid to give someone a better life. While I in no way want to paint an image of my experience as a child that would contradict the reality, I recall being asked by a professional if I were being abused by my father due to my withdrawal at school, I was very pensive and reflective as a child, I could also be non-compliant, and this was reflected in my school attendance. Whilst this assumption was incomprehensible, I remember feeling at the time that someone cared enough about me to ask the question and thought that an external factor could be contributing to my behaviour. At the age of 17 I was asked to leave home when my parents went on holiday, and I never returned due to ongoing conflict with my parents and my unwillingness to follow their boundaries. I experienced a hasty transition from adolescence to adulthood practically but emotionally it took a long time before I saw myself as able to look after myself and as an adult. This has been the experience for many young people who leave residential care. However, as many struggle to make it into adulthood they do not have an opportunity to come out the other end (Dixon and Stein, 2002a; McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014). Living without a roof over my head, having to rely on limited resources and the sense of loneliness I experienced re-enforced my determination to achieve a social work career and my chosen field in residential childcare.

Jung coined the term 'wounded healer', and this is reflective of many practitioners within social work and social care who are drawn to the field due to their own experiences. Barr (2006) also undertook a small study involving 253 participants and found that nearly 74% of therapists had made their career choice after experience of being wounded. Arnett (2014, p.155) asserts that "we often choose our areas of research because they have some personal resonance". In my case this is certainly true.

During my final year of completing this study it did not rain, it poured. The pandemic, COVID-19, affected the world and changed how we all went about our daily lives. Those with care experience have been disproportionately affected by the pandemic (McGhee and Roesch-Marsh, 2021), increasing feelings of isolation (Coram Voice, 2020). While on a personal level I was fortunate in that my daily routine of work remained intact although I had to assume additional roles and responsibilities, as a student access to physical library resources were curtailed but I was able to continue to study with the support of my supervisors and the online PhD forum. Despite not being unduly affected by the pandemic I experienced considerable loss in both my immediate and extended family. In addition, a family secret was exposed that would cause me to question my entire existence and re-evaluate my early life.

For many young people growing up in care this can be their experience as they are not familiar with family narratives growing up. The independent Care Review (2020) recognises that

...there is no 'one size fits all' policy that reflects the experience children and families report of Scotland's 'care system'. For some, they wish their family had received more support to stay together. For others, they wish they had been removed from their families earlier. What unifies the experience of decision making is a recognition that Scotland must be better at listening, reflecting on and doing what children want and need (Care Review, 2020, p. 30).

The conflict within my own family home, growing up, made me question why my parents stayed together. My mother was likely to have been influenced by the stigma of being a divorcee or lone parent and the lack of financial support for women who found themselves in that position, she had direct experience of this through her best friend. While my parents stayed together and seemed to grow affectionately into their relationship, they reflected that they stayed together for their children. I must acknowledge that we are never too far removed from the circumstances of others and while I do not profess to have first-hand experience of the subject matter in this PhD my life and professional experience offer me invaluable insight.

1.2 The Professional

These life experiences led to a professional interest in how young care experienced people are prepared for the adult world. When I completed my *BA (Hons) in Applied Social Studies* and *Diploma in Social Work* in 1998 my dissertation focussed on the effectiveness of throughcare and aftercare services in preparing youngsters for leaving care.

I completed my MSc in *Social Work Management*, the *Certificate in Child Care and Protection Studies* and the *Advanced Award in Social Work* in 2008 while working as an assistant residential unit manager in the third sector. My dissertation looked at whether the social work qualification equipped residential childcare workers for the residential role and task, I believe the eclectic nature of the qualification helped me to view challenges holistically and provided the groundwork for my professional expertise (Whitelaw, 2018). Ryan and Walsh (2006) speak of a post-positivist approach in which your own experiences shape your work. Neil Thompson (2014, p. 64) further asserts that whilst theory underpins practice it is more helpful “to begin with practice and then draw on theory to help make sense of our practice experiences”. In my view it is like the chicken and egg dilemma; we engage in a process and reflect on previous experiences that will help us to make sense of things but it is difficult to ascertain just how much knowledge we have brought to the original situation. I am interested in this interplay and in how the social sciences help us to understand the experiences within the residential childcare sector. It is with this background; a quest for improving practice and providing greater understanding combined with a thirst for continuous professional development and knowledge that I approach this research thesis. For me ‘the personal is political’ (Hanisch, 1970).

I have spent more than two decades working within the residential childcare sector within the statutory, third and private sectors in Scotland. We now live in a society where commissioning, procurement, regulation, and an increased use of business models are utilised to support young people who may have experienced primary and secondary trauma (Scottish Government, 2019). During my time in the sector, I have met and worked with hundreds of young people between the ages of 5 and 18 years old; two out of the three first young people I case managed are no longer alive. This has affected me deeply making me reflect on what went wrong and whether there was anything I or the system could have done differently that could have achieved better outcomes for these young people. These youngsters continue to motivate me and influence my approach to what I essentially view as a vocation rather than a job.

1.3 The Political

Like any research journey I have had to fine tune my area of study and justify the need for my research as any PhD must make an original contribution to knowledge. Figures published by the Scottish Government in March 2021 show that between August 2019 and July 2020 14,458 young people were looked after by their local authority. This was a rise of 1% (196 young people) and reflected a rise for the first time in 8 years (Scottish Government, 2021).

The data also highlights that 6,492 young people were eligible for aftercare services (Scottish Government, 2021). While these terms will be defined within the literature review, it is important at this point to recognise that most young people who come to the attention of the Children's Reporter, do so because of concerns of a care and protection nature (Scottish Government, 2019; 2020; 2021). The Scottish Government (2017) recognises that care experienced young people are more likely to need mental health services, go to prison, become homeless, have their own children removed and have issues with substances.

McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin (2014) also highlight poor outcomes stating "they experience:

- much higher rates of early death;
- poorer access to continuing education or training;
- greater unemployment and homelessness;
- worse mental health and physical wellbeing;
- greater rates of teenage pregnancy; and
- an increased likelihood of involvement in or exposure to, criminal activity" (McGhee Lerpiniere, Wetch and Graham, 2014, p. 7).

It has long been recognised that there are a small "number of referrals being received by the Reporter potentially of a more complex nature", I will return to this in Chapter one (Scottish Government, 2015, p. 4). Very often they will be the young people who are accommodated within residential placements (National Audit Office, 2014; Kendrick, Steckley and Lerpiniere, 2008; Rich, 2009). Research has found that these young people are more likely to leave care at a much younger age than their non-looked after peers who increasingly remain at home into their thirties (Young Scot, 2014; Office of National Statistics, 2017).

Despite these findings there is very little research in Scotland looking at the experiences of young people who have left residential care. Research is limited to government resourced reviews designed to highlight or address concerns and promote improvements in practice (Skinner, 1992; Kent, 1997; Shaw, 2007; Audit Scotland, 2010; Scottish Government, 2008, 2017; McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014; Care Review, 2020), or researcher-led studies reflecting outcomes for care leavers (Jackson and Cameron 2012; Stein & Dixon, 2006; McGhee, 2019). There are also a few pieces of research written by those with care experience (Duncalf, Hill and McGhee, 2013; Rohan and Smith, 2016). Practice

based research in this area in my experience is rare although resources such as CYC-net¹ provide regular practitioner written articles. I am coming from the unique position of working within the environment where my research is grounded but with the belief that those who have lived within residential establishments have the knowledge and expertise fundamental to increasing our understanding of the research problem. I wholeheartedly underestimated the impact my insider status would have in this research process in terms of opening doors to me and being able to put skills, knowledge, and expertise I had developed over time into practice, but I will revisit this in my ethics and methods section.

From an economic perspective the cost of residential services is considerable when compared to alternative care, but it is recognised that residential care can meet the needs of some of the “most vulnerable in our society” (Kent, 1997; Milligan and Stevens, 2006; Kendrick et al., 2008). In England in 2013 £2.5bn was spent on fostering and residential placements for 0.6% of the under-18 population. This equated to £29,000 - £33,000 per annual foster placement, accounting for 75% of placements, and £131,000 - £135,000 per annual residential placement (National Audit Office, 2014). Scottish figures published in 2010 reflect that “councils spend £250 million a year on residential care for children and young people, many of whom have very complex and challenging needs” (Audit Scotland, 2010, p. 5). This accounted for 6.5% of total council expenditure (Audit Office, 2010). Services in Scotland are such that local authorities either provide or commission residential services with most supplied by the independent sector: the voluntary and private sector. Spend cannot measure efficacy and the longer-term costs if good outcomes are not achieved (Audit Office, 2010; N.O.S., 2014).

In 2008, the Scottish Government stated, that we should want for looked-after children the same outcomes we would want for our own children (Scottish Government, 2008). Almost ten years later the goal was to make Scotland the best place for all children to grow up (Scottish Government, 2017). The ‘Independent Root and Branch Review’, that will be explored in Chapter three, looked at the experiences of more than 5,000 children and young people who engaged in a review of the care system, producing a range of reports that identified the need for transformational change within systems, processes, and cultures (Care Review, 2020). The review was commissioned one year after I began my PhD journey and it was extremely intimidating to know that a parallel process was taking place. The review was

¹ CYC-net is the International Child and Youth Care Network that supports and promotes learning and information sharing for those who work or live with children and young people. <https://cyc-net.org>

expected to last three years although from start to finish it was almost four. I feared that it would overshadow my work that would struggle to have anything additional to offer. This has not been the case and I am extremely proud of this reality.

1.4 The Research Problem

Research indicates that residential care experienced young people have poorer outcomes than the general population; despite legislation and social policy that is aimed at redressing this (Ward and Stein, 2021). We do not however, have a good understanding of young people's experiences and what supports good outcomes for this group of individuals, so this thesis aims to provide an original contribution to knowledge by answering the following five key research questions:

1. What are the early childhood experiences of young people who are placed in residential care in Scotland?
2. To what extent are young people supported to understand these experiences?
3. To what extent do young people get what they need from residential care?
4. To what extent are young people prepared for leaving residential care and what supports a successful transition?
5. Does the theoretical framework of emerging adulthood add to our understanding of their transition to adulthood?

This study will share the experiences of thirteen care experienced young people aged 18 – 29 years old, providing valuable insight into their lives before going into care, while being in care and after they have left their care placement. By looking at the overall experiences of this group of young people this thesis will illustrate what young people need from care providers and policy makers if outcomes for care leavers are to improve.

CHAPTER TWO: THE SOCIOLOGY AND PSYCHOLOGY OF BEING A CHILD

2.1 Introduction

The previous section has helped to set a context and position me within this research but to make sense of the data a literature review must be undertaken. The Research Ethics Guidebook (2016a) sees the literature review as ethical practice which builds on previously completed work. The role of the writer is to “develop arguments about what needs to be studied, and why” (Research Ethics Guidebook, 2016a, p. 1), and by evidencing what has been said about a particular topic, through identifying trends, strengths, weaknesses, and analysis gaps in existing knowledge are highlighted and addressed (Phillips and Pugh, 1993). The critical literature review will question assumptions and challenge claims for which there is contestable research evidence (Bell, 2010).

This literature review chapter will begin by looking at the experience of being a child touching on legal, sociological, anthropological, economic, and psychological perspectives. Cohen, Miller and Pate (2019, p. 1211) state that interdisciplinary research “is driven by the need to address complex problems that cut across traditional disciplines”. When we think about childhood, we often reflect upon our own experiences of growing up and what it means to be a child in a particular time and space (James, Jenks and Prout, 1998). This chapter will look at the social construction of childhood and whether this is consistent over time and place (Jenks, 2005). It will also look at how we develop as human beings; from the genetic component of this described as ‘nature’ to the interactive relational element of development referred to as ‘nurture’ (Bukatko and Daehler, 2012; Lightfoot, Cole and Cole, 2013).

Perceptions of evil and good will be discussed from a sociological perspective using Jenk’s typology of ‘Dionysian’ and ‘Apollonian’ views of children (Jenks, 2005). It would be impossible to view childhood in isolation. As social beings our development is bound up in relationships so the chapter will touch on the role of the family. It will conclude by exploring human development and the importance of forming healthy relationships as well as identifying what can go wrong by looking at the impact of adversity (Maslow, 2014; Brendtro and Mitchell, 2015; Asmussen, Fischer, Drayton and McBride, 2020).

2.2 What is a Child

The legal definition of a child is set out in the Children and Young Person (Scotland) Act 2014 under section 97 which states a “child” means a person who has not attained the age of 18

years” (2014, p. 63). While this is in keeping with the definition used by the United Nations in the Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC, 1989) within the Children (Scotland) Act 1995, the previous legislation about children, an age distinction was made between a child in part one of the act which dealt with parental rights and responsibilities. There, a child was viewed as someone aged under 16 years and part two which addressed how local authorities and children’s hearings promote a child’s welfare defined a child as someone under the age of 18 years old. The NSPCC (2020) highlight that in Scotland different legal contexts reflect varied definitions of a child as is reflected in what children and young people are allowed to do and at what age. At the age of 16, a child can join the armed forces with their parents’ consent, they can leave home without consent, they can marry and be in a civil partnership and can vote in the Scottish Youth Parliament. It is not until the age of 18 years old however that an individual is allowed to vote in the general election and buy alcohol in a pub; they no longer need consent to join the armed forces (Young Scot, 2020). It is difficult to understand why these contradictory age distinctions exist given legally someone is viewed as a child but can marry, but similar complexities are evident when we look at childhood from sociological and psychological perspectives.

2.3 Historical and Sociological Perceptions of Childhood

There can be an assumption that childhood has always existed but the French historian Aries (1996) argues that prior to the 17th century there were children but art reflected Rubenesque-like depictions and he states it was not until much later that the importance of children, and perceptions of them as charming and the focal point of family portraits, saw them viewed as significant in their own right. It is said that high mortality rates until the 18th century impacted on the family’s investment in children, who were largely seen as disposable (Aries, 1996; Lightfoot, Cole and Cole, 2012). The British historian Pollock (1983) however argues that Aries view is flawed, and diaries and biographies provide evidence that childhood had previously existed. She states that the indifference parents allegedly felt towards their offspring was not supported by the healthy human development of children who survived mortality (Pollock, 1983). This is supported by Qvorstrup (1999) who highlights that indifference towards childhood, and not as Aries states children, was reflective of the position of them as a marginalised group within society as they had less power and capital than human adults. Despite the differences in status, it is argued “that children and adults alike are active participants in the social construction of childhood and in the interpretive reproduction of their shared culture” (Cunningham, 1995, p. 9).

Cunningham believes it is crucial to separate the child from childhood which is seen as a changing 'set of ideas' (Cunningham, 1995). Childhood ideology by the mid-19th century was powerfully influential in the middle classes of the West (Cunningham, 1995; Jenks, 2005), but most historians cite modern views of childhood as being a product of the industrial revolution, resulting from urbanisation, lower birth rates and reduced child deaths (Qvorstrup, 1999; Hendrick, 1992; Pinker, 2006). The 19th century differed to previous centuries due to the separation between the child and adult brought about by compulsory school education (Cunningham, 1998). This was seen as having the biggest impact on what childhood meant as it removed children from paid work, albeit low-wage work (Cunningham, 1998). The view of the exploitation of the 'factory child' who needed rescued strengthened the view of the need for this separation (Brendtro and Mitchell, 2015; Hendrick, 1992). Qvorstrup (1999, p. 10) believed the influence of macro-structures on childhood are reflective of it being "smaller, poorer, institutionalised (*and*) privatised".

The importance of childhood is reflected "in a concern for the salvation of the child's soul' in a growing interest in the way children learn; and in a sense that children were messengers of God; that childhood was therefore the best time of life (Cunningham, 1995, p. 5). Two models are seen as reflecting the socialisation process of childhood: one is deterministic where the child is viewed as passive, untamed, a novice; the other is constructivist where the child is viewed as an eager learner, as an active agent and a participant in the construct. The deterministic approach fits within the functionalist model which was popular mid-century and was seen as promoting the social order, viewing equilibrium as essential for society therefore children needed to be trained and prepared to maintain the status quo (Corsaro, 2011).

These contrasting views are supported by Jenks (1995). The Protestant Reformation of the sixteenth century introduced the perception of children as being born in 'original sin' needing to be managed through obedience to authority (Lightfoot, Cole and Cole, 2012). 17th and 18th century philosophers expressed a contrasting view of children and Jenks (2005) describes these two competing views of childhood as 'Dionysian' and Apollonian'. The 'Dionysian' view of children holds that they are born evil, this view is rooted in Christianity and the experiences of Adam, although Cunningham (1998) argues that this view had declined by the mid-19th century. Rules and dogma are seen as consensual and external to the individual in a society where people are largely seen as the same and child rearing as universal. Parenting was therefore distinct, strict, through moral instruction and physical guidance. Wet nursing would not be unusual, and socialisation would be a battle of wills in which the child would be 'broken'

but this would be in his best interests (Jenks, 2005). With such social controls the growing child was seen as learning respect and to feel shame (Jenks, 2005).

James, Jenks and Prout (1998) highlight that this view of

...children's naturalness derives from the universal experience of being a child and the persistent and commonplace experience of having and relating to children; the belief in the inevitability and even 'good' of their maturation emanates from a combination of post-Darwinian developmental cultural aspirations and conflated with these, the post-Enlightenment confusion of growth and progress (Jenks, 1982a; 1989)" (James, Jenks and Prout, 1998, p. 17).

The 'Apollonian' view of the child as innocent and born good was reflected in the philosopher Rousseau's *Emile* and this perception is receptive to individual needs with people seen as more complex resulting in less global values. (Rousseau, 1889; Jenks, 2005). Views and rules are wide ranging and "gone are the strictures of uniformity" (Jenks, 2005, p. 65) with children raised in a way that promotes the expression of their individual personalities. Difference is however

both volatile and subversive and must be policed if collective life is to be sustained at all. The control moves subtly in response to such a potentially fragmented social structure; as few symbols are shared, externality is an improper arena in which to uphold the sacred. Consequently, the control moves inside, from the public to the private, and so we monitor and examine and watch the Apollonian child; he or she in turn learns to watch over him or herself and shame is replaced by guilt (Jenks, 2005, p. 70).

Individualism contained for the collective good. Jenks (2005) argues that these distinct descriptions are not literal but reflective powerful images of the discourses around children that inform the "shifting strategies that Western society has exercised in its increasing need to control, socialize and constrain people in the transition towards modernity" (Jenks, 2005, p. 65).

Brendtro and Mitchell (2015) state that research has largely reflected middle class European and North American perspectives and they would argue that the previous description of childhood is ethnocentric. Indigenous anthropological studies of traditional communities reflect observations of children "as radiantly happy, courageous, and highly respectful of elders"

(Brendtro and Mitchell, 2015, p. 1). They argue that it has only recently been acknowledged that these traditional systems have value. Some communities have a deep respect for children who are seen as 'sacred', a 'gift of God' and 'God's gift' (Brendtro and Mitchell, 2015). The ethnocentric nature of much research is supported by James, Jenks and Prout (1998) who refer to the 'socially constructed child' who does not exist in any identifiable form but is reflective of multiple formations of childhood.

Sociologists have argued that childhood is both historically and culturally specific reflecting it is neither universal or natural (Cunningham, 1995; James, Jenks and Prout, 1998; Corsaro (2011). Childhood is viewed as subservient to the status afforded adulthood with the child viewed as striving towards becoming an adult as though this is the primary goal (Corsaro, 2011).

2.4 The Psychology of Being a Child

Within the discipline of psychology childhood is viewed "as a separate, distinct, and unique period, a special time when individuals are to be protected, nurtured, loved and kept free of most adult responsibilities and obligations" (Bukatko and Daehler, 2012, p. 12). For most cultures, childhood involves five distinct developmental periods; pre-natal, infancy, early childhood, middle childhood, and adolescence (Lightfoot, Cole and Cole, 2013), but there are differing views on whether childhood is a continuous developmental process or a series of stages (Coleman, 2011; Bukatko and Daehler, 2012).

Erikson cites a 'series of stages' in human development and his theory has significantly impacted on our view of development over the life span (Hill and Tisdall, 1997). His eight developmental stages were formulated from his experiences as a psychotherapist with children and young people across all social classes (Hill and Tisdall, 1997). Each stage involves the resolution of a 'psychosocial crisis' before moving on to the next. This depicts childhood as biologically driven and with relatively predetermined universal states that form a progression towards adulthood (Hill and Tisdall, 1997). Erikson talks about three principles of organisation; the 'somatic' organism, individual 'ego' and the 'societal' social. He describes them as belonging to disparate scientific disciplines namely: biology, psychology, and social science. Roles evolve from the 'societal' element of organisation crucially important in Chapter three.

The human being, at all times, from the first kick in utero to the last breath, is organized into groupings of geographic and historical coherence; family, class,

community, nation. A human being, thus, is at all times an organism, an ego, and a member of society and is involved in all three processes of organisation. His body is exposed to pain and tension; his ego, to anxiety; and as a member of a society, he is susceptible to the panic emanating from his group (Erikson, 1995, p. 30).

The significance of the group will be revisited shortly but relationships are key to a child progressing from one stage to the next.

UNICEF (2013, p. 42) state that “from the earliest years, the child’s sense of subjective wellbeing is intimately bound up with relationships”. In a comparative global study, it was found that the UK was rated 16 out of 29 when using international child wellbeing indicators, although this improved to 14 out of 29 when the measures included the views of children (UNICEF, 2013). Bowlby believed that positive human attachments between a child and maternal caregiver were key to the wellbeing and the development of healthy positive relationships necessary for a child’s needs to be met and for them to develop and grow into healthy individuals (Bowlby, 1974). He stated that the loss of the healthy attachment figure, generally seen as the mother, could result in “a tendency to make excessive demands on others and to be anxious and angry” (Bowlby, 1974, p. xiii – xiv) when their needs were not being met. He cited evidence of ‘hysterical personalities’ and in “a blockage in the capacity to make deep relationships, such as is present in affectionless and psychopathic personalities” (Bowlby, 1974, p. xiii – xiv) as indicators of what could result from flawed attachments. ‘Separation anxiety’ can result when a child experiences trauma, especially as a result of being removed from their mother to a novel environment with unknown people (Bowlby, 1974).

In Bowlby’s discussions of attachment behaviour, he used observations from a number of studies of children developing a theory of motivation that, while initially reflecting the mother or care-giver relationship, helps us to understand the impact of separation represented in the behaviour sequence of ‘protest’, ‘despair’ and ‘detachment’ (Bowlby, 1974; Cassidy and Shaver, 2008). In his analysis of the Ugandan study by Ainsworth (1963, 1967) and Scottish study by Schaffer and Emerson (1964) he said that once secure relationships were formed through the responsiveness of the carer to the child, children were then able to attach securely to others. However, it was noted “that in any one child the intensity and consistency with which attachment behaviour is shown can vary greatly from day to day or hour to hour” (Bowlby, 1974, p. 202) reflecting the significant interplay between nature and nurture. He further found

that young children did not need to be separated from their carer for a significant period of time to show signs of distress and found that when this experience was repeated by different carers and nurses the child would behave in time as though neither parenting nor human contact had any significance to them. When children did re-engage there was a fear of subsequent loss resulting in the modification of their behaviour. The intensity of the reaction appeared to be mitigated by a sibling presence or stability such as one replacement carer (Bowlby, 1974, 1979; Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

Bowlby states that

...during the course of development a child constructs for himself working models of his attachment figures and of himself in relation to them. The data used for model construction are derived from multiple sources: from his day-to-day experiences, from statements made to him by his parents, and from information coming from others. Usually the data reaching him from these diverse sources are reasonably compatible. For example, not only may a child experience his parents as accessible, considerate, and responsive but information coming from other sources may amply endorse that view... Alternatively, both the experience a child has of his parents and the information he receives from them and from others about them may point consistently to their being unloving. Many more complex relationships can be imagined; but, provided in each case the information reaching the child from the different sources is reasonably compatible, the working models that he builds of parents and of self will be internally consistent in themselves and also complementary to one another. As such the models are able to reflect with a fair degree of accuracy the sort of people the child's parents are, how they see him and how they are likely to treat him. Thus, whether relationships are happy or the reverse, the child is able to make firm and accurate predictions and, on that basis, to construct plans of action likely to prove effective (Bowlby, 1974, p. 317).

The role of attachment in human development continues throughout the lifespan (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1974, 1979; Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Erikson, 1963, 1995; Furnival, 2011). Its function is seen as crucial to the development of the child as it provides a secure base for the child to learn, explore and play, develop a personality, and also feel safe (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1974). A child will seek proximity to a care giver when safety is compromised and when they are alarmed seeking reassurance and protection (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1974).

While Bowlby developed his attachment theory to extend beyond the maternal primary carer it is important to note that alternative theories promote multiple attachment relationships. Mead (1969) believes that there is no evidence that a child needs to be nurtured by their mother and her anthropological studies reflect that being nursed by others and multiple carers is more conducive with healthy development. She states that “children need to have a variety and an intensity of experiences with adults” (Mead, 1969, p. 233) citing evidence from a study of gifted individuals who she said had multiple adult contact. Parental relationships were viewed as important, but it was the quality of time spent with children rather than the duration itself that was seen as important (Mead, 1969). She said that

...they can create very close relations with them if they pay close attention to them when they do see them. If we have a society with fewer children and more diversified communities, and if we get rid of the multi-purpose, nuclear family that is supposed to do everything together, we can bring up children with more varied relations with adults. This means the little boy who is interested in mechanical things will be able to find somebody to teach him, and the little girl whose mother always cooks out of cans, can find someone down the street to teach her how to make a pie (Mead, 1969, p. 233).

Rutter (1979) talks about distress syndrome where anxiety is linked to attachment behaviour. He however questions whether this is provoked by the separation or as a result of what happens during the separation. He cites Bowlby and Ainsworth as sources supporting the theory of attachment in infants where they tend to use attachment seeking behaviours at times, although not solely, of anxiety and fear. While he feels both theorists evidence how bonds will grow with a care giver who is responsive to and meets their needs, they do not explain adequately insensitive unresponsiveness. Relationships are reciprocal with parenting adjusted to the age, stage and individual needs of the baby but ‘monotropy’ and multiple differentiated attachments are most likely to be favourable when at least one secure relationship is experienced.

The social environment is a contributory factor to poor outcomes (Rutter, 1979). Attachment seeking behaviour appears to heighten when stressed despite the response of the attachment figures and it was found that institution-based children approached other children and adults more often than their peers but their social interactions were less successful, this appeared to result from inappropriate attention needing responses from the children (Rutter, 1979). Attachment relationships continue to develop despite adversity and whilst the early years have

a significant impact on both bonding and social development, experiences at any age may be impactful. Despite this many children develop normally although experts still do not know fully why this is the case (Rutter, 1979; Ungar and Perry, 2012).

Vygotsky sees children as active participants with their development rooted in the collective actions of society so it is crucial that children's interactions with others are effective (Corsaro, 2011). New knowledge and skills result from activities with others, and language acquisition is seen as ensuring the reproduction of cultures from one generation to the next (Corsaro, 2011). Unlike Piaget who viewed cognitive development as individualistic, Vygotsky viewed development as collectivist and contextual (Corsaro, 2011). He "argued that they have their source not in biological structures or the learning of the isolated individual but in historically developed socio-cultural experiences" (Daniels, 1996, p. 31). Development for Vygotsky was twofold: the perpetuation of the socio-cultural system transmitted through the generations and the internalisation of organised social behaviour (Daniels, 1996). Vygotsky proposed the concept of internalization where a child learns on a social level before this learning is internalised (Corsaro, 2011). Vygotsky believed in "the need to explain rather than merely describe psychological processes that are unique to human beings" (Daniels, 1996, p. 31).

Brendtro and Mitchell (2015) also state that

...small children in Polynesia watch others work and then pitch in to help as soon as they master simple skills. In all the world's indigenous cultures, children grow to maturity immersed in interactions with adults and older peers as caregivers. Traditional kinship systems worldwide ensure that children have many mothers, fathers, and grandparents (Brendtro and Mitchell, 2015, p. 2).

2.5 The Potential Impact of Negative Early Life Experiences

Maslow (2014) states in his 'psychology of health' that there are several core assumptions that help in our understanding of human development. Our nature is described as intrinsic and relatively unchanging resulting in a unique make up common to humans. Our "inner nature ... seems not to be intrinsically evil, but rather either neutral or positively "good". What we call evil behaviour appears most often to be a secondary reaction to frustration of this intrinsic nature" (Maslow, 2014, p. 21 – 22). We need to bring our inner nature to the fore so we can live healthy, productive, and happy lives. If the essence is suppressed people become sick, this sickness may be delayed. Unlike animals our inner nature "is weak and delicate and subtle

and easily overcome by habit, cultural pressure, and wrong attitudes toward it” (Maslow, 2014, p. 22). Maslow states that humans strive towards actualisation.

Whilst I would challenge the description of behaviour being evil as extreme, it is evident that how children are nurtured will impact on their development. Perry and Szalavitz (2006) state that

...while we don't know whether there is a fixed “sensitive period” for the development of normal attachment the way there appears to be for language and sight, research does suggest that experiences...in which children are not allowed the chance to develop permanent relationships with one or two primary caregivers during their first three years of life have lasting effects on people's ability to relate normally and affectionately to each other (Perry and Szalavitz, 2006, p. 86).

This view is supported by Bronfenbrenner who believes that all children need someone who is ‘irrationally crazy about them’ (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). He identifies four different levels of the ecological environment: ‘microsystems’ – these include the family and school and the relationship the child has with them, ‘mesosystems’ – relates to the relationships between the microsystems such as the relationship between the home and the teachers, ‘exosystems’ refer to systems that have an indirect impact on the child such as a parents work that may result in less time at home or the stress placed on the household and the ‘macrosystems’ which is reflective of beliefs or ideologies outwith the family that may impact indirectly but influences how a family functions such as the input from the state (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). This fits well with Bowlby's observation about how perceptions of carers will inform the internal working model of the child. So, what happens when these relationships are challenging?

2.6 The Impact of Trauma

It is difficult to look at the impact of trauma without looking at the impact of poverty. The Promise report states that

...poverty is a mediating factor among various factors that increase the risk of child abuse and neglect. When a family lacks financial resources, when they face substandard service provision, when the streets they walk are less safe than in other parts of town, when homes are cramped and when keeping food on the table is a struggle, meeting all the needs of a child can be challenging. It is thus hardly surprising that some families, without supportive resources to turn to, are simply

unable to be the parents they want to be and that their children deserve (Care Review, 2020, p. 17).

When born into this situation you are less likely to be able to free yourself from these circumstances and this is articulated in views supportive of the notion that this is a state of mind or mentality trapping people and limiting hope and aspirations (Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008). The assertion of dysfunction in the fabric of these communities is implied rather than highlighting low economic status and a lack of opportunities and agency for people to effect change (Pyysiainen, Halpin and Guilfoyle, 2017). The Scottish Government publishes three yearly data highlighting adversity and terms such as the 'most deprived areas' while not applicable to all those living within a geographical locale, can illustrate multiple deprivation (Scottish Government, 2016). They found in their study of 5.3 million people, conducted in 2016, 5% of the most deep-rooted deprivation levels evident since the study was formed in 2004 were found in Inverness, Dundee City, Stirling, North Lanarkshire, East Ayrshire, seven areas of Glasgow City, Renfrewshire, and Inverclyde (Scottish Government, 2016). Forthcoming chapters will show that some of these areas are linked with the study group as well as high incidences of residential care usage.

The pivotal 'Adverse Childhood Experiences' (ACE) study by Felitti, Anda, Nordenberg, Williamson, Spitz, Edwarads, Koss and Marks (1998) reflects that dysfunction is not determined by poverty or class. The study was conducted with over 17,000 middle-class Americans in receipt of costly private health provision, and it found that ill-health in later life correlated to early childhood adversity. The greater the childhood adversity the greater the long-term impact on the individual (Felitti, Anda, Nordenberg, Williamson, Spitz, Edwarads, Koss and Marks, 1998). The governments early intervention strategy that followed the Allen and Duncan Smith (2008) report focussed on those under 3 years old stating they needed to "receive the stimulus and responsiveness they need to flourish" and that all young people should be provided with "the knowledge and support they need to turn out to be good parents" (Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008, p. 25). At that time, 1.5 million of the 16 million under 16-year-olds within the UK were viewed as 'at risk' (Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008). While they argue that these experiences may not all have occurred while the child was aged 0 – 3 years, they supported the view that what followed this age range was ultimately determined by what had gone before (Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008; Allen, 2011). ACE scores were therefore ultimately determined by circumstances around when children were born (Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008). White and Wastell (2017, p. 2256) challenge the 'cultural ascent' of biological

sciences proposing to help us make sense of both the social and natural worlds. They argue that the improvement of health outcomes is couched in moral and ethical underpinnings that begun with neuroscience in the 1990's and continues with epigenetics. It provides an explanation of the mechanisms underpinning the interaction of the environment and the DNA blueprint, and thus invites an interest in the impact of adverse conditions, such as deprivation or normatively deficient parenting (White and Wastell, 2017, p. 2256).

White and Wastell (2017) argue that this is done without any indication of how poverty and social disadvantage is going to be tackled. Gervai (2009) also highlights that parenting approaches account for only one third of differences in secure and disorganised attachment relationships. Accumulated risk factors of income, family size, marital conflict, age, massive stressors, severe ill-health, the impact of separation and education were all identified as playing a role in whether attachment relationships were secure or insecure (Gervai, 2009).

Meeting a baby's needs is crucial for positive development and being stimulated in a healthy environment encourages the growth of healthy brain cells and synapses (Perry, 2006; Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008). The exact impact of multiple childhood adversities and economic deprivation is still being researched as the dominant discourse continues to focus on 'individual pathology' (Walsh, McCartney, Smith and Armour, 2019). What is known is that trauma can be felt as a result of these experiences and for Ungar and Perry (2012) trauma and its impact has several variables. There is increased risk when there is an ongoing threat for instance with multiple or repeated incidents, the duration, severity and intensity of its nature, the relationship of the source of the harm and when there is disruption caused to the individual and or family members (Ungar and Perry, 2012). They believe the term trauma is over-used and one of the most poorly defined terms within neuropsychiatry (Ungar and Perry, 2012).

Blower (2017) however describes both 'simple' and 'complex' trauma. 'Simple' trauma is described as a one-off event such as an accident or assault, whereas 'complex' trauma is repeated or complicated as would be the case of abuse when the relationship between the victim and perpetrator may be that of care giver. Brendtro and Mitchell (2015) describe these differences as 'type one' and 'type two' experiences of trauma with complex trauma most often interpersonal in nature. Kinniburgh, Blaustein and Spinazzola (2005) state that

children who suffer from complex trauma have been exposed to an environment marked by multiple and chronic stressors, frequently within a caregiving system

that is intended to be the child's primary source of safety and stability (Kinniburgh et. al., 2005, p. 424).

Unlike non-traumatized children who can focus their energies on the development of a range of competencies, for children who are traumatised the focus is on survival (Kinniburgh, Blaustein and Spinazzola (2005). While Perry (2006, 2014) states that the stress response system in human beings is one of the few neural systems that when damaged can result in dysfunction across the main areas of the brain, he also says

...one of the most important characteristics of both memory, neural tissue and of development, then is that they all change with patterned, repetitive activity. So, the systems in your brain that get repeatedly activated will change and the systems in your brain that don't get activated won't change. This "use-dependent" development is one of the most important properties of neural tissue. It seems like a simple concept, but it has enormous and wide-ranging implications (Perry, 2008, p. 29).

Rose and Rose (2012) argue that the neuroscientific determinism associated with brain research must be challenged as it is untrue and driven by pharmaceutical companies who benefit from the medicalisation of social problems through increased diagnosis of 'conditions'. Edwards, Gillies, Lee, Macvarish, White and Wastell (2017) in a submission to the science and technology select committee contest the ACEs evidence base. They also view the determinist discourse as serving interests which reduce social problems to those deemed to possess individual deficiencies.

Evidence reflects that the brains malleability is lifelong and recovery relies on new patterns of repetitive experiences through healthy containing nurturing healing relationships (Kohlstaedt, 2010). Evidence also reflects that changing economic circumstances would help to alleviate ACEs in the first place (Edwards, Gillies, Lee, Macvarish, White and Wastell, 2017). Further research is needed that addresses both ACEs and social circumstances (Walsh, McCartney, Smith and Armour, 2019).

2.7 Summary

This first literature chapter has helped to set a context to childhood by exploring psychological and sociological theories around being a child, both globally and in Scotland, and illustrating the complexities which are both historically and culturally specific (James, Jenks and Prout,

1998; Corsaro, 2011; Cunningham, 1995; Erikson, 1963, 1965). It has explored what it means to be a child from a range of social science perspectives, illustrating that perceptions of childhood change over time and space and appear to have been influenced by urbanisation and the separation of children and adults in the workplace with the introduction of compulsory education. It also looked at the influence of psychology in helping us to understand how children develop and grow when nurtured by care givers who are attuned to meeting their needs. The impact of family ideology on childrearing and socialisation has been explored and the growing body of neuroscience and epigenetics research particularly linked to ACEs has been discussed and critiqued (Perry, 2006; White and Wastell, 2017; Gillies, White and Edwards, 2019; Marrayat and Frank, 2019). It concluded by identifying potential barriers to healthy development, the importance of reciprocity and the impact on the developing brain when stress responses are triggered because of adversity or trauma. Further research has challenged the claims of neuroscientists showing that the brain continues to develop well into our twenties giving promise that things can develop and change. The next chapter will look at the social policy context by moving outside the individual relationships explored above by exploring how society treats children.

CHAPTER THREE: THE SOCIAL POLICY CONTEXT

There can be no keener revelation of a society's soul than the way in which it treats its children (Nelson Mandela, 8th May 1995).

3.1 Introduction

It is difficult to get an understanding of the present without first revisiting the past as is reflected in my research thesis journey. Residential childcare and what supports successful transitions to adulthood for care experienced young people is no different. To help in our understanding of this I looked at being a child in the previous chapter as well as touching on adversity including poverty but to continue this journey, I must now look at this in more detail by exploring the historical context to public support through a literature review beginning with the Poor Law and continuing with contemporary legislation, social policy and guidance that informs provision in Scotland. The chapter will illustrate the values inherent in public relief as well as the philanthropic history of residential care for children. It will conclude by exploring the measures in place to support children, young people and their families including provision for when they leave care and transition to more independent living arrangements.

3.2 The Legacy: The Poor Law

Early evidence of social welfare is reflected in the 'Old Poor Law' provision of Scotland, England and Wales. In Scotland, "only the 'destitute' and 'disabled' could claim relief; the able-bodied unemployed, for whom the English Poor Law made provision, were excluded" (Englander, 1998, p.2). This may in part have resulted from an assumption in Scotland that the employed did not experience the poverty experienced by others, but it might have been more likely to have resulted from more limited resources available in Scotland subjecting the employed or seasonal poor to a form of means testing; in this case exclusion (Abrams, 1998).

Accounts reflecting provision in Aberdeen shows that the administration of poor relief was formulated in acts of parliament where statutes were grounded in concerns about beggars who were viewed as a burden to their parish, rather than resulting from any wish to address poverty (Lindsay, 1975; Nicholls, 1967). The movement of people was discouraged as eligibility for relief depended on physicality.

Katz (2013) reflects that poverty was historically viewed in two ways; due to scarcity or as a result of human deficiency. This view continued to pervade despite contrary research evidence

(Townsend, 1979; Abel-Smith and Townsend, 1965). Poverty as seen as a 'problem of persons' has "both hard and soft versions" (Katz, 2013, p. 3). The soft view reflects poverty resulting from idleness, dysfunction, immorality, or skills deficiency while the hard view reflects "inherited deficiencies that limit intellectual potential, trigger harmful and immoral behaviour, and circumscribe economic achievement" (Katz, 2013, p. 3). The soft version is more deeply rooted in history but offers the potential for poor people to escape their circumstances with hard work and moral guidance whereas the latter version appears destined. Neither view shows much sympathy to those who experience poverty although there were exceptions in the form of children and those not viewed as responsible for their circumstances such as widows; the 'deserving poor' (Katz, 2013). Those viewed as bringing their circumstances on themselves were viewed as the 'undeserving poor' (Katz, 2013). Many decades later Rowntree and Booth would become viewed as pioneers in defining poverty, with it seen as not being able to afford necessities. Poverty was seen in both 'relative' and 'absolute' terms with the former seen as being poor in relation to others, whereas the latter definition reflected a significant lack of resources (Abel-Smith and Townsend, 1965).

Growth in the population and economic movement resulted in increased vagrancy in the sixteenth century. In Scotland "provision for the deserving poor was formalised in an Act of 1535 which made each parish liable for the support of its own aged and infirm poor and collections (*were*) to be made for that purpose" (Unions Scotland, nd, p. 1). Money was raised through church collections, fund raising events and donations. Further legislation followed and the 1579 act "authorised the scourging and burning" of those aged 14 – 70 years old who travelled the country unemployed (Lindsay, 1975, p. 13). This was never enforced but by 1592 statute ordered imprisonment for vagabonds. Relief was means tested with lists drawn up of 'deserving poor' while beggars were either returned to their birthplace, punished or both (Lindsay, 1975).

The historian Beier highlights that "vagrancy was one of the most pressing social problems of the age" (Beier, 1995, p. xix), again dealt with through legislation that was not enforced. In principle legislation appears to have been meant as a deterrent but the burden of enforcement seems to have been unmanageable. This disparity is not uncommon and modern examples of the limited enforcement of legislation can continue to be found with begging or smoking for those under 18 years old in Scotland. Beier identified 'masterless men' who when uprooted were viewed as a menace to society. These were men without land, with few prospects and

no secure roots. Over 80% of the poor were able bodied and subject to laws regarding begging (Beier, 1985). Women here appear to have been only viewed in terms of their relationship to men and seem to be absent from the research literature.

In England, changing ideology from biblically supported deserving notions of poverty to views of wilful idleness also resulted in means testing and perceptions from philanthropists that “good Christians worked to pay *(their)* way” (Beier, 1985, p. 5). There was no need for this in Scotland as the able bodied were largely denied poor relief (National Record of Scotland, 2017). Considerable stigma surrounded those who were poor, and this view is evident in modern times with contemporary examples evident in media coverage of benefit claimants and policy and practice designed to catch ‘benefit cheats’. Within society there is a classed distinction made between poor people who claim money they are not entitled to and wealthy people who do the same thing, for instance with corporation tax evasion despite both resulting in less resources being available to those in need.

In 1672 poverty was such a big issue that legislation stated that ‘correction houses’ were to be erected to provide accommodation and punishment for beggars, one of the first of these was operational in Edinburgh from around 1720. The children of beggars aged over five years could be taken into the servitude of landowners, until they were the age of 18 for girls and 24 for boys (Cage, 1981). 24-year-olds could be referred to as boys emasculating the lower classes. 1754 accounts show that 7 men, 35 boys, 12 girls and 20 women were housed in the Aberdeen workhouse. By 1768 orphaned boys or boys of ‘needy’ parents were accommodated within the workhouse (Lindsay, 1975). By 1776 boys needed to be younger than ten years, healthy and have appropriate recommendations (Lindsay, 1975). Those who were accommodated were educated in the three R’s and apprenticed to trades. Girl recipients had to be destitute, friendless, and healthy and aged 6 – 9 years old (Lindsay, 1975). This shows that criteria were set to ensure that children were also scrutinised to ascertain if they were eligible for support.

Workhouses served several purposes in addition to feeding the poor. They were institutions with very strict criteria for admittance and the harsh treatment whilst resident ensured only the destitute would venture there (Lindsay, 1975). Charles Dickens’ depiction of *Oliver Twist* dramatizes the experience of young boys who were orphans and highlighted the unjust nature of society where the working classes were policed, marginalised, and criminalised (Dickens, 1838). If they were able to secure service they were further isolated from communities as

young girls needed to be friendless and 'boys' were infantilised remaining into adulthood (Lindsay, 1975).

3.3 The New Poor Law

The 1707 Act of the Union meant Scotland had an independent judicial system so the Poor Law Amendment Act enforced in 1834 in England and Wales did not replace previous legislation in Scotland until 1845 (Englander, 1998). The lateness of legislation being enacted in Scotland compared to other parts of the UK is a theme that we will revisit later in this study.

The Church of Scotland split and the "formation of a secessionist Free Church threw the Kirk based relief system into turmoil" (Englander, 1998, p. 49). In 1845 the Amendment Act developed an administrative framework but there continued to be no formal system for the able bodied unemployed in Scotland. Relief practices therefore varied across parishes and while the inspector would not allow people to perish due to the need for assistance, he had the autonomy to make up the rules about provision (Englander, 1998). Those in need relied on the honesty and integrity of enforcers which could result in further marginalisation for some individuals or groups.

In England and Wales there was a system for the able bodied unemployed but as historically Scotland was a much poorer country it was not able to support all its poor according to research evidence (Lindsay, 1975; Englander, 1998; Abrams, 1998). Sampling of Mitchell library records of the late 1880's reflect that able-bodied recipients of poor relief in Glasgow were often Irish settlers with alcohol difficulties. Limited resources and attitudes of the time meant that there was a need to ensure that the poor relief system was used as a safety net and as the "very last resort" (Englander, 1998, p. 46) as was reflected in the exhausting of all avenues prior to care being provided to both adults and children

intensive searches (*were*) made for irresponsible parents. Boarding-out pauper children to suitable guardians was deemed superior to institutional provision; it gave the disadvantaged child the benefits of a secure home, mainstream schooling, the prospect of a job and a chance to escape the influence of a degenerate environment and so break the cycle of dependency (Englander, 1998, p. 51).

The preference for the boarding out of children in Scotland and inferior view of institutional care will be revisited but for now, as poverty was viewed as a personal failing, individuals were

encouraged to believe that “the taking of public assistance was a badge of disgrace” (Cage, 1981, p. ii). This helped to curb the number of claimants, but by the end of the 1820s philanthropists challenged the Scottish system for poor relief, particularly when it came to the needs of children (Cage, 1981). Despite this however, Mahood (1995) describes the prevention era of 1800 – 1854, when children were viewed as dangerous. To prevent them from causing harm and criminality they were housed in mixed gender prisons with adult offenders. Records show that a 9-year-old Scot was given the death sentence, by hanging, having broken a window and stolen paint (Mahood, 1995). Although this child was given a reprieve, working class children were very much viewed as disposable. The age of legal responsibility in Scotland was 8 years old and until 2018 it was the lowest in Europe, only being raised to 12 years old in 2019 (Scottish Parliament, 2019).

Mahood (1995) also talks about the policing of working-class families and highlights that by 1850 legislation promoted ‘in loco parentis’ where the state assumed responsibility when parents were not seen as meeting the needs of their children. Children were viewed as in danger and local authorities as ‘child savers’. Within Scotland there was some attempt at ‘rescue and reform’ in Glasgow both with young men offenders and women who were described as ‘magdalenes’ (Mahood, 1995). Gender differentials were evident with girls seen as in moral danger whereas boys were viewed as offenders.

Between 1885 – 1932 children were viewed differently and during this ‘protective era’ legislation was designed to safeguard those who were considered as less fortunate (Mahood, 1995). Local Government Boards replaced the regulatory bodies for Poorhouses in 1894 and they were accountable to Parliament. By the First World War poor relief buildings were used for military casualties and the Local Government Act (1929) meant Poorhouses became care establishments for the elderly, chronically sick, infirm, and unmarried pregnant females (Mahood, 1995).

Stewart and Welshman’s (2006) study of wartime evacuation describes

...how the Scottish experience of evacuation and the condition of children was understood through a structural explanation of poverty and social conditions rather than by blaming the behaviour of individuals (cited by Elsley in Shaw, 2007, p. 168).

Despite this insight and social reform developments in England relating to early years education in 1870 which became universal this step was not replicated in Scotland until 1872 (Mahood, 1995; Elsley, 2007).

3.4 Philanthropy and Institutional Child Care

At the same time as the introduction of compulsory education and the move to protect children there were a variety of philanthropists who had a significant impact on the care of initially orphaned children, through the introduction of Ragged Schools. The largest children's homes providers in Scotland, Aberlour – founded by Miss Macpherson Grant of Aberlour in 1875, and Quarrier's – founded by William Quarrier in 1871, were established in the 1870s (Abrams, 1998). Smith (2009) reflects on early care for children being borne from a desire for them "first and foremost to be educated for the purpose of ensuring they could earn a living and not become a burden on the state" reflecting that support was not borne from wanting to do good (Smith, 2009, p. 23). Despite this assertion there was also recognition that early philanthropists such as Thomas Guthrie in Edinburgh, Thomas Barnardo in London, Elizabeth Kibble in Paisley and William Watson the Sheriff in Aberdeenshire, were motivated by their abhorrence of children and young people's living experiences and not by their burden on the state (Smith, 2009).

The 'Scottish Parochial Board' was the responsible authority in Scotland for relief and residential care was only used for youngsters who couldn't be found homes and were viewed as older, unruly or challenging. These youngsters would be accommodated in industrial schools or reformatories (Abrams, 1998). Scotland differed from other UK systems where industrial schools were used for care and protection whilst reformatories were used for offenders and despite the differentiation between needs and deeds both systems relied on harsh regimes (Smith, 2009; Higginbotham, 2017). Due to a dearth in Catholic carers catholic young people were likely to be institutionalised rather than being placed with a substitute family (Abrams, 1998). Decades later this experience would resonate with the experiences in fostering where local authorities attempted to recruit carers from similar ethnic backgrounds to those children and young people they were trying to place (Rashid, 2000).

Reformatories grew from the prison system although industrial schools evolved from the education system (Mahood, 1995). This evolution in 1838 resulted from funds raised by Miller from the Glasgow police and Brebner who founded the Scottish Prison System (Mahood,

1995). This drive to do good combined with increasing middle-class concerns about convicts and the working classes which resulted in more children being involved in compulsory education in Scotland in 1872 (Abrams, 1998).

By the 1930s Approved Schools replaced both reformatories and industrial schools, providing vocational and educational opportunities in addition to an alternative provision to prison for the young, this followed negative publicity over how they were being run (Higginbotham, 2017). Legislation such as the Youthful Offenders Act (1854), the Reformatory Schools (Scotland) Act 1854 and the Industrial Schools Act (1857) saw the poorest children in society, punished for begging and ‘wandering’ and parents of the children were required to contribute to the cost of their care (Higginbotham, 2017). It would not be until the Social Work Scotland Act (1968) and the reforms brought about by the Kilbrandon committee, that Approved Schools, known in Scotland as List D schools, would become part of the remit of the newly formed social work departments and local authorities (Higginbotham, 2017), I will return to this shortly.

3.5 An Early Review for Children and Young People Living Away from Home

The Poor Law provision was a product of primary legislation which is referred to as ‘acts’, while secondary legislation reflects ‘rules and regulations’. In addition to this Common and European law and guidance informs our practice with children and young people, it is important to highlight these differences prior to moving on to more contemporary legislation. The Children Act (1908) combined previous childcare legislation in the UK but it would take further legislation and many decades to change how Scotland treated young people who offended. A development was evident in 1930s legislation which introduced the welfare principle and juvenile courts (Smith, 2009). The post second world war optimism, the previous decade had been ravaged by the great depression, was viewed as a time to rebuild Britain, and the development of the welfare state in 1945 combined with a reflection of greater emphasis on childcare and families with government support (Elsley, 2007). Lady Allan, the ‘Nursery Schools Association’ Chairman, told the Times of 15th July 1944 about the condition of residential care where there were “repressive conditions that (*were seen as*) generations out of date and unworthy of our traditional care of children” (Shaw, 2007, p. 182). The death of Dennis O’Neill in England who had been placed in foster care by the NSPCC and the maltreatment of Norman and Harry Wilson in Fife at the hands of carers combined with other concerns resulting in the first examination of the care system for children and young people accommodated away from home (Shaw, 2007). The fact that both situations occurred to

children who were boarded out or fostered made no impact on the ongoing negative association with residential care for vulnerable children and young people.

3.6 Kilbrandon and Beyond

In 1961 the Secretary of State selected a committee to review provision for “juvenile delinquents and juveniles in need of care or protection or beyond parental control” (Kilbrandon, 1995: vii). Chaired by Lord Kilbrandon reform was revolutionary and innovative setting Scotland apart from other parts of the UK. From the start the recommendations from the Kilbrandon Committee were seen as “radical, humane and far reaching” (Fraser of Carmyllie, forward to Kilbrandon, 1995, p.vii). They informed the Social Work (Scotland) Act 1968 that “also created the Children’s Hearing System that aimed to ensure the safety and wellbeing of vulnerable children and young people through a decision-making lay tribunal called the Children’s Panel” (Daniel and Scott, 2019, p. 1).

A subsequent review of these reforms resulted in the Children’s Hearings (Scotland) 2011 legislation fifty years later resulting in the modernisation of the system, but the principles remained the same. The Children’s Panel continued to be made up of three lay people and the most common underlying factor resulting in referral to the hearing system remained issues around upbringing (Kilbrandon, 1995; SCRA, 2020). However, The Promise Scotland Team (2021) highlighted the need for the reform of the Children’s Hearing System (CHS) and a working group consisting of the CHS, Scottish Children’s Reporter Administration (SCRA) and The Promise Scotland Team with a remit of redesigning the system ensuring that lived experience is at the heart of this reform putting children and families first.

While other countries such as Sweden were viewed as having a progressive way of dealing with children in need, the system in Scotland has been viewed worldwide as ground breaking and the envy of both the global north and south (Glasgow Herald, 3.8.2015; Partners in Advocacy, 2020). The legal framework surrounding this system continues to determine how young people are placed within residential care, the criteria they must meet to live there, and the systems and processes followed while they are there. One of the challenges reflected in the Care Review however results from a lack of coherence in the legislation pertaining to children and young people (Care Review, 2020). It includes 44 parts of primary legislation, 19 pieces of secondary legislation, three international conventions that cut across six out of nine governmental policy areas (Care Review, 2020b). This lack of consistency and comprehension is likely to reflect contradictions in addition to those outlined in Chapter two in

relation to the legal definition of a child. The Care Review highlights that children can be lost as systems fail to be responsive to their needs and their situation and circumstances are not viewed holistically. It can also be a minefield for practitioners trying to navigate the legal basis for their work.

Before moving on to the next part of the journey looking at provision within residential care placements the legal framework for placements will be explored. The Children (Scotland) Act 1995 continues to underpin legislation in place for children in Scotland with part one of the act relating to parents, children and guardians including parental responsibilities and rights, and part two relating to the welfare of children who are the subject of local authority involvement (Norrie, 1995). This legislation has at its heart children's voice and the three underlying principles of the act are; the views of children should be taken into consideration, the no order principle, and the welfare of the child is paramount (Scottish Government, 2004). This legislation sets out the guidance and regulation for children and their families and identifies the process and criteria for a child to be looked after, I will discuss this fuller in the following chapter.

The Looked After Children (Scotland) Regulations (2009) set out that prior to considering a residential placement local authorities must carry out an assessment identifying a child or young person's needs and how they will be met within the placement, considering the function and objectives of the establishment. This guidance also sets out that members within the same family, wherever this is appropriate and practical, should be placed together. Under the Children (Scotland) Act 1995, the local authority must provide the residential placement with comprehensive written information reflecting the child or young person's experiences and identifying their needs in keeping also with the 'getting it right for every child' approach which puts the child at the centre (Audit Office, 2010).

In keeping with changing practice, childcare legislation continued to be refined and developed with the introduction of the Children and Young Person (Scotland) Act in 2014. This resulted in additional measures being introduced for children who were care experienced who would previously have been supported within legislation up to the ages of 18 and 21 in the form of throughcare and aftercare, measures have been increased to 21 and 26 with children capable of remaining within care placements until 21 years old, referred to as 'continuing care' and to advice and guidance until just before their 26th birthday (Scottish Government, 2014). New

corporate parenting responsibilities resulted in an emphasis on statutory responsibilities although this was framed in terms of 'eligible needs' and 'may' provide advice resulting in discretionary rather than entitled to supports for children and young people up to the age of 26 years old (Scottish Government, 2014; CELCIS, 2014).

Local Authorities should ensure care leavers have “the necessary life skills and receive adequate financial and other support at what is a difficult time for all young people” (Scottish Government, 2008, p. 6). There is a formal preparation process in place in Scotland that was introduced in 2004, Pathways Planning, where a young person is assessed, and a plan put in place to prepare them for leaving care and for living more independently (Scottish Government, 2004a). Data from the Scottish Government in 2020 reflects that 266 of 326 residential care experience young people had a pathways plan (Scottish Government, 2020). Figures consistently show that around 82% of those leaving residential care have a pathways plan and it is crucial that this figure is increased as it promotes good practice and a mechanism for a holistic assessment of readiness. Practical preparation and planning can be put in place to manage this transition sensitively, but this does not equate to young care leavers being afforded the same opportunity as their non-care experienced peers. Equating corporate parenting with natural parenting could help to move away from the age distinction associated with maturity for care leavers. This is difficult to achieve when statutory agencies are required to undertake pathways plans for accommodated young people who remained looked after at the age of 16 years, but government gathered data in 2017 reflected that only 65% of young people had these, although this figure rose to 82% for young people in residential care who appeared to fare better in this respect (Scottish Government, 2017). By July 2020, statistics remained stable at just under 82% which is more remarkable when we consider the impact of COVID-19 on workers ability to continue to engage with young people (BASW, 2021). However, without an assessment of needs and a plan our most vulnerable children and young people are likely to continue to achieve poor outcomes post care.

3.7 The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child

In 1991 the UK ratified the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) and in January 2021 the Scottish Government agreed to incorporate the principles of the UNCRC into Scots law embedding the rights of children in the process (Scottish Government, 2021). While it was unanimously passed in Scotland in March of the same year, it was challenged by the UK Supreme Court as the Scottish Government overstepped its

governmental powers. Sections 6, 19, 20 and 21 are currently being revised so that this can become statute. Article 20 outlines an entitlement to “special support and assistance from the State” for those “children without parental care” (Munro, Pinkerton, Mendes, Hyde-Dryden, Herczog and Benbenishty, 2011, p. 2418).

The UNCRC also produced alternative care guidance which highlights the significance of three phases when leaving state care, these are: ‘preparation and planning’, the ‘transition process’ and ‘aftercare support’ (Munro et al., 2011). Each phase should help to prepare young people for adulthood, a time of maturity, and this will be explored further in Chapter eight when I will look at these processes in detail using this as a framework to share young people’s experiences. It is worth noting that despite the UNCRC committee requiring feedback from member states about their adherence to the Convention, resulting in a five yearly progress update, it has been highlighted that little, if any, feedback is received when countries do not promote the wellbeing of care leavers (Munro et al., 2011). This means that nations are not being held accountable when they do not meet the needs of some of the most vulnerable young people in our society but there are barriers to recommendations as member states experience different economic status.

Similarly in Scotland legislation, the Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014, promotes a gradual transition to adulthood through ‘continuing care’ and ‘aftercare’ which are legal terms although the latter only comes into force when young people are no longer receiving ‘continuing care’. This law reflects the principles of Staying Put Scotland, and the next chapter will explore this in more detail as well as looking at planning for children moving on from residential care. The comprehensive three-year root and branch review of the care system completed the orientation and discovery stages with a ten-year strategy put in place and an implementation plan due to be published in spring 2022 that in keeping with other aspirations, should see an increased focus on the needs of care leavers (Care Review, 2019, 2021). The review will be discussed further in the forthcoming chapters as it continues to impact on the culture, practices, and systems within the care sector. At the end of 2021, a consultation was also being developed taking the form of the children’s care and justice bill with children’s rights firmly rooted in discourse around children and young people (Lightowler, 2020).

3.8 Summary

This chapter has illustrated the impact of historical social policy and legislation on perceptions of individuals and families. It has set out the legal framework that has helped to set a context in Scotland and the rest of the United Kingdom within which models of welfare were established that worked with the dichotomy of care and control resulting from the concerns regarding the social order that led to the policing of citizens when providing charity and poor relief (Beier, 1985; Mahood, 1995). Individuals were viewed as either deserving or undeserving of poor relief and there was criteria that determined whether someone received support (Beier, 1985; Mahood, 1995; Campbell, 1978). The chapter went on to look at more contemporary approaches to children and young people who were viewed as in need of care and protection. It introduced the UNCRC that promotes children's rights, the convention was ratified in the UK in 1991 and the Scottish Government recently put forward a bill to enshrine the UNCRC in Scots Law. The chapter also introduced legislation that supports increased provision for children designed to ensure a more gradual transition to adulthood. The next chapter will develop the literature review further by focussing on residential care for children and the social and formal supports for those who move on.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESIDENTIAL CHILDCARE AND LIFE AFTER CARE

4.1 Introduction

The previous chapter explored the legislative framework for children and young people deemed to need care, support, or guidance over the past few hundred years. This chapter will begin by introducing the concept of 'corporate parenting', the term used in Scotland to describe the statutory and collective responsibility of state agencies to ensure that they work in partnership with other providers and resources to ensure the needs of children and young people both in families and alternative care are effectively met. It will look at residential care as an alternative care for these children, defining what is meant by residential care, why children and young people may be placed there and its role and function. It will continue by exploring the opportunities and experiences that prepare these young people for adult life by discussing their throughcare and aftercare needs. The chapter will conclude by exploring the concept of emerging adulthood and discuss whether this is a developmental stage that can help us to understand residential care young people's experiences.

4.2 Corporate Parenting

To be a good 'corporate parent' local authorities should prioritise the needs of young people living within their authority and "seek for them the same outcomes any good parent would want for their own children" (Scottish Government, 2008, p. 3). Corporate parent is the term used to reflect the formal local partnerships needed between statutory agencies and associates to ensure that they work together to meet the needs of children, young people, and care leavers (Scottish Executive, 2007). There is a statutory duty for agencies to co-operate and coordinate activities and when services are purchased these functions may be delegated to those responsible for providing day to day care (Scottish Government, 2008).

4.3 Age and 'Looked After' Status

It is helpful at this point to define what is meant by residential childcare. There are several placements that cater for children and young people who are under the care of their social work departments, also known as 'looked after' (Scottish Government, 2008). This 'looked after' status ceases when a young person reaches the age of 18 years old and currently this status cannot be attained at the age of 16 or 17 years old unless a child has previously been referred to the children's Reporter or they are an open referral (Children's Hearing (Scotland) Act, 2011). The Care Review and children's rights groups have challenged this as it is not in

keeping with the adoption of the UNCRC (Scotland) Bill (Scottish Government, 2020). When this Bill is passed and becomes enshrined in Scot's Law, a child will constitute someone under the age of 18 years old and a young person will be defined as someone between the ages of 18 and 26 years old (Lightowler, 2020). This change in status and language should engender a paradigm shift as our expectations of children are less than those we have for young people in relation to comprehension and responsibility taking.

Children and young people can live in residential homes, residential schools, secure accommodation, crisis and respite care, foster care, with prospective adopters, kinship care or they can reside within the family home subject to legal jurisdiction (Scottish Government, 2017). Residential schools are resources that provide residential accommodation as well as educational provision for children (Shaw, 2007). They have their origins in industrial and reform schools referred to in the previous chapter evolving to approved and List D schools (Shaw, 2007). Their history has had a lasting legacy and going back to the middle of the last century, it was stated in both the English Curtis Report (1946) and the Scottish Clyde Report of the same year, that young people without appropriate alternative homes would preferably be adopted but if this was not an option they should be fostered or as a last resort placed within an institutional home that should house less than eight children (Higginbotham, 2017). The term residential care is used to refer to children's or residential homes or schools or secure accommodation (Scottish Government, 2017). These refer to the group care living experience where children and young people may live with other children who are not related to them. Peer friendships can be framed in negative terms, but they can also provide an important 'source of support' for children (Emond, Steckley and Roesch-Marsh, 2016). The terms outlined above will be used interchangeably as to do otherwise due to the limited sample size of this study, may result in individuals being identifiable. It should also be highlighted that secure accommodation has different criteria to other forms of group care, for admission and length of stay, as young people residing there have lost their liberty because they have been deemed to be a risk to themselves or a risk to others (Nolan, 2019).

The age of criminal responsibility was raised from 8 years old to 12 years old in 2019 in Scotland, but it remains one of the lowest age rates in Europe, although it is now higher than the rest of the UK where it is currently 10 years old (Houses of Parliament, 2018). A very small percentage of young people placed within secure accommodation are there because of criminal acts and those placed within this accommodation can have the most challenging life experiences of any young people who live within the care system (Gibson, 2019).

4.4 Looked After Statistics in Scotland

The interplay between the private realm of the home and public sphere of statutory agencies continues to change over time and is reflected when families are faced with challenges that result in state intervention (Asmussen, Fischer, Drayton and McBride, 2020; White and Wastell, 2017). This can result in compulsory measures of supervision when universal services are seen as insufficient for ensuring that the needs of the child are being met (Norrie, 1995; Scottish Executive, 2002: Scottish Government, 2008; 2012).

Local authorities, also known as councils, have legal duties to care for young people, either in voluntary arrangements agreed through parents or on a compulsory basis through the hearing system or courts, whether they have committed a crime or not (Audit Scotland, 2010). Since 2002, the numbers of young people who are 'looked after' has steadily risen from 11,241 in March 2002 to 14,458 by 2021 (Audit, 2010; Scottish Government, 2021). In March 2021 7,959 children were the subject of Compulsory Supervision Orders (CSOs), children are made the subject of a CSO when they meet the grounds for referral under section 67 of the Children's Hearing (Scotland) Act 2011 and are deemed to need state intervention to address issues relating to either care and protection or offence-based behaviours (Scottish Children's Reporters Administration (SCRA), 2021). This amounts to 0.9% of the child population in Scotland and the most common reason for referral to the children's Reporter and for being the subject of a CSO reflects a 'lack of parental care', most children continue to be referred on care and protection only grounds at 85% (SCRA, 2021). The duration of a CSO continues to predominantly reflect 0 – 2 years accounting for 42.7% (3404) but 20.2% (1611) of children continue to require compulsory measures of supervision for five or more years (SCRA, 2021). Despite these high numbers, figures have reduced for the 11th year, but boys (56.6%) are more likely than girls (43.4%) to be referred to the children's Reporter and the most common age for referral continues to be 14 or 15 years (SCRA, 2021).

Audit Scotland (2010) data shows that

...at any given time there are around 1,600 children and young people in residential care. They are among the most vulnerable members of our society and many have complex and challenging needs. Professional practice and work with these children is good in many respects, but not all children get the best quality of care and support. Many do not reach their full potential and go on to have major problems

in later life. This leads to questions about the extent to which councils are fulfilling their corporate parenting role (Audit Scotland, 2010, p. 3).

In 2020 1426 children were placed within a children's unit or residential establishment, while 13,022, most children were looked after at home or within a family style placement (Scottish Government, 2021). Statistics for 2018, the last data available, reflects that more than one third of residential placements were taken up by four out of the 32 local authority areas, these unitary authorities were formed following the enactment of the Local Government etc. (Scotland) Act 1994. This is reflective of Glasgow City (232) 15%, Fife (131) 8%, City of Edinburgh (106) 6% and Highland council (85) 5% (Scottish Government, 2018).

4.5 Who Provides Residential Care and What are The Financial Implications

Local authorities either provide their own residential childcare services or provision is commissioned through a variety of voluntary or private sector organisations (Audit Scotland, 2010). A national framework is in place through Scotland Excel for independent service providers and almost all residential school placements and most of secure care provision is provided by this sector (Scotland Excel, 2021; Audit Scotland, 2010). It is stated that "looked after children who are placed in residential care often have the greatest and most complex needs. The NRCCI (*National Residential Child Care Initiative*) report describes children and young people who are looked after in residential care as having very serious challenging or self-harming behaviours and a range of mental health disorders, complex disabilities and conditions" (Audit Scotland, 2010, p. 7). While this view is supported by others Audit Scotland (2010) reflect that this has resulted in part from medical developments and increased diagnosis for conditions such as autism spectrum disorder (National Audit Office, 2014; Kendrick, Steckley and Lerpiniere, 2008; Rich, 2009).

The cost of residential care for councils is considerable. In England in 2013 £2.5bn was spent on fostering and residential placements for 0.6% of the under 18 population. This equated to £29,000 - £33,000 per annual foster placement, accounting for 75% of placements, and £131,000 - £135,000 per annual residential placement (National Audit Office, 2014). In Scotland

councils spent around £250 million on residential child care in 2008/09. This is 30 per cent of all social services expenditure on children and families and 6.5 per cent of total social services expenditure. It is equivalent to an average of £150,000 per

child each year, although weekly costs vary between around £800 and £5,500 depending on the type of placement and the complexity of the child's needs (Audit Scotland, 2010, p. 7).

Rising costs have meant that while the numbers of children placed within residential care has continued to fall expenditure continues to rise (Audit Scotland, 2010).

4.6 The Regulation of Residential Placements

Despite the emphasis on cost and commissioning, contracts between councils and service providers promote a monitoring and review process designed to ensure that children's needs are met in a way reflective of managerialism (Daniel and Scott, 2019). This is evident in a continued focus on evidence indicators such as the recording of processes such as care plans, rather than their impact. Taylor and White (2000) argue that scepticism in practice has resulted from technical-procedural work that is reflective of proformas, regulation and monitoring designed to promote consistency. This is further supported by the quality framework developed by the Care Inspectorate who regulate social work and social care services as well as inspecting residential care (Care Inspectorate, 2019). Criticisms that inspection processes are systems rather than relationship focussed were restated within the independent care review, but the new framework had already attempted to redress this with a larger focus on care and support and individual care planning as well as reviewing leadership, staffing and the environment; all through a lens of how they are positively impacting on the care of children and young people (Care Review, 2020; Care Inspectorate, 2019). The changing emphasis reflective of a rights respecting approach to engaging children should place them at the centre, particularly when aligned with the health and social care standards (Care Review, 2020; Lightowler, 2020). The principles of the standards promote 'dignity and respect', 'compassion', inclusion, 'responsive care and support' and 'wellbeing' (Scottish Government, 2017b). These principles have built on those identified by Skinner (1992) in 'Another Kind of Home' and within Kent's (1997) 'Children's Safeguarding Review'.

4.7 The Purpose and Provision of Residential Child Care for Children and Young People

Jackson and Martin (1998, p. 569) identify the purpose of residential care as being "to provide a better environment for the child than his or her own parents could have done". This view is not far removed from early perceptions of institutional care which was seen as providing refuge from immoral or defective familial influences in that while there are aspirations for better care,

there is an inference that parents have been insufficient (Chakrabarti and Hill, 2000). Smith (2009, p. 64) however states that “poverty and inequality are perhaps the defining features of children in care and their families”. The location of residential homes is such that distance is seen as impeding family contact when a child has been removed from the family home (Berridge and Brodie, 1998).

Petrie, Boddy, Cameron, Wigfall and Simon (2006, p.5) state that “being separated from family and friends, changing neighbourhoods and spending time out of school are difficult experiences for any child...it helps to explain why almost half of children leave care with no qualifications”. For Mayer (1987, p. 7) it is the separation from parents that is significant. He states that this “leaves (*the child*) feeling abandoned. He asks himself whether he is worthwhile. He wonders what is wrong with him. He feels inferior, rejected, lonely”.

These responses to being apart from one’s family can leave children feeling insecure. In addition, despite numerous attempts to change the narrative around group care, it continues to be seen as necessary for those young people who are troubled (Milligan and Stevens, 2006; Ainsworth and Fulcher, 2006), rather than being seen as a positive intervention strategy in itself where the minutiae of the day-to-day work with children promotes change (Maier, 1987).

Residential care provides both ‘direct’ and ‘indirect’ care (Ainsworth and Fulcher, 2006). Direct care is reflected in personal care, individualised care planning, developmental activities, educative and therapeutic input, everyday counselling opportunities and structures and routines (Ainsworth and Fulcher, 2006). Indirect care is evident in the systems, processes and resources that provide the infrastructure for direct care activities (Ainsworth and Fulcher, 2006). The routines of everyday life within the care setting provide safety and predictability (Treischman, Whittaker and Brendtro, 1969; Emond, Steckley and Roesch-Marsh, 2016), however work patterns, anti-social hours, disturbed sleep, and challenging behaviour can impact on staff morale and consistency (Berridge and Brodie, 1998).

To promote consistency and predictability the relationships described in the previous chapter continue to be crucial to ensuring a child achieves developmental tasks and longer-term good outcomes within residential care (Chakrabarti and Hill, 2000). Responsive caregiving is required to help young people to recover from previous experiences through attachment promoting interventions and secure relationships (Furnival, 2011). Care workers are distinguished from other adult-child relationships as they are actively responsible for the care

of others (Ainsworth and Fulcher, 1981). A dance analogy is used to describe the rhythmic synchronization between the child and adult (Ainsworth and Fulcher, 1981), and it has been highlighted that the relationships formed can impact on successful outcomes (Welch et al., 2018). Welch et al. (2018), in their literature review of the relationships between staff and children within residential care settings, show the importance of relationships. They cite “availability, seeing the young person as positive and trustworthy, offering ‘parental gestures’, continued transitional support, support above and beyond paid duties, feeling valued, and being there for the long-term (Newton, Harris, Hubbard, & Craig, 2017; Sulimani-Aidan, 2017)” as characteristics of relationship-based practice (Welch et al., 2018, p. 8).

Containment’ is used to describe “the processes that help a person to become able to use thinking to manage their experiences and emotions” (Emond, Steckley and Roesch-Marsh, 2016, p. 64). This containment allows staff to hold another’s emotional upset and provide relief enabling the other to manage effectively (Emond, Steckley and Roesch-Marsh, 2016). Emond, Steckley and Roesch-Marsh (2016) state that staff need to be tuned in to their own emotions before they can tune in to those of the child. Care experienced young people have fewer people to fill in the gaps in their history, but carers can be memory keepers promoting identity and life story work (Emond, Steckley and Roesch-Marsh, 2016).

The Care Review listened to many accounts of positive experiences and of people who made a difference to young people’s lives when they were in all forms of care, including residential care (Care Review, 2020c). However, in 1997 Kent stated “residential childcare is not seen in the positive constructive light it should be with the status that children deserve” (Kent, 1997, p. 4). In 2008 the Scottish Government committed “to work with partners to make residential care the first and best placement of choice for those children whose needs it serves” (SIRCC, 2009, p.8) but despite this the negative perceptions of this form of care continues to be evident today. Radford, Dodd, Barter, Stanley and Akhlaq (2013) reflect that there has been a deficit of research in Scotland outwith abuse inquiries, which have plagued perceptions of this provision. Further studies also reflected evidence that found around 8% of Scotland’s children in care experienced sexual exploitation within the year preceding the study (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014). US and European studies reflect that most of the current care population do not experience care giver abuse within the system (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014). Figures in Scotland are lower than the rest of the UK, but they remain considerable with 2 children per 100 in residential care experiencing

some form of abuse (Radford, Dodd, Barter, Stanley and Akhlaq, 2013). This figure compares with 13 – 15 per 100 in England and 10 – 18 per 100 in Wales (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014).

Researchers highlight that most of the scholars who are critical of residential care provision have never worked within the sector or with the young people who live there (Ward, 2006; Smith, 2009). They also indicate that much of the research in the field is not practitioner-led (Ward, 2006; Smith, 2009). Audit Scotland identifies that more research is needed to ascertain what impacts on experiences and long-term outcomes for children and young people who have lived in residential care and there is a view that “even the best care cannot erase children’s earlier life experiences or the difficulties that some of them face, but it should help them to achieve their full potential” (Audit Scotland, 2010, p. 14).

Good outcomes are associated with the leadership within group care having a clearly articulated theoretical and therapeutic orientation and a stable staff team (Berridge and Brodie, 1998). Stable care giving and placements can be a challenge in residential care. The Care Review highlighted that children and young people may experience multiple moves during their time in care and moves can be “accompanied by feelings of loss, sadness, anxiety and a lack of security” (Care Review, 2020c, p. 56). Emond, Steckley and Roesch-Marsh (2016) also reflect on the loss felt by staff and young people when someone transitions, when it is due to breakdown there is also a feeling of failure.

Disadvantage within residential care has been exacerbated due to COVID-19 (McGhee and Roesch-Marsh, 2021). Restricted or limited access to the internet and digital devices left children feeling different, isolated, and stigmatised (Care Review, 2020; McGhee and Roesch-Marsh, 2021). A Freedom of Information request illustrated that a record number of children during lockdown, have died in care (Goodwin, 2021). Between the beginning of 2014 and September of this year, 111 children or young people have died (Goodwin, 2021). Most deaths resulted after young people left care and care experienced young people told the paper that “they had grown up normalising the premature deaths of those around them” (Goodwin, 2021, p. 2).

4.8 Leaving Residential Care

The Scottish Government (2008; 2013) has highlighted that it is widely accepted that care-experienced young people are more likely to need mental health services, to go to prison, become homeless, to have their own children removed and to have issues with substances. Those who experience multiple transitions are more likely to leave care early, have a limited social network and need support to cope with living independently (Scottish Government, 2008, 2013). In recognition of the vulnerability of care experienced young people the Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014 introduced a duty for local authorities to provide 'after care' until the age of 26 offering support, advice and guidance and 'continuing care' until the age of 21 years old, enabling children and young people to remain within their care placement. This support is only enshrined in legislation in England and Wales for young people who are in foster care (Children and Families Act, 2014). It is more reflective of the national average in 2014 when young adults left home at the age of 22 although it was recognised that they are likely to return several times before finally establishing themselves in the wider world (Young Scot, 2014). There is an expectation that young people are prepared for moving on from the outset of their care placement (Children and Young People (Scotland) Act, 2014).

Many researchers and statisticians have highlighted that care experienced young people return to abusive families post care (Bullock, Litte and Millham, 1993; Duncalf, Hill and McGhee, 2013; SCRA, 2017; Scottish Government, 2017). In 2016, 76% of young people accommodated within a residential establishment, including secure care, had family or friends as their leaving care destination (Scottish Government, 2017). In the Duncalf, Hill and McGhee (2013) study youngsters spoke of experiencing isolation, poor accommodation, no formal support and homelessness.

The Scottish Government recognises that care-leaving is a difficult time for all young people whether this be from state care or the family home (Scottish Government, 2008). Young people leaving residential care are more likely to leave home earlier than their peers despite changes to legislation. Young people with multiple placement breakdowns were also found to leave care earlier than those who have a network of social support (Scottish Government, 2013). For these young people there will be an accelerated transition from adolescence to adulthood. The notion of adolescence is not straight forward as it can be seen as the transition from childhood to adulthood, but this perception is associated with puberty that occurs at the start of adolescence, and it has been illustrated that this can range from the age of 9 – 20 years old (Aldgate, 2006; Coleman, 2011).

4.9 Emerging Adulthood

An internet search on the 'transition from adolescence to adulthood' initially resulted in disappointing results as the term is largely used in England to refer to resources and services for young people with disabilities. US studies appeared mainly anthropological but 'aging out of care' is the language used there to describe young people who leave the formal care system (Bynner, 2005; Arnett, 2007; Avery, 2009). While we are familiar with outcomes for young people as studies have shown that care experienced young people have poorer outcomes than the general population, comparisons are not made between these groups developmentally. Aries stated

it is as if, to every period of history, there corresponded a privileged age and a particular division of human life; 'youth' is the privileged age of the seventeenth century, childhood of the nineteenth, adolescence of the twentieth (Aries, 1996, p. 29).

Could it be argued that 'emerging adulthood' is the privileged age of the twenty-first century? Another question that is worth exploring is whether those leaving or out of care experience emerging adulthood but before turning to the data, what is emerging adulthood?

Arnett (2015) argues that sociological notions such as leaving home and getting married are not how young people view their progression to adulthood. He states that the big three international markers of adulthood are accepting responsibility, independent decision making and financial independence, a view that will be supported by some of the participants in this study (Arnett 2007, 2010, 2015). While the universality of emerging adulthood has been challenged, as traditional markers are still viewed as evident in most societies, it can be viewed as not adding value to life stage theory. Life stage theory can already use the term youth or young adult to describe someone not fully matured to adulthood (Hendry and Kloep, 2010; Arnett, Kloep, Hendry and Tanner, 2011). It does however add value to life cycle theory and helps to explore what would be reasonable expectations and aspirations to have for all care experienced young people. The study will illustrate that some young people experience the transition before they reach the age associated with emerging adulthood, 18 – 29 years old, but despite this there is evidence that they may face the same challenges and experiences although the support systems are less dominant.

Arnett coined the term 'emerging adulthood' to describe those young people aged 18 – 29 years old, although some studies use the 18 – 25 years age group, to refer to those who are

neither adolescents, young adults or youths (Arnett, 2006, 2014; Arnett, Kloep, Hendry and Tanner, 2011). The term youth has been associated derogatively with reference to 'yobs' or 'chavs' demonising an age group (Owen, 2012), while these negative associations have not been linked to emerging adulthood although the term has been in use in academic circles since the mid-nineties and is increasingly popular across multiple disciplines (Arnett, 2010). While studies have largely concentrated on American college students, they have found that sociological notions such as leaving home and getting married are not how young people view the progression from adolescence to adulthood (Arnett, 2015; Molgat, 2007; Galambos and Martinez, 2007). Financial independence, responsibility taking and decision-making mark this transition in modern western societies (Arnett, 2015; Nelson, Willoughby, Rogers and Padilla-Walker, 2015).

Arnett (2015) believes that "the transition to adulthood has become so prolonged that it constitutes a separate period of the life course in industrialized societies, lasting about as long as adolescence" (Arnett, 2010, p. xii). Within the USA the five main features of emerging adulthood are: 'identity exploration', 'instability', 'self-focus', feeling neither child or adult and 'optimism'. There is an extended notion of identity formation that supports Erikson (1950). There are three themes linked with identity formation and these are accepting responsibility, the ability to make independent decisions and being economically independent. Whilst cultural differences may emerge there is an assumption that this life experience is universal and critics, such as Hendry and Kloep (2011) believe that Arnett's theory reflects only a small percentage of the population as it does not take account of social class, race, cultural or historical context and as a stage theory they argue that it cannot explain life course transitions. However, Arnett states that he has

...found consistently that, across SES groups, the same four criteria for adulthood end up at the top: accept responsibility for your actions, make independent decisions, become more considerate of others, and become financially independent. Becoming employed full-time ranks relatively low across SES groups, as do the rest of the traditional criteria for adulthood, especially finishing education and marriage. Structural factors matter more for one's subjective of reaching adulthood. African American and Latino emerging adults are more likely than Whites to feel they have reached adulthood, primarily because they are more likely to be from lower SES backgrounds (Arnett, 2006, p. 116).

Arnett (2006) does, however, see having a child as the one life event that appears to exclude individuals from the emerging adulthood developmental stage as this limits the parents opportunity for identity exploration and instead of being self-focused there is a focus on another human being. Being a parent also impacts on the breadth of future possibilities (Arnett, 2006). He found that the emerging adulthood years are a time of great instability; it may be the most unstable stage of the life span. In a poll of 18- to 29-year-olds, 83% agreed with the statement that this period of their lives was full of change (Arnett, 2014).

4.10 Summary

This chapter has explored residential care, firstly by looking at the responsibility of corporate parents. It looked at restrictions resulting from age despite our increased knowledge of brain development and the 'looked after' status that young people can have when living in state care. The chapter discussed different forms of residential placements illustrating that services can be state, independently, or privately run and their cost is considerable when compared to the overall budget allocated to social care. It discussed the regulation of residential care and highlighted that it is measured against a quality framework that has been systems focussed rather than relationship based despite evidence to reflect those relationships are what support good outcomes for children and young people. The ethos, purpose and function of residential care were outlined, and the features of children placed there explored. Residential care should meet the developmental needs of children better than the parents the children have been separated from and to do this there has to be effective leadership within establishments and stable staff teams.

The chapter concluded by discussing young people leaving care and the developmental theory of emerging adulthood that is viewed as the experience of most young people within developed societies. It looked at how prepared young people were for leaving care and societies expectations that they will be ready for adulthood earlier than others within the general population despite their earlier life experiences and potentially impaired social support system (Ainsworth and Fulcher, 1981; Dixon and Stein, 2002a; Dixon and Stein, 2002b; MacDonald, Cruikshank and Ray, 2013). Research evidence reflected that young people experience both a hasty transition and accelerated journey to adulthood (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014; Stein, 2006; Duncalf, Hill and McGhee, 2013). This concludes the literature review chapters and the next part of this thesis will begin by exploring the ethics and methodological features of this PhD.

CHAPTER FIVE: ETHICS AND METHODOLOGY

5.1 Introduction

This chapter will look at the importance of ethics in my research, and the difficulties when trying to engage with young people who have been in residential care and moved on to a variety of settings. These living arrangements were discussed in the previous section. It will illustrate the methods used within this study and why they were selected. I recorded reflections during my research journey, they will be incorporated here, and I hope that they will provide insights into some of the challenges I found when conducting this research and how I was able to overcome them. I will also discuss some of the limitations of this research.

5.2 Ethics

The University of the West of Scotland (2020, p. 3) views ethics in research as ensuring “honesty, rigour, transparency and respect” and for this study ethics is embedded in all areas of the work. The Research Ethics Guidebook (2016) sees the literature review as ethical practice that builds on previously completed work. It can “develop arguments about what needs to be studied, and why” (The Research Ethics Guidebook, 2016, p. 1) and as outlined in Chapters two to four this research has emerged because of a critique of the literature and the identification of gaps in knowledge in relation to what supports the successful transition to adulthood for care leavers in Scotland. The review illustrated that to understand the present and future, it was necessary to revisit and reflect on the past, setting a historical, political, and cultural context reflective of the breadth of the social sciences. While the literature review is crucial it is the actual research that adds to the body of knowledge. When conducting this research it has been important to subject it to scrutiny and rigour and apply theory to the data gathered. The literature review reflected theory sourced from library, Yahoo, Bing, Google, Google Scholar, Researchgate, CYC-net, the Children and Young People’s Centre for Justice, the International Research Network on Transitions to Adulthood from Care (INTRAC), article bibliographies and national newspaper searches.

The UWS’s guidance cites four principles for conducting ethical research (UWS, 2009). These principles involve doing ‘good’, causing ‘no harm’, respecting the right to self-determination and the treating of participants fairly. Moral rules derive from these principles requiring honesty, privacy, and confidentiality (UWS, 2009). Personal data remained confidential throughout the study. I used an encrypted pen drive and once discussions were transcribed,

the Dictaphone and tape were kept within a locked cabinet. This was in place from the outset and all questionnaires and information transcribed was stored on an independent hard drive stored within my home. In addition to confidentiality, Grinyer (2002) talks about the legal guidance reflecting the importance of maintaining anonymity when possible. She further asserts that the Data Protection Act (1998) means that “the consideration of anonymity and privacy is no longer simply a matter of ethics; it can also have legal implications” (Grinyer, 2002, p. 1). There is emphasis on the need to ensure data does not identify the individual although when read by them they may identify themselves (Grinyer, 2002). It is important when securing data that it is not kept for longer than is necessary and that it is accurate and processed in a fair and lawful way. My data has been retained with pseudonyms should it be needed for scrutiny at a later stage in the research process, the university requires data to be stored for ten years for this purpose (UWS, 2016). Participants were asked to select a pseudonym for themselves and only two of them wished me to choose an alias for them. While those taking part in this study were aged between 18 and 29 years old, I have referred to them as young people throughout. This is in no way meant to do anything other than reflect that in comparative terms to the researcher they are ‘young’ people. It must be pointed out however that it is also reflective of a notion of being ‘young’ as opposed to being ‘adult’.

Another ethical consideration that had to be contemplated related to the participants stories and their potential need for support. As with any study a caveat around disclosures that could result in someone being at risk of significant harm was reflected in the information sheet, as details of this nature must be shared with the appropriate authorities (Appendix 1). Stanford University (2016, p. 1) provide debriefing guidelines that state: “debriefing provides more information about the study, gives participants the opportunity to ask questions, and can provide valuable feedback to you about your study”. As well as verbal input, an information sheet was provided in case anything was missed during discussions to ensure that participants made an informed decision about taking part in the research and potential withdrawal from the study (Appendix 1).

5.3 Recruitment

The Social Research Association (2003, p. 14) state that “social researchers must strive to protect subjects from undue harm arising because of their participation in research. This requires that subjects’ participation should be voluntary and as fully informed as possible and no group should be disadvantaged by routinely being excluded from participation”. Young

people who have formerly been looked after can be considered a vulnerable group and the Scottish Government (2013) considers their transition from care as a particularly vulnerable time. To highlight how challenging their experiences can be their voices have to be heard. This was fundamental to the success of this research and safeguards were put in place through the gatekeeper and supportive services identified within the information sheet. Recruitment did not come without its challenges. Some of these challenges I was already familiar with as I had undertaken evaluations and surveys in my workplace when young people were moving on. Stein (2006) highlights that many young people may be disengaging, managing the transition itself or trying to integrate into a new state. Engagement with a researcher may not therefore be considered important in the wider scheme of things.

Within supervision I discussed recruiting from an agency Facebook page where more than 100 young people aged over 16 years old were active, but difficulties around inclusion and exclusion ruled out this group as I acknowledged that the majority moving on from care were not members. This source would also have resulted in research being focussed within a single agency. It was agreed that I would pursue my alternative recruitment source which would involve the use of a gatekeeper who formed part of my professional network and worked within an advocacy agency, referred to as Champions Advocacy Group (CAG) throughout this study. McFadyen and Rankin (2016, p. 1) state that “gatekeepers have a key role to ensure researchers gain access to potential participants and sites for research”. By using a gatekeeper I would be able to reach young people outside my own place of work and across local authorities throughout Scotland. I was not naïve enough to think that recruitment would be without its challenges as I was familiar with the research on outcomes for care experienced people. My reflective diary states that I initially referred to the research group as ‘care leavers’ and while the Independent Care Review highlighted that ‘care experienced’ is not the terminology used by everyone it is how young people referred to themselves within discussions and within the advocacy group (ICR, 2020). I was aware how vulnerable a group they can be on leaving care as research has indicated that they have poorer outcomes than the general population (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014). I also knew from a Third Sector perspective of how difficult it was to retain contact so I had carefully considered how I would access participants for my research. I was aware of several instances where individuals within my professional network had been unable to complete their study, including at PhD level, due to a lack of participant engagement. The study by McFadyen and Rankin (2016) illustrates that even the use of a gatekeeper does not come without its

challenges and researchers need to ensure that gatekeepers are involved from the outset of the research process.

I contacted the conduit for my research in May 2016 and after a series of emails and face to face discussions, initially in September of the same year exploring the purpose and aims of my research, he confirmed in writing in December 2016 that his organisation was happy to engage in my research process if I gained ethical approval (Appendix 2). He advised that this was the first piece of external research to be approved by the agency encouraging me to reflect on what was different about my proposal. I believe the social capital and relationship I had developed with the gatekeeper was an influential factor. I had more than twenty years' experience within the field and a reputation as a child-centred practitioner. This description could equally apply to many of CAGs practitioners, we shared values, commitment, hopes and aspirations for children and young people. The study was also at a PhD level and the conduit stated that CAG felt that it would be of benefit to their agency.

I was aware that there may be difficulties using one source to access participants. The agency could change their policy around research, my gatekeeper could leave, it may limit the experiences of young people sourced as they are all actively involved within advocacy so I networked with an alternative source but they were keen to engage only with insider researchers. I was very fortunate as my engagement with CAG largely went to plan but this helps to highlight some of the barriers to researchers wishing to conduct studies within the leaving care and care experienced field.

My use of a gatekeeper also highlighted potential challenges. While I know that he worked very hard to promote my research, the challenges were evident within the interview with Hamish who was approached by two advocacy members of staff and agreed to do the research after being asked by my gatekeeper who has positional power and authority within his agency. This raised a question for me in relation to integrity and was illustrated in the work reflected by Reid, Brown, Smith, Cope and Jamieson (2018). One of the researchers, Brown, spoke about retaining "lingering doubts as to the extent to which hidden coercive influences impact on participant recruitment" (Reid, Brown, Smith, Cope and Jamieson, 2018, p. 71). I had a sense of this following my first interview when I arrived at the busy office expecting to see four participants but only one arrived. The staff attempted to reach a potential participant through Facebook and while they stated they were reminding him as he may have forgotten the arrangement and I went along with this; it took him not showing up for me to reflect that

he may have changed his mind or not wanted to take part. He advised the worker that this was the case. I knew because of this study group that ethical challenges would be a feature of this research and this has allowed me to question the altruistic integrity I thought was inherent in my research. I had hoped to interview 15 participants, my initial goal was 12 – 15 and I had to question the ethics of continuing to pursue young people who had not chosen to come forward without additional encouragement, so I did not pursue them further.

I produced a poster, participant information sheet and letter in addition to the interview schedule and consent paperwork (Appendices 3, 1, 4, 5 and 6). This was shared with CAG who disseminated some of the information and posters and contacted me regarding young people who had shown interest in taking part in the research. It took 18 months to identify, meet with and interview 13 young people and many of those who originally agreed to be interviewed were subsequently unavailable. Unfortunately, despite our best efforts, no one agreed to reschedule which would suggest that they were not keen to participate in the first place and ethically it would have been wrong to attempt to pursue this further. My criteria appears to have been a barrier to recruitment as I was looking for young people who had experience of residential care within a limited age range. This age range had been selected as it was in keeping with the scope used within Arnett's research into emerging adulthood. Kendrick, Steckley and Lerpiniere (2008, p. 8) highlight that "gaining access to children and young people in residential care is a complex process which involves different stages of discussion and negotiation". This was also my experience of those who had left residential care and the advocacy group believed that they had more young people who accessed their support service with experience of residential care than they had. The gatekeeper identified four additional practitioners to support with my research and without him and his colleagues this research would not have been possible. One colleague put me in contact with four young people in the first instance, one of whom turned up. On the second occasion I was expecting three candidates and one was interviewed. Another colleague linked me to another participant and the gatekeeper put me in contact with four young people all of whom were interviewed. The final CAG colleague invited me to a support group meeting providing me with an opportunity to pitch my research to a roomful of people, I secured three further interviews because of this. I was introduced to a student on placement within CAG from a similar resource and I was encouraged to share my research aims and objectives with a view to acquiring further participants, but this returned no results. I secured two interviews from another member of the CAG team and one young person was identified through a residential colleague who

was familiar with my research. In total I successfully interviewed 13 candidates out of a possible 19 people.

5.4 Ethical approval

I applied for ethical approval from my place of employment in August 2016 but this was deemed by the panel as unnecessary as I would be interviewing young people over 18 years old who may not have lived in residential care within this setting. I received ethical approval for my research from the University of the West of Scotland on the 14th of December 2016. My original application related to two methods and secondary data, however secondary data has not been utilised within this PhD as it did not add value to the overall piece of work.

The first method reflected a short questionnaire designed to gather demographic information. The second method consisted of individual interviews, and I had hoped at a later stage to undertake three to four focus groups with 20 – 30 participants. The focus groups would help me to consolidate the problem and through discussions participants would 'evoke conversations' (Krueger and Casey, 2015). I submitted a revised application to extend the scope of my study to enable me to undertake the additional research, but it became clear I was going to be unable to engage additional people, despite attempting to gain access to additional participants through both a local authority and additional advocacy agency. I had underestimated how difficult recruitment would be but essentially, I had to question the purpose of the groups considering the data already gathered. My research was conducted during a time when a monumental national review of the care system was being conducted involving 5,000 children and young people's voices (Independent Care Review, 2020). While this related to all care settings I felt that a focus on individual narratives would be more powerful considering the discussions within interviews.

I agreed to give participants a £10 Amazon voucher for taking part in the study; this was in consideration of their time and the money was applied for as part of my study grant. All but one of the participants accepted the voucher but a further three did not cash in their voucher, so these was re-sent in May 2020. The Research Ethics Guidebook (2016b) reflects on the controversy around payments for participants. As young people were giving up their time, I felt that it was important to show them a token of my appreciation even though the sum was small. Payments can be viewed as "an inducement to participate (Research Ethics Guidebook, 2016b, p. 1) but I feel that the sum was unlikely to influence participants or have an impact on informed consent, since all the young people who participated were in work and/or training

and the money was given in voucher form via email. Involve (2010, p. 6) state that “payment is a tangible way to acknowledge the value of” contributions by participants. Participants were advised that should they wish to withdraw from the study they would still receive a voucher.

Motivation to participate in research is always a challenge as while I as the researcher may view involvement as beneficial as it may be cathartic or helpful to future residents of group living, those involved may not experience any benefits from the research at all (Ethics Guidebook, 2016). Rohan and Smith (2016) found in their Voices Project study that included consultation in relation to the 2014 Children and Young People (Scotland) Act that of the young care leavers the most enjoyable element of their research was said to be speaking about their experiences. The Research Ethics Guidebook (2016) stresses the importance of being realistic about achievements within social research as the study in itself may not bring “real benefits without time and effort being spent on disseminating and implementing the findings” (P1). While I hoped that this would form part of my overall PhD process, to date this has largely been restricted to changes I have made organisationally and within my professional networks, where I have been able to share my research findings. I have presented to a team of psychologists, delivered a poster presentation to an international audience in Portugal (2018) and contributed as a speaker at a conference on social development in Johannesburg (2021). I was invited to join the International Research Network on Transitions to Adulthood from Care (INTRAC) after the Portugal event, but I have yet to share my findings through publications. This is largely to do with significant work demands during the pandemic but I hope to engage in publications in the future.

My research data was gathered before the pandemic which may have posed additional challenges both practically and emotionally. Newman et al. (2008) conducted a study of 613 college students and found that 1 in 10 found the research more upsetting than they expected it to be. When liaising with the gatekeeper at CAG it was agreed that those involved should largely be trainees or ambassadors as these young people have some distance from their care experiences reducing any likelihood of harm. This was also seen as enhancing my likelihood of recruitment. Researchers and gatekeepers have responsibility for protecting subjects from harm that may result from research (McFadyen and Rankin, 2016). This selection however results in limitations as these young people receive some form of informal support through their involvement with CAG and the findings may not be reflective of the wider residential care experienced group.

I had to acknowledge that participants may have felt pressure to take part in the research due to their involvement in CAG, I tried to minimize the risk of this by ensuring that my information sources highlighted that participation was voluntary and that this could be declined at any time. I felt strongly that staff would ensure that no-one took part in the study without being fully informed of what was involved and without informed consent, but it was evident during my initial engagement that relationships played a part in people's willingness to engage.

Research interviews took place at a time and place convenient to participants. Prior to embarking on meetings, I informed CAG that a meeting had been set up and made my line manager aware that I was conducting interviews. While agency policy does not specify an application to researchers, it recognizes that some staff, volunteers, and contractors work alone and under health and safety legislation they have a responsibility to raise awareness and keep people safe. The aim of the policy includes ensuring staff are equipped to recognize and address risk and to promote practical advice when lone working. It was important that I promoted the safety of both myself and the young people. CAG agreed to allow me access to their premises, and this was used in all but two interviews where I used my own office space and a café. On reflection, having a consistent research base may have reduced some of the minor obstacles I experienced, I will return to this shortly.

I gained informed consent by ensuring that the information sheet for the research was shared with participants. In addition to providing a script of the purpose of the study, its aims and goals, how the information would be stored and used and who would gain access to the data – only the researchers supervisors would have access to the anonymised data, I provided a verbal input outlining the purpose of the study, potential and proposed real benefits to participants. I stated that they could answer any number of the research questions and withdraw from the study at any point. I stated if they withdrew their data would not be used and they would retain their voucher. Participants were given time to digest the information and read the sheet and consent form before this was signed. To ensure reflexivity I sent participants the verbatim data transcription and asked if they were happy with the information recorded. I asked if they would like to reread the transcript prior to me completing the PhD in case they wanted to change anything. Disappointingly there were no responses to these emails, so I have assumed that all parties were happy with what was written. A number of participants have abstractly kept in touch on Twitter, so I am hopeful that they continue to be interested in reading the study's findings.

5.5 Methodology

This study has used a mixed methodology, the first method was the use of a short questionnaire designed to gather demographic information and factual details including duration of stay in care, age and number of placements (Appendix 7). This data allowed me to understand features of the group and ascertain whether these were consistent with other young people who had experienced residential care in Scotland. Bell (2010) states that posted questionnaires have low response rates and greater cooperation is likely with personal distribution. I asked participants to complete the questionnaire prior to the interview and this allowed me to develop rapport as candidates asked questions as they completed the form. Despite the questions being piloted prior to the study there were some questions that were not answered, and this may have been due to the questionnaires design, the box may not have been large enough. Burgess (2001, p. 5) states that “your greatest enemy in survey research may well be poor response rate. Clear and concise questionnaires can help get the best response”. While this will largely relate to quantitative studies, I had asked two colleagues to complete the form. It is something that I would revise if I were to undertake a similar study again.

Prior to compiling the questionnaire, I ruled out the use of a standardized purchased questionnaire. The focus of this research on the transition from adolescence to adulthood resulted in considerable background reading in emerging adulthood and Arnett (2000a, 2000b, 2007) illustrated using a questionnaire how contemporary college students within a range of socio-economic groups and cultures experience this transition. Questions included gathering information regarding sexual experiences and similar sensitive information and this was explored within supervision, and it was agreed that it was too prescriptive and not in keeping with the aims of this study. While it could be argued that sexual and gender identity is particularly relevant at this stage of someone’s life this is something that could be pursued within a follow up study. Arnett’s studies afforded participants credits towards a psychology module which was part of the college curriculum resulting in a very high response rate (Arnett, 2000a, 2000b, 2007).

Some research into care leavers has taken a similar quantitative approach resulting in statistical information reflecting outcomes; this may derive in part from studies being policy driven and government led. I aimed to gather qualitative information and to do this it was easy to determine that interviews were the most effective way to gather the type of information I was looking for. Interview questions were designed to be open ended and “well-structured...

(to avoid) problems at the analysis stage” (Bell, 2010, p. 142). Interviews are adaptable and can allow for observation on how something is presented as well as the actual response itself independent of external variables and the semi-structured format can provide structure facilitating discussion without restricting the narrative (Bell, 2010). Interview questions are included in the appendix and discussions lasted between 12 and 60 minutes and took place face to face with all interviews recorded using a Dictaphone, this was highlighted on the consent form (Appendix 6). Keeping interviews within an hour reduced the risk of participants becoming bored or repeating responses. Whilst other discussion methods, other than face to face, could have been used this was my preferred option to encourage the development of rapport and allow for observation in a way that email or telephone conversations cannot. At a care leavers event ‘stories’ had the most impact on professional participants and I wanted to capture narratives, so this had to be a fundamental element of this study.

Connelly (2003, p. 104) states that

social work most frequently concerns interviewing people, and interviewing skills can readily be transferred across from practice to research. Indeed, it could be argued that social workers have a huge advantage over other beginning researchers in that they have a repertoire of interviewing skills that can be enhanced by training in the particular skills of qualitative interviewing.

My experience within the field of study and social work was invaluable despite being a novice researcher. I knew that my role was not to provide emotional support but signpost to any additional measures as required but it was difficult during the initial interviews to distance myself from my role as helper. I am a safeguarding adviser, have received life space crisis intervention training, am a qualified social worker and social work manager and I am familiar with a range of professional networks that are available to support young people. I was also aware of the role of CAG in this process should the need for support arise and the information sheet I provided illustrated additional supports. At the end of the interview, I asked if participants had any other questions, and I checked in with candidates to ensure that they were alright.

5.6 The participant demographic

Between May 2017 and September 2018, I conducted 13 interviews with care experienced young people aged 18 – 29 years old, all of whom had experienced group care. All of the young people identified as white Scottish/British. The barriers I experienced in the recruitment

process, despite using a strong advocate of the research and conduit within CAG, has been similar to barriers experienced by other researchers who have attempted to engage care experienced youngsters (Jackson and Martin, 1998; Rohan and Smith, 2016), although I found one exception but the participant criteria was much broader than my own, Duncalf, Hill and McGhee (2013) conducted research with those up to the age of 78 years old across a range of care settings. Parsons et al. (2020) speak about methodological weaknesses that result from limited sample sizes but until systems are developed to empower researchers to gain access to multitudes of people, research must continue in this vein.

The demographic of the 13 participants was six young women and seven young men. Their age ranges can be broken down into six 18 – 21-year-olds, four 22 – 26-years-olds and three 27 – 29-year-olds. I used these age differentials due to the different provision by way of social support and educational support made for these age groups within the legal context as set out in Chapter four (Norrie, 1995, Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014). It is not surprising that slightly more young men were interviewed than women as Scotland's Census of 2011 reflects annual Scottish Reporter statistics which state "there were slightly more boys than girls starting episodes of care in 2017, 54% boys compared to 46% girls (Scottish Government, 2018, p. 7). This number has remained steady for several years, but it continues to be the case that boys are more likely to be placed within residential establishments (Scottish Government, 2017, 2018). The young people in the study came from seven of the 32 local authorities in Scotland and a third of the participants came from Scotland's largest local authority.

5.7 Research approaches

The approach I have taken to this study has been determined by my focus on factors that support effective transitions to adulthood. Phillips and Pugh (1993) distinguish between three types of research approaches when undertaking a PhD; 'exploratory' which tackles a new problem, 'testing out' which applies a theory to a set of circumstances, and 'problem solving' where we seek a solution to an established problem. This study is interested in seeking positive solutions to a long-established problem: poor outcomes. Similar studies have been undertaken in relation to educational outcomes for young people looked after at home in Scotland (Fitzpatrick, 2015) and aging out of foster care in the US where outcomes were seen as similar to the outcomes for residential care experienced young people (Avery, 2009). I have taken a problem-solving approach to my research. Phillips and Pugh (1993) describe this as

starting with a particular problem and pulling together intellectual resources to solve the problem. The problem, for this thesis, is that young people formerly looked after within residential childcare have poorer outcomes than their non-looked after peers (Audit Scotland, 2010; Ward and Stein, 2021). A number of studies already highlight these outcomes, but I aimed to look at this problem from a holistic perspective and apply a theoretical framework to the study.

Chilisa and Kawulich (2012) state that researchers have their own perspective about what is knowledge and truth, and this view is reflected in how researchers think about the world and the assumptions that are made. An understanding of 'ontology', 'epistemology' and 'axiology' is crucial here but I am sure for many outside the world of research and academia these terms are alien. So, for me gaining understanding has not been an easy task but an evolution as my research journey developed. Ontology reflects a theory of being and my ontology is post positivist. For Ryan and Walsh (2006) who take a post positivist view of research, the notion of an objective and detached researcher is a myth as how we view the world is influenced by experiences. My theory of knowledge, described as epistemology within the literature, is that there are multiple realities. I take a constructionist view which sees "all knowledge, and therefore all meaningful reality as such, is contingent upon human practices, being constructed in and out of interaction between human beings and their world and developed and transmitted within an essentially social context" (Crotty, 1998, p. 42).

5.8 Theoretical framework

Knowledge will differ depending on the theoretical approach used by the researcher and social constructionist theory reflects that meaning making changes over time, space, and context (Crotty, 1998). Post modernists support a view of the world as contextual, proposing that there is no objective, universal or absolute perspective but multiple claims of legitimacy and truth (Sweetman, 2005). Grant and Osanloo (2014) state that within a qualitative study it is common for the theoretical framework to emerge during the data analysis stage of research, and this has been the case for my study where grounded theory helped me make sense of the data over time.

Grounded theory is described as involving "the progressive identification and integration of *categories of meaning* from data" (Willig, 2013, p. 70). It involves both the method, identification and integration, and the product where categories are identified, linked by established relationships and explained (Willig, 2013). I used this method to code my initial

data. Phillips and Pugh (2005, p. 49) also state it is “the application of theory that turns intelligence gathering into research. It is important to show what my evidence is rather than agreeing or disagreeing with a particular theory. I must explain, show relationships, compare, predict, generalise, and theorise if this PhD is to be of value (Phillips and Pugh, 2005). During the initial stages of data collection, I identified the themes of ‘family and gender’, ‘chaotic lives and negative assumptions’ and ‘emerging adulthood and identity’ as my coding developed.

5.9 Reflections

Reflection forms an important element of any kind of research as it is an evaluative process (Wellington, 2015). On reflection, my experience of doing a PhD involved a number of light bulb moments that have taken the form of: a partial meltdown asking the question do I really know what I’m doing; engulfing myself in more reading which either allowed me to focus on the subject or become distracted from the task at hand; reflective time where I put myself under pressure to perform but sit with the laptop on and do anything rather than work; talking consistently about my research to anyone who wanted to listen and ‘eureka’ or light bulb moments where my reading, reflection, planning and discussions could be applied to my practice and writing. Murray and Lawrence (2000) reflect this process as one that is best

...understood as an enhanced perceptual and cognitive ability – one in which reconsideration, reviews of work done and information gained, consultation with self and significant others, recapitulation and self-criticism blend with insights largely stimulated through confrontation with the obligations immanent in the research methodologies adopted (Murray and Lawrence, 2000, p. 10).

My experience had me questioning the discussions we had as student university undergraduates where we would often talk about Freud and the defence mechanism of avoidance. What I have found, the more I study, is that this avoidance produces reflective periods which have allowed me to absorb the information gathered. I also needed regular feedback from others within academia and practice to enhance my knowledge and learning and to reach my full potential. Reflecting on Vygotsky’s zone of proximal development, I can only become my best self in this area by going through this light bulb process and getting input from others who are able to push me towards a more informed self. My supervisory team have proved invaluable in this process.

The feedback from the transfer event was constructive and enlightening. I was reassured that my journey was leading me along an appropriate path and provided me with input that would keep me on track, not negating the bumps along the road. My tacit knowledge was highlighted, the importance of reflexivity stressed, and the volume of big concepts and the analytical framework explored. The latter of these have been discussed elsewhere so I will touch on tacit knowledge and reflexivity.

5.10 Tacit knowledge

Fundamentally as my research is practitioner-led I am coming from a position of working experience within the environment where my research is grounded. Taylor and White (2000) highlight parallels between social work and qualitative research and my reflective diary highlights how significant this was in my experience.

I realised just how good my engagement skills are today, or are young care experienced people keen to share their stories? Is this due to my network relationships. With all three candidates so far I have managed to break the ice and put them at their ease by using a hook through my active listening skills...The interview left me emotionally drained but on reflection this was more to do with insight gained that made me question my practice, I think. It may also have been difficult because it is not often a stranger opens their heart... (Reflective diary, 4th December, 2017).

Essentially this thesis aims to bring the voices of young people to the attention of practitioners and decision makers who can impact on how we meet the needs of children and young people and promote effective transitions to adulthood. Wellington (2015) talks of 'situated cognition' and 'tacit knowledge' and it was evident within interviews that I spoke a similar language to the young people I interviewed; we had a shared understanding. Wellington (2015) also illustrates that knowledge can be situational and my 25 years' experience working as a residential practitioner provided me with this insider context as well as earned me respect from participants. Polanyi (1966, p. 4) states that "we can know more than we can tell", practitioner knowledge can be difficult to articulate as it may be implicit.

What is shown here is that all knowledge is not explicit (Polanyi, 1966; Wellington, 2015). Polanyi (1966, p. 25) illustrates that tacit knowledge needs the researcher to have "a compelling sense of responsibility for the pursuit of a hidden truth". Both the commitment to

knowing the truth and sharing it have been drivers for me to complete this PhD. Knowing that these young people's stories need to be shared has motivated me when my enthusiasm has stumbled. I imagine that this is a feature of any writing of this magnitude. I also believe that I have a unique perspective in residential care having been firmly involved in promoting young people's participation, agency and voice throughout my career. My practitioner-researcher academic position is relatively unique.

5.11 Reflexivity

For Wellington (2015, p. 101) "reflectivity and the more specific reflexivity are vital (but different) parts of the research process". The extent of self-analysis and critique involved in the writing up of a research study is contested and varies from being seen as essential to being viewed as a form of arrogance that can compromise how the research itself is viewed by others (Troyna, 1994 in Wellington, 2015). Within my own work the ongoing reflection touched on above I hope allows the reader and assessor greater insight in relation to my own values and bias within the study but, ultimately, I must not lose sight of what the research is about and must ensure that it is the voice of participants that is heard and the critical analysis and understanding of the data that provides the original contribution. The epistemological perspective of reflexivity sees knowledge as a constructed ongoing developmental process as the research unfolds (Reid, Brown, Smith, Cope and Jamieson, 2018). They say that "transparency about the researcher's position and potential biases and assumptions is vital in judging accounts of qualitative research and the authenticity of the findings" (Reid, Brown, Smith, Cope and Jamieson, 2018, p. 70).

While Wellington (2015) is writing about educational research his views of the research position apply to my situation. When referring to position and assumptions he states we must firstly examine our own position in relation to the research, I have done this by setting out my 'positionality' when reflecting on my personal and professional experiences, but my philosophical perspective may be less clear. In Chapter three I introduced Jenks 'Apollonian' and 'Dionysian' philosophical conception of childhood and I firmly stand with the 'Apollonian' and Rousseau view that children are born good and they are active agents who should be nurtured. In keeping with my values, I also believe that people have the capacity to change and overcome adversity while recognising that social structures can impair people's ability to reach their full potential. These views would firmly route me in the constructionist ontological perspective where I believe that there are multiple truths, and the interpretivist epistemological

perspective as I believe that reality relies on subjective interpretations (Crotty, 1998). The constructionist view in this context reflects that knowledge is reliant on the interaction between individuals and their world and therefore a social context (Crotty, 1998). Meaning making therefore evolves from the sense we make of the world.

Wellington states that we must secondly examine organisational assumptions and here he identifies barriers to insider research as “an outsider may sometimes be better placed to question and examine” (Wellington, 2015, p. 102) values and assumptions than an insider, I do not agree with this assertion as there is a suggestion that we cannot critique within our own field, I will discuss this further in the next section. The third element results from the need to challenge language and question whether this means the same to different people. I will return to this when discussing the data in Chapter seven.

Reid, Brown, Smith, Cope and Jamieson (2018) reflect on their own experiences as ‘practitioner-researchers’. Being a practitioner-researcher results in a working knowledge of the study at hand and results in a “shared identity with participants” (Reid, Brown and Smith, 2018, p. 70) which can be seen as a valuable position to be in when seeking to develop ‘practice insights’ but it can result in ‘assumptions and biases’ being made that may have ethical implications. I cannot underestimate the impact of the relationship I had with Billy as insiders within the field, although not solid at the beginning of the research process, I had had various contacts with Billy over a ten-year period. We shared a passion and commitment that reflected a ‘common bond’ which made him a good fit when I was initially considering a gatekeeper. This common bond reflects a shared knowledge and experience but also a language that is spoken by practitioners and residents involved in the residential field (Wellington, 2015). I would find this insider language invaluable during interviews.

5.12 Emic-etic perspective

Olive (2014) reflects on the tensions between what is described as emic (insider) and etic (outsider) perspectives in research. My insider status in the field of residential care for children afforded me unique access due to my relationships within the field of study, my gatekeeper Billy advised me that his agency received dozens of research proposals every year yet mine was the only one accepted. Gaining access to participants for any research project is a challenging task but I had no idea that it would take more than a year to organise and have the gatekeeping arrangements in place. Perseverance in this area paid off.

Coming into this study I was aware that I was a relative expert in my field with 25 years of experience working in the frontline of residential childcare services. For me that meant I had a developed understanding of the theory, skills, and practice of the social care sector and that there was not a problem I had not faced before or overcome. What I had not given a lot of consideration to was what I was bringing to the research process despite this being discussed at university supervision, the feedback at the transfer event really brought my tacit knowledge. Tacit knowledge is not held by someone outside a field and this is not something easily acquired. I had spent most of my adult life sharing experiences with children and young people in their living space and I also believe that I was able to convey how much I cared about the study and its' purpose. The aim of the study was to change practice to improve the experiences for other children living in residential care or moving on from this provision.

5.13 Power differentials between the researcher and participants

Within the interviews I assumed as the researcher I was in a position of power, although I recognised the power individuals had to engage or not engage in the process. Reid, Brown, Smith, Cope and Jamieson (2018, p. 72) talk about 'power asymmetry' being "a feature of research with the balance generally considered to be in favour of the researcher who directs the process while the participant responds". It is also argued that "power is actually co-constructed through the process, as participants exert power in shaping knowledge through choosing what to reveal" (Reid, Brown, Smith, Cope and Jamieson, 2018, p. 72) and an example was cited in practitioner research when a respondent went off script and began to talk about issues he was experiencing within the workplace, using the interview process as a means to share professional grievances. On that occasion the researcher kept to task, but I found myself in a not dissimilar situation with Bruce in interview six.

To increase the opportunities for me to meet with participants I offered to meet at a place of their choice using my lone working experience to ensure that this was appropriately risk assessed. I met with Bruce in his supported accommodation placement which was busy and although we had a private space to conduct the interview there was noise coming from outwith our room. I committed a massive research faux pas and did not start the Dictaphone, this distraction was not a feature of other interviews. As this was one of two interviews conducted at the time, I did not realise this until a few days after the interview. While Bruce agreed to be re-interviewed throughout the second interview he was distracted and irritable, so I asked him if he was alright. I knew in doing this I was pushing the boundaries of research as I was not

there as a counsellor or member of staff but as Bruce had responded differently in the previous interview, I felt partly responsible for his irritated state. I listened and reassured him signposting him to appropriate others for support and continued with the interview.

Having worked with people most of my adult life my effective communication skills are well developed. Having worked with many traumatised young people and adults I am emotionally intelligent and able to effectively manage conflict. I was able to read body language and social cues and use encouragement techniques within the interviewing process. Having engaged young people and staff in a range of group and one to one sessions, this element of the research came relatively naturally to me. As was the case with Billy there is a common bond evident with people who have experience of group care. A shared language and understanding that I had not thought about before conducting this research.

5.14 The rationale for the study and research questions

Gaps in current research have been outlined in previous chapters and include the relative absence of a theoretical framework in leaving care research (Avery, 2009; Stein, 2006; Pinkerton, 2021). A social constructionist theoretical framework underpins this study, it recognises that knowledge is socially constructed and results from the interplay between human practices and interactions with the wider world which suggest that there are multiple truths or interpretations (Crotty, 1998). Post modernists however view knowledge and truth as relative and Lyotard (1984) separates what he refers to as philosophers from experts, the latter of which he views as limited in their knowledge and understanding as they view things through a particular lens. My epistemology throughout this study is grounded in a critical approach. It recognises the impact powerful institutions play in the dominance of particular discourses, although there is an argument that human agency can impact and challenge this dominance (Andrews, 2012). However, as many sociologists have indicated the subservient nature of being a child compared to that of an adult, results in them having relatively less power and capital than their grown-up counterparts (Corsaro, 2011; Qvorstrup, 1999). This study will illustrate the agency and autonomy young people have experienced and I hope for future young people the Scottish Government's adoption of the UNCRC bill into domestic law will see an increased focus and embedding of children's rights in policy and practice moving forward (UNCRC Bill team, 2021).

In addition to a lack of a theoretical framework there is a relative absence of positive reports around the benefits of group living (see Henderson, 2020; Forester et. al, 2009 for exceptions).

Most studies in the field are conducted by professional researchers and academics (Stein, 2006; CELCIS, 2014; MacDonald, Cruikshank and Ray, 2013; McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014) and although there is some evidence of care experienced research (Duncalf, Hill and McGhee, 2013; Rohan and Smith, 2016), there is a deficit of practitioner research which this study will help to address. Theoretically throughcare and aftercare literature rarely engages with the emerging adulthood debate (McGhee, 2019), and most research that looks at transitions across care focuses on placement moves, breakdowns or changes in the milieu (Smith, 2005; Smart and Digby, 2015; Brendtro, 2015; Henderson, 2020); research rarely looks at the entire care journey with a specific focus on the journey into, experience within and outcomes after leaving care making this study relatively unique. For an exception, Gabriel, Keller and Bombach (2021) undertook 37 interviews in a Swiss study of residential care experienced adults viewing their journey as a lifelong process. They reached out to individuals who experienced residential care between 1950 and 1990 providing retrospective insight. There is also a deficit of research of this nature undertaken in Scotland, so the aim of this study is to contribute to the body of knowledge in the field (Stein and Dixon, 2006; Jackson and Cameron, 2012; Duncalf, Hill and McGhee, 2013; McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014; McGhee, 2019).

The evolution of the research questions and why I chose the questions that follow needs to be explained. Bell (2010) states that literature reviews need to be concise and present a picture of the nature of knowledge and significant questions of the topic under study. As this research explores effective transitions including the transition to adulthood reading in emerging adulthood has helped to illustrate how this was experienced (Arnett, 2000a; 2000b; 2007), but to understand this for a care experienced youngster it was important to consider their journey towards adulthood. It is important to restate my research questions before discussing the data. These are:

1. What are the early childhood experiences of young people who are placed in residential care in Scotland?
2. To what extent are young people supported to understand these experiences?
3. To what extent do young people get what they need from residential care?
4. To what extent are young people prepared for leaving residential care and what supports a successful transition?
5. Does the theoretical framework of emerging adulthood add to our understanding of their transition to adulthood?

5.15 Interview Participants: Group Composition

Data Chart One (p. 74) provides demographic information for the research participants that was largely gathered through the details provided within the study questionnaire. The data that follows in the forthcoming chapters result from the thirteen semi-structured interviews. It took an average of just under six minutes to complete the questionnaires and midway through the interview schedule I ensured that all engagement was taped from the outset as it became evident that candidates started talking at the beginning of the research process and it was more effective for this to be taped than for me to record it in a reflective diary after the event. Interviews 6 – 8 took place outwith the allocated office making it more challenging to put the tape on from the outset when I had to put the candidate at their ease first to facilitate an effective interview. With hindsight future research should be consistently recorded from the outset to ensure that no important information is lost. As mentioned previously, difficulty with the recording equipment resulted in me completing the interview with participant 6 twice. On the second of these occasions, he was less engaged in the process and I blurred the boundaries of worker/researcher when he spoke about anxiety he was having about his future and I found myself providing him with reassurance and offering to share his concerns with a manager. I have attached a brief overview of the interviews in the appendix, but an abridged version follows the chart below (p. 75 - 77).

Chart One: Interview participants questionnaire demographic data

NAME	AGE	YM/YW	RACE	IN AGE	NO. PLACE (YR RESSIE)	OUT AGE	FROM	TO	RELAT	CONT	EDUC LEVEL	EXPLANATION	INTERV. TIME	LA
1 Luna	19	Young Woman	NSW	13	4 (4Yr)	18	RC	SA	“	NO	COLLEGE	NO	22.49//	LA1
2 Lisa	22	Young Woman	NSW	12	6** (.5Yr)	16.5	SC	OT	£	YES	COLLEGE @~<	YES Own safety	20.38//	LA2
3 Carol	24	Young Woman	W/S	6	4 (6Yr)	18	RC	OT	£ \$	YES	SVQ3>? ONGOING	YES Home unsafe/ mothers alcohol issues	13.41	LA3
4 Tania	20	Young Woman	British	0	18**(4Yr)	17.5	RC	OT	\$	YES	COLLEGE ONGOING @~<	NOT SURE WHAT IS TRUE “I was in one residential unit and I got told I was going to be in for the weekend and I was actually there for four and a half years.	16.57	LA3
5 Kevin	22	Young Man	W/S	10	2 (8Yr)	18	RC	Sc	%	NO N/All	DEGREE~>	YES	52.15	LA1
6 Bruce	18	Young Man	W/S	U/K	5+**(6Yr)	18	SA	OT	^&	YES	SECONDARY SCHOOL	YES Didn’t want to say	6.37//	LA4
7 Mark	19	Young Man	W/S	15	1 (2Yr)	17	SA	SF	**	YES	COLLEGE ONGOING	YES	8.17//	LA5
8 John	20	Young Man	W	12	1 (7yrs&1 SA)	20	SA	OT	“	YES	COLLEGE<>	YES Don’t remember	13.36//	LA3
9 Hamish	29	Young Man	W/S	9 (14)	2 51**(5)	19.5	SA	OT	^	YES	APP UNI@~<>	YES Temp for own protection. “I was meant to be in for three days”	36.18	LA1
10 Liam	27	Young Man	W	11	15**(5)	21	Sc	OT	^	YES	SVQ3@<	YES Not in detail	38.25	LA1
11 Tina	20	Young Woman	W	3.5	14 (13.5)	19.5	RC	OT	“	YES	DEGREE ONGOING ~<	YES For years I thought my fault but “ explained it was how my mother treated us. “12 years relationship	33.16	LA3
12 Amy	24	Young Woman	S	15	5 (1)	16	SA	OT	+”	+ Only	SVQ3 ONGOING~	NO Not in detail	22.37	LA6
13 Bob	27	Young Man	S	6	2 (6)	18@	SA	FH	^	NO N/All	SVQ3 ONGOING@~>	NO	20.53	LA7

NSW – Not disclosed Scottish White, W/S = White Scottish. SC = Secure Care, RC = Residential Care, SA = Supported Accommodation, Sc = Supported Carers, OT = Own Tenancy, SF = Student Flat, FH = Family Home. “=Member(s) of staff, £=School teacher(s), \$=Unit staff, %=Unit management, ^=Key worker, &=Social worker, *=Peers, +=Throughcare worker. @also completed non-academic practical training; <wants to/works in the care sector, ~works with care experienced youngsters, > involved in policy development. **=Total placements, ()Years in residential care. //tape started after participants had completed the questionnaire with 5.45 mins on average to complete this. LA = Local Authority regions.

5.16 Luna: Interview one

Luna is a 19-year-old young woman who experienced four residential placements after she was accommodated at the age of 13. She lives within supported accommodation and sees herself as a care leaver as she is no longer in the residential unit. She has siblings who remained at home with her mum when she was taken into care.

Lisa: Interview two

Lisa is aged 22 years old and she is the only married participant, this is unusual as social trends reflect the average age for marriage is 35.7 years. She spent six months within secure accommodation after several foster placement breakdowns. After four and a half years in care she left at 16.5 years and moved on to her own tenancy. She parents her younger sister who lives with her.

Carol: Interview three

Carol is 24 years old, and she spent 12 years in a range of care placements, including six years within residential care. She has sustained her own tenancy for nine years and continues to have ongoing contact with staff from her previous children's unit. This appeared to be a feature for those who lived in local authority residential care.

Tania: Interview four

Tania is a 20-year-old who has experienced 18 placement moves having come into care post birth. She is part of a large sibling group of nine, all of whom were in the care system. She left her residential placement at 17 and a half to move into her own tenancy and she stated she struggles to trust adults.

Kevin: Interview five

Kevin is 22 years old, and he was accommodated when he was 10 with his older brother, they were placed in a children's unit together. He moved to supported carers from his residential unit after being there for more than seven years. He experienced three placements and he now flat shares. He has a negative view of the care system.

Bruce: Interview six

Bruce is the youngest participant at 18 years old, he spent six years within his residential placement and experienced more than five transitions. He moved to his own tenancy from supported accommodation, and he had siblings who did not experience care.

Mark: Interview seven

Mark is aged 19 years and the only participant to experience one placement, a residential unit for two years. He moved on to supported accommodation which he viewed as leaving care. He had older siblings who were not in the care system.

John: Interview eight

John is 20 years old and experienced one residential placement after his kinship care placement ended. He spent seven years in this placement moving to supported accommodation for one year before securing a tenancy, he viewed supported accommodation as still being in care. He had another sibling who was in an alternative kinship care placement.

Hamish: Interview nine

Hamish is the oldest participant at aged 29 years old. He spent five years in a children's unit but he was initially accommodated at age 9 with his younger brothers. Hamish experienced 51 transitions which included kinship care placements.

Liam: Interview ten

Liam is 27 years old and he went into care at 11 years old, experiencing more than 15 placements and spending five years in residential care. He was removed with his siblings who have not fared as well as him and Liam recently became a parent. He left his supported carer placement at the age of 21.

Tina: Interview eleven

Tina is aged 20 years and she was taken into care when she was three and a half years with her younger sister, her older siblings were all in care. Tina experienced 14 placements and left her residential unit for her own tenancy six months ago. She continues to visit.

Amy: Interview twelve

Amy is 24 years old, and she went into care at 15 years after a few years living with kinship carers. She is an only child and had her own child at aged 17 years, a year after she left care to move into her own tenancy.

Bob: Interview thirteen

Bob is aged 27 years and he went into care at the age of 6 experiencing two placements, a residential unit and supported accommodation. He left his supported accommodation

placement at the age of 18 and returned to his family home. Bob's brother was never taken into care.

5.17 Summary

This chapter highlighted the methodology used for this research which results from a short questionnaire and thirteen in-depth semi-structured interviews with young people in Scotland aged between 18 and 29 years at the time of the interviews. Each of the interviews were recorded between May 2017 and September 2018 and the data that follows in future chapters results from discussions that lasted an average of 26 minutes. The duration of the interview did not determine the quality of the data and I am indebted to participants for their openness and honesty, and I feel honoured to be trusted to share their experiences; this has helped to keep me motivated over the past six years. All the interviewees had experience of living within group care settings; either residential or secure care placements, and all of them described themselves as having left care.

This chapter has also illustrated the ethics process involved in this research. It has highlighted the importance of the use of a gatekeeper and how this enabled me to engage with a range of participants, although research has shown that this is not an easy process. Three methods were discussed as well as the recruitment and selection of participants. The challenges in recruitment were identified and obstacles experienced in part due to the inexperience of the researcher as well as not having a secure base from which to conduct the research.

The importance of reflexivity and positionality as a practitioner-researcher-academic were discussed and tacit knowledge that both enabled this research to take place and made it more achievable were highlighted. This cannot be underestimated as barriers to research with this group of participants has been illustrated across other research studies indicating why there is a dearth of qualitative care leaving research. It is now time to turn to the heart of this study and the data chapters, starting firstly by exploring candidates' early life experiences.

CHAPTER SIX: Early Life Experiences of Family and State Support

6.1 Introduction

The next three chapters will look at my data and illustrate the findings of this study while focussing on the areas outlined in the previous chapter. This chapter will look at the beginning of the journey into care by exploring young people's experiences within the family and the circumstances that brought them to the attention of the authorities. It will show that for many young people, their early life reflects experiences of multiple care givers and attachment relationships that are not enduring. Experiences of shame and blame are explored, and young people discuss placement changes described as transitions throughout the literature (Smith, 2005; Smart and Digby, 2015; McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014; Stein, 2006), but this term will be challenged as this is not how the young people reflect on changes to their circumstances and living arrangements. The potential impact on the child will also be explored as participants share their experiences as children and we begin to discover the impact of adversity and trauma on their childhood development. So, let us firstly turn to the family and the composite make up of this 'institution' for participants in the study.

6.2 Family Ideology and Composition

Notions of 'family' are intrinsically linked, in the Western world, to the dominant discourse of familial ideology where the view of what constitutes a normal formation, and ideal family type perceived as mother, father and children continues despite research and statistics reflecting the evolution of family form over time (Parsons, 1961; Bernardes, 1985; McNeill, Blundelle and Griffiths, 2003; Scottish Census, 2011). The ideology suggests that this family type, which is largely based on middle-class values, is better than others; it is seen as functional for society as it promotes gender roles within the family where traditionally men are the primary breadwinners and women take on an unpaid role where they have significant responsibility for the nurture and socialisation of children and meeting the emotional needs of their husband (Parsons, 1961; Seidman, 2008). Within this study only Liam and Bob (Interviews ten and thirteen), had experience of living with both biological parents and brothers and sisters immediately before being taken into care, while Hamish lived within a re-constituted family consisting of mother, her partner, and children (Hamish, Interview nine). Two out of these three participants would not be described as having experienced the traditional family where father goes out to work as their male figureheads engaged in criminal activity that brought them to the attention of the police and the courts. Hill (2012) states that one of the roles of the family is to ensure the economic survival of the unit but access to legitimate means of doing

this can be more challenging within some communities. Squires and Goldsmith (2017) talk about the 'precarity trap' that results from criminal behaviour that may lead to individuals with criminal convictions and potential terms in prison having reduced career and employment opportunities. The parents of participants in the study known to criminal justice services were also described by participants as having issues with drugs and alcohol which may have also influenced their motivation to commit crimes.

The census in Scotland is completed every ten years and illustrates that the most common household is not a traditional family unit, but a home that consists of single adults (National Records of Scotland (NRS), 2018). In 2011 the data showed that 35% of all households were made up of a single-family unit and the Scottish Household Survey showed that by 2016 this number had increased to 37% reflective of an increasingly aged population (NRS, 2018). Unlike a family which is seen as having a biological connection – although Chapter one has shown that this is not always the case - a household is described as one or more person living together who are not necessarily related (National Statistics, 2018). Amy is the only participant who spoke about living with someone who was not a relative, she moved in to live with a neighbour when her family were not able to look after her (Amy, Interview twelve). The census also illustrates that 'lone parent households' are reflective of 11% of Scotland's 5,295,403 population (Scottish Census, 2011). 54% of participants in this study lived within lone parent households, when including the two participants who spoke about their grandmother also providing support in relation to their care. The extended family unit was important for young people in this study and grandmother was described as playing a role in the parenting of four of the participants, either directly or in caring for a sibling and for two of the participants, an aunt played a role. Chart Two reflects the family composition for all participants before they were taken into care. While this information is of significance, Treanor (2016) stresses that it is stability rather than family composition that is important for the wellbeing of a child.

Chart Two: Family composition before being taken into care

6.3 Economic Circumstances and Family Monitoring and Surveillance

In 2011, 26% of all households contained at least one dependent child and there were one million dependent children living within 614,000 families (Scottish Government, 2019). The Scottish Government (2019) data reflects that one in four children reside within households living below the poverty line and although the Child Poverty (Scotland) Act 2017 aims to reduce poverty by the year 2023, Corlett (2019) of the Resolution Foundation believes that the Government are unlikely to meet their targets. A low income from poorly paid and unstable work or state benefits could result in a family living in poverty. There are parallels here with experiences of poverty under the Poor Law discussed in Chapter three. None of the participants discussed their economic circumstances when growing up. It is difficult to make comparisons here with other looked after children as economic information is not recorded as part of the Scottish Government or Scottish Children’s Reporters Administration annual data collection. However, the Joseph Rowntree Foundation (2021) data shows that figures for those of working age in 2011 reflected workless households in Scotland of 21%, reducing slightly to 18% by 2019. The figures for participants appears to be reflective of 100% workless for the parents the young people lived with before going into care with none of the participants mentioning their care givers as being in any form of employment, education or training. This would indicate the increased likelihood of residential care experienced young people coming from low socio-economic families with limited or no experience or opportunity to work.

The policing of the family, by way of monitoring and surveillance, is reflected in government policy and social initiatives which can be seen as consistently reflecting a view of certain families within society that is negative as is seen in the view of the 'dysfunctional family' in need of state intervention evident in 'problem families' or the 'troubled families' initiatives which predominantly impacted on the poorest members of society (Welch, 2018; Welshman, 2017). The old notion of 'what goes on behind closed doors' being a private matter is no longer relevant as we increasingly become aware of the impact this can have on children (Scottish Government, 2014; 2018), and, when intervention is necessary, the cost to the public purse (Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008). The 'troubled families' program is believed to mark a move in neoliberal politics from the need for containment or rehabilitation to that of rescue (Welch, 2018; Welshman, 2017). In this study, for 30% of participants they had social work involvement before being removed into the care of the state and 36% moved between family members before moving to more formal arrangements. Taylor and Rogaly (2007, p. 433-434) state that in the 1950s "social work theory emphasized the essential individuality of each client's problem", and they reflect that despite the rediscovery of poverty it's cause was largely attributed to individual 'failure' instead of structural inequalities (Taylor and Rogaly, 2007), I will return to this in Chapter seven when discussing the impact of austerity and the economic climate on job security, particularly for young people and emerging adults, but many of the families related to this study experienced adversity.

The cause of poverty is not reflected in the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation which splits Scotland into 6,976 zones comprising of 760 people reflecting 'data zones.' Multiple deprivation is not just about poverty but includes people's limited access to resources and opportunities (Scottish Government, 2016). It is recognized that this is a relative measure of deprivation. It offers invaluable insight into the circumstances for the Scottish population but predictions that social policy initiatives will not end child poverty within government timeframes do not engender optimism that opportunities will be increased (Corlett, 2019). The most recent study illustrates that pockets of the populations within Glasgow, Inverclyde, Renfrewshire, Dundee, Stirling, North Lanarkshire, and East Ayrshire are in greatest need of support and intervention due to their relatively high levels of multiple deprivation (Scottish Government, 2016). Only two young people within this research lived outwith these areas. The 2016 study also found that 66% of people who experience income deprivation do not reside in deprived areas. This could reflect low income working families and some of the 33% of children and families during 2017 – 2018 who received emergency parcels from food banks (The Guardian, 2018). The SIMD study shows that "people who live in the most deprived areas are most likely

to experience conditions which limit their opportunities in life” (Scottish Government, 2016, p. 12). While the young people within my study did not explicitly discuss the material circumstances within their families, they did discuss the other issues associated with adversity I will return to shortly. Only one of the participants had lived in an area that had a low level of deprivation and this young person experienced public school education before being taken into care. This would suggest that state intervention within the private domain of the family is linked to class and socio-economic group, although there is limited statistical information that reflects this in relation to this group as neither the Scottish Government nor Scottish Children’s Reporter’s Administration collect demographic information of this nature about referrals to social work services or the Reporter and a referral to the Reporter is generally a precursor to formal state intervention. For agencies to identify appropriate interventions this issue has to be addressed.

Socio-economic status can be affected by family size as people try to make effective use of scarce resources. Chart Three (page 84) illustrates other siblings who lived within the household before the young people were taken into care and it is evident that two young people, described in Scotland as 18 – 26 years old, came from families with five or more siblings (Scottish Government, 2018).

Chart Three: Brothers and sisters living in the household

6.4 Early life experiences

I have looked at family forms for young people within this study and households more generally and highlighted economic challenges. It is internationally accepted that children “should grow up in a family environment” (UNICEF, 2010, p. 1). This view is promoted by all childcare legislation in Scotland and is underpinned by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), 1989 which was ratified in the UK in 1991 and as previously indicated Scotland endorsed the UNCRC bill in 2021 putting children’s rights at the forefront of policy and practice. The environment should be nurturing and loving, promoting warmth to meet the child’s needs resulting in healthy human development (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1988; Kellmer Pringle, 1986; Maslow, 1970; UNICEF, 2010). For developmental growth the child must experience a sense of safety and security, widely recognized as achieved through a relationship to a significant other who promotes a positive relationship by providing stimulus for growth that results from the adult being attuned to the baby’s needs (Bowlby, 1988; Maslow, 1970; Allen and Duncan Smith, 2008; Allen, 2011). In Western societies these needs are likely to be met within the family. Brendtro and Mitchell (2015) highlight that within indigenous kinship systems across the globe, children are likely to grow up with multiple parental figures which may be similar to the experiences of some participants described in this study. There is worldwide recognition that in most societies children will be raised by more than parental figures reflected in the sentiment of ‘it takes a village to raise a child’ (Seymour, 2006).

Carol was removed from the family home at the age of six years old having been known to social work services from birth (Carol, Interview three). From the beginning of life, a child’s wellbeing is bound up in social relationships (UNICEF, 2013; Bowlby, 1974), and while Bowlby initially believed that these relationships were essentially maternal, it was subsequently highlighted that a variety of connections are at the heart of positive human relationships (Mead, 1969; Rutter, 1979). Carol had experienced a number of parental figures as she had been moved between the care of her mother and the kinship care placement with an aunt illustrating that social workers had tried for several years to keep her within her birth family, but these separations – even when necessary to keep her safe from harm, will have impacted on her early experience of feeling nurtured and her ability to form trusting relationships (Carol, Interview three). Erikson (1963) states that relationships are formed in the first developmental stage from birth. It is recognized that alcohol and substance using parents are not always able to provide the consistent care conducive with secure relationships but within the Scottish Government good practice guidance, ‘Getting Our Priorities Right’ (2013), problematic alcohol

and drug use is viewed as treatable with early and supportive intervention seen as an appropriate response. The guidance promotes building on strengths such as the extended family while assessing the needs and risks to every child within the household with a focus on the potential impact the problem may have and the immediate risks, but where possible the best place for a child is seen as remaining within the family. Carol said that she was placed in care for her own safety as her mother prioritized her own needs but like many of the participants in this study father was absent from the narrative. A longitudinal study in Avon highlighted the importance of both parents, in the promotion of positive role models, in relation to the good long term mental wellbeing and development of children (Opondo, Redshaw, Savage-McGlynn and Quigley, 2016), but Ward and Stein (2021) have highlighted that historically policies made it easy for relationships to be severed from parents.

Like Carol, Tania was known to statutory agencies from the time she was born, and she also experienced early kinship placements. Part of a large sibling group, when the family were removed from home, she was initially identified as appropriate for adoption, and it appears that early decisions around permanency planning had a significant impact on her relationship with the wider family in both the short term and the longer term. In the short term she was separated from her brothers and sisters and by the time it was realized that adoption was not an option, they were settled in alternative placements. The relationships did not recover from this, and she now only has contact with one of her sisters. Tania said, “at the start they wanted to get me adopted but then they started going against it” so she rejoined some of her siblings who had been kept together in a foster placement before the group were split up and she was eventually placed in group care (Tania, Interview four). Tania blamed the system for separating her from her siblings as she stated that they should never have been split up from them in the first place. She does not understand why she was taken into care and although she said attempts were made by professionals to explain the rationale, she felt that much of what was said to her was lies (Tania, Interview four). This experience was not unusual for this participant group.

Tina lived with her mother and younger sibling prior to them both going into care. Like Tania she was part of a larger sibling group, and her brothers and sisters were all removed from the family home when she was around the age of one year old, due to their parents' issues with alcohol. Tina struggled to understand why she was left with her mother until she was aged three, she felt that somehow, she was not as important as the rest of her family, as she believes that she was removed aged three due to concerns around her younger sister (Tina, Interview eleven). She said: “my mum was the reason I was in care...I didn't meet my dad

until I was 14 years old” (Tina, Interview eleven), all her siblings were adopted, two of them by a member of the extended family and while she initially had contact with this family group, she said that this was inconsistent. She said of her family, I

...felt kind of estranged from them cos they would hold my behaviour against me, like the way I worked through my trauma, they kind of didn't realise it was because of that and it wasn't just because I was a 'bad kid', so they didn't want to meet me anymore (Tina, Interview eleven).

This added to Tina's overall sense of rejection. I will return to the issue of being a 'bad kid' in the next data chapter but feeling abandoned and to blame for being in care was a theme amongst the young women who were interviewed for this research but not the young men; young men were more likely to blame factors outwith themselves and their families to explain why they were in care. This is consistent with research into adolescence that reports boys are more likely to externalise and girls to internalize feelings when stressed, although gendered expectations can be highly influential in these findings (Kort-Butler, 2006). While Tina spoke about it being her mother's fault and 'my trauma' she did this using language that had been given to her by one of the professionals she worked with. Trauma is not language that children use independently, and Urquhart-Stewart and Wylie (2021) illustrate that a lot of the day to day language children in care experience is often negative and disempowering. She spent more than a decade blaming herself and feeling shame about not being adopted, which she internalized as meaning that there was something wrong with her. While all the girls verbalized negative feelings towards their mother there may be a number of reasons for this including: societal expectations of mother as the carer, their own experiences of mother as the primary carer, and the need to look both outward and inward at the experience of being placed away from their families and communities. Of the six young women in the study two had siblings who did not experience care (Luna and Lisa, Interviews one and two).

It was clear that Tina wanted to be claimed by her wider social network. She spoke repeatedly within her interview of being disconnected from the family who had retained contact within their various placements, and of how they used her behaviour to stop seeing her (Tina, Interview eleven). She spoke about her need for counselling due to a lack of a sense of belonging and feelings of abandonment (Tina, Interview eleven). Changes to law and guidance in 2021 means that all care experienced children should be able to maintain contact with their brothers and sisters (Children and Young People's Commissioner Scotland, 2021).

By the mid-20th century, the experience of an 'extended family' with family members such as aunts, uncles and grandparents who may have lived locally changed because of the reduction in family size and movement for work which impacted on the availability of supportive networks (Parsons, 1961). This was not a significant issue for the group with only Tina's siblings moving local authority to stay with family members. Six other participants experienced kinship care placements within their own local authority area. For John this placement was with his grandmother, he said "I lived with my gran up until I was 12. She unfortunately passed away, so I was actually in kinship care from a very young age and then I went into residential care from there" (John, Interview eight). John was the only participant who did not mention his mother, so I have made the premise that she is deceased, and he spoke of his father's considerable drugs dependency which meant he was unable to care for any of his children. It did not feel appropriate to probe about his mother's status as it is widely acknowledged that Scotland has the highest death rate from drugs of any country in Europe and he spoke about his father's drug dependency (Socialist World, 2021). John did not officially go into care until his extended family were no longer able to care for him, they already cared for a younger sibling who he believes would have struggled living with other children. His placement with his grandmother was an 'informal kinship care' arrangement and not legally seen as being looked after within the Children and Young People (Scotland) 2014 legislation. This would have had financial implications for his grandmother as financial support has to be claimed and would be subject to conditions such as a successful application through the courts for a residence order (Looked After Children (Scotland) Regulations, 2009; Citizen's Advice Bureau, 2020). Families can be vulnerable to agreeing to these informal arrangements as they are not regulated in the same way as formal kinship care placements which may be appealing as carers may be fearful that children who have been removed from parents will also be removed from them. Many families can be suspicious of social workers as was the case for Liam's family (Thoburn, 2009), due to experiences of initial intervention and this can result in informal care arrangements with authorities withdrawing support of any kind when they believe a child or young person is within a secure living arrangement which is in keeping with the no order minimum intervention ethos of the Children (Scotland) Act, 1995 (Liam, Interview ten). This also means that these families potentially do not get the support that they need or deserve although they would be free from formal state intervention and the surveillance and monitoring that goes with it.

Eleven of the thirteen young people within this study did not come from a family form where both biological parents were living with their children, as is outlined in the family composition chart (p. 81). In the six solely matriarchal families only one mention was made of father and

no reference was made in relation to any other men as positive role models such as grandfathers, uncles, and teachers. This is not surprising in my 25-years' experience and reinforces the need for gender balance across the social care field.

6.5 Adversity in Childhood

In 2018 the Scottish Children's Reporter Administration (SCRA) completed a report on the increasingly complex lives of children and families receiving statutory intervention between 2003 and 2016. They found increasing 'family fragmentation', and a range of "high risk parents with multiple serious problems" (SCRA, 2018, p.5), which included criminality, mental illhealth, and their own difficult childhood, both victims and perpetrators of abuse, substance issues and volatility in their relationship. Only one young person within this study spoke about a parent who had also been placed within residential care as a child (Tina, Interview eleven). They noted that within the wider population there was increased complexity resulting from an increase in alcohol and drug abuse (SCRA, 2018). Participants in this study spoke about a range of adverse experiences growing up including: mental health concerns, living with a sibling with a disability, parental alcohol and drugs issues, domestic violence, experiencing neglect, violence and abuse, the incarceration of a parent or sibling and familial death. The death of a parent was experienced by a high number of children and young people placed within secure care in Scotland in 2018 (Gibson, 2019). Gibson (2019) and Vaswani (2018) talk about the absence of bereavement from ACEs given the prevalence of this within their own research. This is consistent with my own findings with two of thirteen young people experiencing parental death. Given the role that grandparents play in parenting children the NRC (2019) statistics estimating life expectancy across Scotland is also of relevance. While this has increased since the 1980s, growth has stalled with healthy life expectancy variance significant across local authority areas; amounting to a difference of 23 years for men and 24 years for women with reduced figures linked to areas of multiple deprivation such as Glasgow, Dundee, Edinburgh and Inverclyde for men and Renfrewshire, North Ayrshire, Glasgow, Inverclyde and Edinburgh for women. This is significant as only four participants in this study lived outwith these areas.

Ross (2019) completed a Secure Care Census of the five secure care establishments in Scotland and found that of the population, 87 young people in a single point in time, 73.5% of whom were aged 14-16 years old, were more likely to come from an area with a high level of multiple deprivation and to have experienced relative poverty. While all the young people within this study came to the attention of authorities initially on care and protection grounds

rather than offence grounds - and I will return to this in the next chapter - it would appear that deprivation and adversity is a feature for both groups of young people. While most (12) of the young people in my study did not want to return to their family home only three young people during interviews spoke about how their life chances would be reduced if they returned to the area where they had been born, reflecting an understanding of reduced community opportunities and an association with fewer life chances (Kevin, Tina and Amy, Interviews five, eleven and twelve). Other young people did not mention this but as we will see in Chapter eight, only one of the young people returned to their own community post care.

Three of the young people had fathers who had moved to England resulting in a special barrier that their fathers did not attempt to overcome (Lisa, Kevin and Hamish, Interviews two, five and nine). Narratives reflect a view of caring responsibilities being associated with mother and when things have broken down within the family the blame associated with this has been directed at her. As previously mentioned, the females were also likely to blame their mother for their experiences. Lisa said mum “couldn’t wait to see the back of me” (Lisa, Interview two) and Luna said: “I kind of felt a lot of resentment because it was actually my mum who put me into the care system” (Luna, Interview one). Starkey (2000) argues that ‘problem family’ essentially means ‘problem mother’, this view was expressed by some participants within the study who shared negative perspectives about why they had come into care. Effectively they blamed their mother. Crossley (2016) goes further and reflects on the narrative of ‘troubled mothers’ who are both viewed as undeserving and inadequate rearing feral children in need of policing and punishment. This perspective frames social problems as the responsibility of individuals drawing attention away from societal and essentially structural problematizing blaming those with less power for their difficult circumstances (Crossley, 2016). These themes are also evident within the adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) research (Devaney, Frederik and Spratt, 2020).

Felitti, Anda, Nordenberg, Williamson, Spitz, Edwards, Koss and Marks (1998) conducted seminal research into public health. Their study of 8,056 San Diego adults, illustrated for the first time, the links between early childhood experiences and poor health outcomes and early death in adulthood. They recognized links had been previously made in psychology and sociology but not within public health studies. Individuals who experienced four and more categories of adversity in childhood were more likely than those who had experienced none to be at increased risk of between four-and-twelve-fold health concerns including alcoholism,

drug misuse, depression, and suicidal ideation (Felitti, Anda, Nordenberg, Williamson, Spitz, Edwards, Koss and Marks, 1998). Seven categories of childhood exposure were used and included: emotional, sexual, or physical abuse, exposure to domestic violence, a household member who abused alcohol or drugs, a parent with mental ill health, or who had experienced incarceration, and parental separation. The study found a co-relation between the number of ACEs and increased health behaviours or diseases which included liver, heart and lung disease, skeletal fractures, and cancer. While there was recognition of overlap within the study, the number of categories were counted making an ACEs score and these findings have been replicated in subsequent studies (Anda, Felitti, Bremner, Whitfield, Perry, Dube and Giles 2006; Vaswani, 2018). The study makes no mention of duration or depth in the exposure to adversity, but it provides a good starting point to develop an understanding of the lifelong impact of early childhood experiences on adult outcomes.

A review of the ACEs literature, conducted by academics from Scotland, Ireland and Australia found that while the original ACEs study has become reductionist and troublesome, there is clear evidence

...that 'numbers matter' and that whereas children may be able to cope with a little adversity over a short period of time when they have good support networks, too much adversity over too long a time period, even with good support, will be problematic for the child and their family (Devaney, Frederick and Spratt, 2020, p. 1).

They advise caution however about the 'new' science of ACEs as it has "the potential for homogenisation of how we think about children's individual experiences of life pathways" (Devaney, Frederick and Spratt, 2020, p.3). Bunting, Webb and Shannon (2017) highlight that the impact of childhood adversity is certainly not inevitable. The Scottish study of 3119 children by Marryat and Frank (2019), unlike most other studies, does not rely on adult recall and they state that we have an incomplete understanding of protection and resilience factors. However, there is evidence that reflects a gradient of incidences of child abuse and neglect (CAN) and socio-economic status as well as associating being 'looked after' with a history of CAN (Bywater, Bunting, Davidson, Hanratty, Mason, McCartan and Steils, 2016).

While my own study did not directly ask the participants about adversity, the semi-structured interview questions enabled the research group to speak about early childhood experiences. Young men in this study discussed between zero and five adverse childhood experiences with

an average of less than three while the young women discussed between three and four adverse experiences with an average of four. Commonality with increased ACE scores resulted from parental separation, drugs or alcohol misuse and child neglect or abuse. Carol said: “the house wasn’t safe to live in and mum couldn’t cope as she drunk all the time and (was) mostly interested in her friendships” (Carol, Interview three). The lower number for the young men results from two having no adverse experiences using the measurement criteria which does not take into consideration parental death which was experienced by one of the three low rating young men. Mark spoke about his family saying: “I only have two brothers and a sister” (Mark, Interview seven), they were not able to look after him as they had their own lives to live, and he appeared understanding of this.

Vaswani’s study of 130 young people who received a service from ‘IVY’ (Interventions for Vulnerable Youth) found that 59% of them experienced four or more ACEs. This provision is a diversionary service that aims to keep young people out of the criminal justice system, but a recent news article described recipients of this forensic mental health risk management service as ‘dangerous’ because of them presenting a high risk to others (BBC News, 11.09.2019). Vaswani (2018) states of the ACEs criteria that the score cannot tell us of the nature or impact of the experiences and death and bullying should be included in the research. While the original study may have a bearing on health outcomes, I would argue that the psychological impact and one’s ability to function is more complex and therefore a considerable other number of variables must be taken into account. These would include who caused the adverse experience, the relationship to that person, the duration of the adversity and its severity, was it experienced across a range of settings, what supportive mechanisms, strategies and relationships were available to mediate these factors, the temperament of the individual would also be of importance here. The ACEs study therefore creates more questions than answers when dealing with the complex array of difficulties experienced by some of the participants of this study.

When lecturing on the practice implications of ACEs and psychological trauma Blower (2017) discussed both ‘simple’ and ‘complex’ trauma. ‘Simple’ trauma was described as a one off event such as an accident or assault, whereas ‘complex’ trauma was defined as repeated or complicated as would be the case of abuse when the relationship between the victim and perpetrator may be that of care giver. The impact of trauma on the brain has been the subject of many studies. Perry (2006) highlights that the earlier the trauma begins the greater the

brevity of its impact and the greater the difficulty is to treat. However, Brendtro and Mitchell (2015) state that traumatic experiences are cumulative and can affect generations. They cite indigenous populations as evidence of the impact on populations (Brendtro and Mitchell, 2015).

While we can reflect on extreme examples on the impact of trauma; in Perry and Szalavitz's *The Boy Who Was Raised as a Dog* (2006) or news coverage of Romanian orphanages from the 1990s these researchers also highlight tempered hope (Perry, 2006; BBC News, 2017). Sonuga-Barke et al. (2017) found in their longitudinal study of English and Romanian adoptees that

notwithstanding the resilience shown by some adoptees and the adult remission of cognitive impairment, extended early deprivation was associated with long-term deleterious effects on wellbeing that seem insusceptible to years of nurturance and support in adoptive families (Sonuga-Barke et al., 2017, p. 1).

Four of the young women in the study were exposed to early years adversity, before coming into care and experiences of neglect continued for several years as only two of these young people were removed entirely by the age of three. Carol spoke about the family home saying “there was always potential, there was always fights” in addition to her needs not being a priority and feeling unsafe due to adults consuming alcohol (Carol, Interview three). Tania said “when I was born, I went into my family home but I had a social worker so that’s still classed as being in care. So, I’ve basically been in (*care*) since I was born” (Tania, Interview four). Although Tania did not say why she was in care from birth statistical data shows that child protection measures are more likely for children post birth (Scottish Children’s Reporter Administration, 2018).

For Tania when she was removed from the family home, she was moved around numerous placements before she experienced stability, she had 18 moves during her time in care (Tania, Interview four). Much research highlights the plasticity of the brain reflecting how damage to neural pathways can be repaired with loving, nurturing care but criticisms have been levelled at the legitimacy of neuroscientific research into genetic malleability as this predominantly focusses on maternal behaviour, rather than addressing issues in relation to social deprivation and poverty (White and Wastell, 2017). Both need to be tackled if we are to make progress

for the young people who continue to remain at home as well as the young people who need to live within the care system, for whatever reason.

6.6 The Relationship with State Systems

I have already mentioned the complexity of the participants' experiences and there is considerable variance within the group around when individuals were removed from their biological parents. This ranged from birth to 15 years; one young person could not remember what age they were when they were removed from their family although further exploration uncovered it was at the age of 12 years, and another described this as when they were 'wee wee', which conjures up the view of when you were too small to even remember, for instance as a toddler (Bruce and Amy, Interviews six and twelve). The Scottish Children's Reporter Administration statistical analysis for 2017/18 illustrated that there were 773 children and young people living in residential establishments with most on Compulsory Supervision Orders (CSO's), the legislative basis for children and young people to be accommodated within the placement. While the predominant age for young people to be received into residential care is at the age of 14-15 years old participants in my study were placed there at the age of six, ten and eleven (SCRA, 2018). Although statistics give us an overall sense of phenomena, they do not tell us anything about the anomalies. The data also reflects that of the 13,240 referrals made to the Children's Reporter, Child Protection Order referrals were most likely to be made for babies aged under 20 days at 25.7% and infants under 2 years old at 50.4% (SCRA, 2018). Girls in the study were more likely to be known to the social work department from an early age and they appear to have been more vulnerable to care and protection grounds that could have been picked up prebirth or as part of universal services such as health visiting. This would suggest that concerns related to parenting capacity or ability, and this was influenced by drugs and alcohol for the majority of the girls. The issues in care and protection relating to boys appear to have been picked up by education or social work services staff which may be representative of more acting out behaviours from the child or young person, although again there was a high incidence of parental drug or alcohol use here. 85.1% of referrals to the Reporter were solely on care and protection grounds, this figure is likely to rise as the age of criminal responsibility has risen from the age of eight years to that of twelve years leaving Scotland behind international standards and the principles intended by Kilbrandon (Holloway, Lyle and Wishart, 2018). Reduced crime figures across Europe and the 'whole systems' policy which is designed to divert young people away from statutory involvement in Scotland has also impacted on the reduction of referrals to the hearing

system on offence grounds (Holloway, Lyle and Wishart, 2018). While three participants spoke about offending behaviour this was not the initial reason why two of them became part of the social work system and the third appears to have come into care as an orphan who did not have a wider family support system.

The young people's first experience of the children's hearing system also varied considerably. One participant said that they were removed from their families in infancy (0-2 years old) and three in early childhood (2-6 years old) (Keenan, Evans and Crowley, 2016). One young person was accommodated in middle childhood (6-11 years) and six in adolescence (11-18 years old) (Keenan, Evans and Crowley, 2016). The increase in removal age is consistent with the figures reflected by SCRA statistics which show that other than birth 13–15-year-old children are more likely to be taken into care, as by this stage they are more likely to be seen as outwith parental control so experiences of adversity may be masked, age of admission is less likely to be associated with care and protection at this point in a young person's life. Within this study three young women and five young men were formally taken into care between the ages of 11 and 18. Nine young people within the study knew why they were accommodated by their local authority as is evident in Chart One of Chapter five, while three young people said that they did not know why they came into care and one other young person as mentioned earlier did not know the truth about her situation. Why young people are removed from their families is surely crucial to how they make sense of that broken affectional bond and as we will discover shortly not knowing can result in young people blaming themselves for their journey into care. This will be revisited in Chapter seven.

While there is a growing body of research that highlights the importance of early years intervention strategies for improving the lives of children, it is also recognised that this is not enough (Allen, 2008; CSJ, 2016). The Scottish Governments response has been to identify a range or preventative measures throughout childhood (Scottish Government, 2008b). Early and Effective Intervention strategies are embedded in the Whole Systems Approach designed to ensure that agencies work together to achieve the best outcomes for 8 – 18-year-olds. This has effectively reduced the number of young people receiving statutory social work services but structural challenges remain (Scottish Government, 2021b). There is recognition across the literature that good quality services must be available for young people throughout their childhood (Allen, 2008; Allen and Duncan Smith, 2011; CSJ, 2016), but there is no description about what good quality services look like, I will revisit this in the forthcoming chapters. Liam stated that what he needed when he went into care was not just someone caring for him and

his siblings, but services being made available to his parents (Liam, Interview eleven). In addition to the need for multiple services, it is recognised that the Kilbrandon principle of need and not deed has to be restated as this distinction disadvantages both those who come into the system in later life and those who come into the hearing system on offence grounds if we have the basic premise that all children are born good (Holloway, Kaliani and Wishart (2018). A Chance UK case study states that “children have to get help when they need it, when the distress first starts to show and before the pattern of disruptive behaviour defines the child. It’s about agencies working together in a way that meets their unique needs” (CSJ, 2016, p. 6). Approaches to partnership working has been impacted by COVID-19 and austerity measures resulting in a reduction in both personal state-assisted care and third sector developments (ESCR, 2021). Fundamentally, all too frequently the system defines older children in terms of disruptive behaviour and the experience of Hamish coming into care is a case in point. He said

...at 9 basically my mum was an addict, and her partner was a heroin dealer and all of the bad stereotypes that you can imagine came with that. And she would try and leave him, and we went to respite with her at the women’s refuge and basically (*they*) couldn’t house her and us which was fair enough as there were other women there and stuff so we got put into foster” care (Hamish Interview 9).

After several years outwith the system Hamish returned after an altercation resulting in him seeing himself as the cause of this intervention as his siblings did not return to care with him. What he believed was going to be a short-term strategy lasting a few days resulted in five years away from his family (Hamish, Interview nine). This was echoed in Tania’s account when she thought she was going to a placement for the weekend, and she never returned home (Tania, Interview four). Hamish and Tania experienced considerably more placement moves than the other participants with Hamish experiencing 51 and Tania 18, as earlier stated. English statistics for 2013 reflect that over 10% of young people looked after in care have three or more placements over a one-year period (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2013). Hamish experienced almost six and a half years within care and even if put within the top 10% of placement moves of three per year this would equate to around 20 placements, reflecting 51 is extremely high. The Scottish Executive developed a range of policy initiatives to support children and families where parents had issues with drugs and alcohol including Getting Our Priorities Right in recognition of the poor outcomes for children when agencies focus their interventions on the needs of adults and fail to share information that leaves children and young people vulnerable (Scottish Executive, 2003). While services,

including the police, may prioritise the needs of the child, accessibility to support is dependent on the availability of resources at a time when they are extremely scarce (BASW, 2021). For Hamish it was not until he was assaulted and retaliated that the services stepped in, in this instance the police, and he returned to care (Interview nine).

Only one other participant mentioned the experience of violence within the family. For Kevin, his older brother's behaviour resulted in social services visiting the family to ascertain the home circumstances (Kevin, Interview five). This resulted in Kevin and his brother being taken into care, Kevin stated that he flagged up concerns about how he was being looked after with statutory agencies. There was a theme within the study where participants were looking for someone to blame for their situation; either internally in terms of themselves or a family member, most often the mother, or externally in terms of the wider society or social work systems as was evident for Kevin who blamed both his older brother and the social work system. As his older brother had committed a crime, agencies became involved with the wider family and the two brothers were taken into care together but subsequently separated (Kevin, Interview five). As previously mentioned, Kevin had no difficulty disclosing information within the interview and while this may have resulted from his attachment style it is also common for young people to have shared their narratives considerably whereby there may be a desensitisation to sharing personal information.

None of the participants within this study remained with their brothers or sisters during their time in care and this issue was highlighted as part of the Independent Care Review (Care Review, 2020). Part 13 of the Children (Scotland) Act 2020 and the Looked After Children (Scotland) Amendment Regulations 2021 has introduced the importance of keeping siblings together, although there is a caveat that allows agencies not to follow this if it is seen as not being in the best interests of the children. Tina went into care at the age of three years old with her baby sister. The separation and loss she experienced is palpable. She says

...I think my sister got adopted when I was only in (*the children's unit*) for about a year. I remember waiting to see her for my birthday and she never showed up and for six months she didn't have any contact with me or anything so I was still going through traumatic times settling in... and my gran and my auntie they ... adopted one of my brothers and one of my sisters, well my gran adopted them, and they would sometimes come to visit me. But they weren't consistent and after a while they would just stop coming to visit (Tina, Interview eleven).

Most of the young people received inconsistent support from their families and I will revisit this in the next chapter. Amy was one of five participants who was admitted into care after the age of twelve and she was the only participant to spend time between her mother, grandmother, and a neighbour; all other young people experienced only familial care before becoming accommodated. She was the only participant who had no siblings and she said

...I was 13 and I started to get involved with drugs and stuff, but I did have social work involvement when I was younger like 'wee wee' (*she didn't know what age she was*). But I think things got more out of hand because there was a lot of stuff that happened growing up and I think 13 was when I cracked and kind of just like lost it (Amy, Interview twelve).

During the interview she did not talk about her home life experience, even with prompting, but recognised that she was not in a safe situation living with an adult 'boyfriend'. Child sexual exploitation literature highlights the abuse triangle reflecting how skilled adults can be coercing children into believing that sexual relationships with them are legitimate where in fact they reflect remuneration and veiled affection towards young people who are vulnerable (Barnardo's, 2014).

Twelve out of the thirteen participants had brothers and/or sisters although half of the twelve were the only members of their family to experience care re-enforcing their own narrative that they were in some way to blame for their circumstances. Of those with siblings who did experience care four spoke of spending time in placement with one or more of their brothers and sisters. Irrespective of what young people were advised about their situation when they went into care there was a real sense of shame for many which manifested itself in many ways, I will return to this shortly in Chapter seven but before moving on to residential care experiences I will conclude this chapter by looking at participants experience within foster care and their relationships with their brothers and sisters.

6.7 Foster Care and Brothers and Sisters

While the findings in this research study involves young people who have experienced residential care, including secure care, it has to be acknowledged that all but three of the males interviewed spent some time within a foster or kinship placement. Retaining children and young people within family settings is viewed as more beneficial to their wellbeing, growth and development but what this serves to do is increase the potential number of changes and placement experiences they endure as they may move between temporary foster placements until something more permanent is found rather than permanence being sourced in the first

place through a long-term foster or residential placement (Tania, Interview four). Most of the group experienced several transitions before they were moved into residential care. Smith (2005, p.1) states that “the notion of transition goes beyond the actual change to encompass how we as individuals (or perhaps collectively) process that change. Transition is emotional and experiential as much as it is structural”. Smart and Digney (2015, p.14) highlight that young people in the system ‘experience simultaneous transitions’ that don’t become easier to navigate but more problematic, “they don’t become immune they become frozen” when experiencing these changes as they are no longer able to emotionally react as they become numb. I would suggest that the use of the term transition, by professionals, masks the reality for young people who are looked after. Rather than a transition being experienced as a change from one placement to another, the children, and young people’s experiences of moving between family members and foster carers is better viewed as a series of rejections. If the placement was successful there would be no need to be moved on, although in one instance this was seen as having little to do with success or failure. Tania stated that she was moved from carers’ due to criteria, age, and duration restrictions (Tania, Interview four).

Multiple nurturing experiences are needed to overcome the adversity experienced by participants and rejection can trigger fear which impacts on learning and brain development (Brendtro, 2015). But decision making around keeping children within the family and the extended family unit is complex. The ‘rule of optimism’ has retained currency for three decades and reflects practitioners’ decision making when dealing with child protection (Kettle and Jackson, 2017). Social work staff continue to give families too many chances to turn their behaviours around reflective of an optimistic view of their ability to provide appropriate care for their children. Serious case reviews too often reflect children die as a result of this view and a lack of action to remove the child from the situation (Kettle and Jackson, 2017).

The minimum intervention ethos of legislation and government policy adds an added complexity to this process. Three young people were initially taken into care with their sibling(s) and spoke about living with them for a period although all three were subsequently separated. One of the reasons for using residential care, which is described as meeting many functions, includes being able to keep sibling groups together, although this is assumed rather than being the norm (Shaw, 2007).

Tania was separated from her sibling group as her social worker initially attempted to promote her adoption, she had been accommodated shortly after her birth. What followed was a series

of placements and experiences of isolation from brothers and sisters. She said: “they wanted to adopt me so my social worker was fighting for that and then she lost the fight and I ended up getting fostered with my family... and then we all separated..., I was on my own.” (Tania, Interview four). Tina had experienced 12 failed foster placements (Tina, Interview eleven). Tobin (2013) highlights that there is considerable research on placement breakdown, also referred to as placement disruption. The literature reflects such breakdowns can range from 20 – 47% (Tobin, 2013). Tina also experienced several respite care experiences by the age of three (Tina, Interview eleven). Respite care describes a placement that affords either the young person or foster carer respite from their current living arrangement.

Research “suggests that membership of a sibling group is a unique part of the identity of a child or young person and can promote a sense of belonging and promote positive self-esteem and emotional wellbeing” (NICE/SCIE, 2010, p.33). All the participants in this study, except Amy (24), were part of a sibling group and subsequently experienced attachment, separation, and loss when they were removed from their families, placed within care and subsequently separated from their siblings (see Chart Three, p. 84). This can be very complex as was the case for John (20). He said

...I did have contact with my sister and aunt because although I couldn't have lived with my sister, me and my sister just couldn't have got along enough to live together because we didn't from a young age...My sister was an only child and was used to it being that way so it would have just caused too much tension in the household without bringing in two other young people (John, Interview eight).

In this account John refers to two stepsisters; one on his father's side and one on his mothers with his younger sister living with an aunt while he and his other sister lived together with their grandmother. John was the only participant who spoke about having a stable placement for most of his life with his grandmother, he lived with her from what he called a 'very young age' and went into residential care following her death when he was around 12 years old.

Bowlby discusses attachment behaviour and used observations from several studies of children developing a theory of motivation that, while initially reflecting the mother or caregiver relationship, helps us to understand the impact of separation represented in the behaviour sequence of 'protest', 'despair' and 'detachment' (Bowlby, 1974; Cassidy and Shaver, 2008). In his analysis of the Ugandan study by Ainsworth (1963, 1967) and Scottish study by Schaffer and Emerson (1964) he said that once secure attachment relationships were formed through the responsiveness of the carer to the child, children were then able to attach securely to

others. However, it was noted “that in any one child the intensity and consistency with which attachment behaviour is shown can vary greatly from day to day or hour to hour” (Bowlby, 1974, p. 202) reflecting the significant interplay between nature, the child’s temperament and genetic makeup, and nurture reflected in the interplay with environmental factors. He further found that young children did not need to be separated from their carer for a significant time period to show signs of distress and found that when this experience was repeated by different carers and nurses the child would behave in time as though neither parenting nor human contact had any significance to them. When children did re-engage there was a fear of subsequent loss resulting in the modification of their behaviour, so they may present as clingy or at the other extreme aloof. The intensity of the reaction appears to be mitigated by a sibling presence or stability such as one replacement carer as was the case with John (Bowlby, 1974, 1979; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). In addition to John’s positive experience, Bob refers to his own secure relationship with both of his parents (Bob, Interview thirteen. He spoke about poor relationships with his social worker and some residential staff, but this was related to what he saw as them controlling his access to his family. He said “I would have to wait for them to come back and say like aye or naw sort of thing. Or for them to go and contact the social worker to see if I was allowed to go on contact, do you know what I mean” (Bob, Interview thirteen). I will return to professional relationships in the next chapter.

None of the participants in this study experienced only one replacement carer so this is likely to have had a significant impact on their ability to form relationships. Kevin said his “attachment issues are like ridiculous. My ability to detach from people and detach myself from situations is quite worrying” (Kevin, Interview five). This was evident to me in how he approached me when I attended a meeting looking for volunteers for my research. I initially thought he was assured and confident, but he overshared, a common behaviour with young people who have issues with trust, either not sharing anything or sharing everything all at once. Bowlby helps us to make sense of Kevin’s experiences through his theory of ‘internal working models’ which moved away from the dominant view of the time and recognised the impact experiences have on what we internalise (Bowlby, 1973; Cassidy and Shaver, 2008). Bowlby states that

...during the course of development a child constructs for himself working models of his attachment figures and of himself in relation to them. The data used for model construction are derived from multiple sources: from his day-to-day experiences, from statements made to him by his parents, and from information coming from others. Usually the data reaching him from these diverse sources are

reasonably compatible. For example, not only may a child experience his parents as accessible, considerate, and responsive but information coming from other sources may amply endorse that view... Alternatively, both the experience a child has of his parents and the information he receives from them and from others about them may point consistently to their being unloving. Many more complex relationships can be imagined; but, provided in each case the information reaching the child from the different sources is reasonably compatible, the working models that he builds of parents and of self will be internally consistent in themselves and also complementary to one another. As such the models are able to reflect with a fair degree of accuracy the sort of people the child's parents are, how they see him and how they are likely to treat him. Thus, whether relationships are happy or the reverse, the child is able to make firm and accurate predictions and, on that basis, to construct plans of action likely to prove effective (Bowlby, 1973, p. 317).

The role of attachment in human development is well documented and continues throughout the lifespan (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1974, 1979; Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Erikson, 1963, 1995; Furnival, 2011). Its function is seen as crucial to the development of the child as it provides a secure base for the child to learn as outlined in chapter one, explore and play, develop a personality and feel safe (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1974). A child will seek proximity to a care giver when safety is compromised and when they are alarmed seeking reassurance and protection (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1974). There was evidence that even at very young ages, young people within this study helped to care for their younger siblings and felt responsible for them when faced with adversity, this appeared to form a significant bond (Hamish and Tina, Interviews nine and eleven). For Tina she said "I believed for years that it was my fault that me and my younger sister were in care" despite being only three years old when she was removed by the social work department (Interview eleven). Hamish described undertaking parental tasks such as paying rent and caring responsibilities for his younger siblings before he returned to care at the age of 14 years old (Interview nine). There will inevitably be worries around who will look after the family when the young people are separated and remain within the family home where there continues to be parental issues with substance misuse and domestic violence. There cannot be an assumption that state agencies will intervene as it can be assumed that the child who has been removed has been part of the problem. Ongoing family time with his brothers allowed Hamish to maintain his positive relationship with his siblings. Bob who was removed at the

age of nine felt that being separated from his brother had a negative impact on their relationship, his brother is one year older than him. He said that the separation

...did affect us, it affected us really. So, like now the two of us just fight with each other and do what brothers do sort of thing we still do that but that's because he's got learning disabilities so he obviously doesn't know right from wrong but then like small things will just trigger him and he will just kick off and I'm stuck in the middle of it. But we are getting there slowly but surely (Bob, Interview thirteen).

Rivalry and conflict between brothers and sisters are not unique to young people who are accommodated but there is a theme within interviews that sibling relationships are very complex. Shared experiences and sibling attachments form a bond that appears to have been severed for almost half of the participants due to separation and the loss of contact, this will be further explored within the next chapter when I talk about family time. For Luna (19) further complexity resulted from her being one of three children and the only child within the family to be removed from the family home. While she expressed this by talking about the 'unit' what she reflects is the emotional impact of both her separation and the ongoing management of this as she lived apart from her siblings. She said

...one of the hard things for me in the unit was the fact that my brother and my sister were still staying with my mum when I went into care and for me that was really difficult. When I was going to school the two of them were in the same school as me and they would just walk home because it was like close to the school and I would have to get the bus back or whatever and that was really hard and left me feeling a bit more left out, I guess. And it didn't help that I was the middle child already. That just sort of added on to the whole middle child syndrome (Laughs) (Luna, Interview one).

Bronfenbrenner (1979) talks about the complex interrelations evident in several interviews, including Luna's experience. In his theory of human development he identifies four different levels of the ecological environment: 'microsystems' – these include the family and school and the relationship the child has with them, 'mesosystems' – relates to the relationships between the microsystems such as the relationship between the home and the teachers, 'exosystems' refer to systems that have an indirect impact on the child such as a parents work that may result in less time at home or the stress placed on the household and the 'macrosystems'

which is reflective of beliefs or ideologies outwith the family that may impact indirectly but influences how a family functions such as the input from the state (Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

All the above impact either directly or indirectly on all human beings so this theory helps us to get a better understanding of the interplay between the public sphere of the family and home and the private spheres outside the initial dyadic relationship between parent and child that extends to triadic and further interpersonal relationships (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). He states

...the most unorthodox feature of the proposed theory is its conception of development. Here the emphasis is not on the traditional psychological processes of perception, motivation, thinking, and learning, but on their *content* - *what* is perceived, desired, feared, thought about, or acquired as knowledge, and how the nature of this psychological material changes as a function of a person's exposure to and interaction with the environment. Development is defined as the person's evolving conception of the ecological environment, and his relation to it, as well as the person's growing capacity to discover, sustain, or alter its properties (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, p. 9).

An 'ecological transition' such as moving is seen as developmentally significant as it results in a role change and behavioural expectation changes (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). This will have additional significance when a child or young person leaves their own systems and becomes part of an alternative system that may not initially be connected to their home, family, school, and own community.

6.8 Conclusion

This chapter has illustrated that there are differences within the participant group around when they were first involved with social work services with young women being more likely to have been involved from an early stage and young men not involved until after they have at least started school, for most it was in secondary school that they became part of the formal state looked after system. Whilst crude measures of ACEs were made there were differences and similarities in gender with ACE scores ranging from 0-5, although the young men were more likely to have 0 as a scoring due to the categories that are included; the absence of duration and depth of experience was touched upon and recognition given that the impact of this on health outcomes may not be as significant as the outcomes experienced outside health, but this will be revisited in future chapters. More contemporary literature reflects that while children may cope with some adversity, too much over an extended time period could be troublesome

for both them and their families (Devaney, Frederick and Spratt, 2020; Bunting, Webb and Shannon, 2017).

It has been recognised that prior to being accommodated young people may have experienced several transitions moving between family members and foster placements before going into residential care. The use of language is particularly relevant here as transitions evokes a sense of change and purpose as we move from one experience to another which is not a true reflection of the emotional impact experienced by participants who spoke about feeling shame and blame towards themselves and particularly their mothers when they did not remain within the family home or within their extended family network. While a gendered perspective of parenting pervades, this is challenged within research literature across the social science field (Bunting, Webb and Shannon, 2017; Crossley, 2016).

Being rejected is more in keeping with the lived experience of young people who struggle to understand their care history as this is not always explored with them as part of their care journey. Sibling relationships were also explored, and attachment theory helped us to understand the complexity around decision making about keeping siblings together within placement. Things were likely to be experienced differently within sibling groups where not all the children have been accommodated together or where different outcomes have been achieved when they are. An understanding of relationships also helped to illustrate the importance of these for young people in the study: whether this was with parents, parental figures, brothers and sisters or staff. The narratives presented here show that children and young people need safe, secure and stable placements for healthy development and to ensure that any damage that may have been caused is supported to be repaired. For all the young people a significant relationship was crucial here.

Social work services can be viewed with suspicion by families as social problems tend to be pathologized and there is a negative association between help and not being a good parent (Bunting, Webb and Shannon, 2017). This chapter helped to identify some of the challenges faced by services because of both COVID-19 and austerity measures that exacerbate poverty which has implications due its association with child abuse and neglect (ESCR, 2021; Bywater, Bunting, Davidson, Hanratty, Mason, McCartan and Steils, 2016). The chapter also highlighted that there is an absence of statistical information that reflects class and poverty in social work intervention statistics. This deficit has been recognised for some time and it is difficult to see how we can successfully evaluate early intervention strategies without having the data necessary for measurement, although it was also pointed out that the data only tells

us part of the story. Increasingly critics have revealed that appropriately addressing poverty could have the biggest impact on life chances and experiences for children and young people in Scotland. So, let us now turn to the next stage of the journey by looking at the experiences the participants had within residential care.

CHAPTER SEVEN: THE COMPLEXITIES OF THE GROUP LIVING EXPERIENCE

*I never make the same mistake once, I make it five or six times just to be sure
(Anonymous, 2014).*

7.1 Introduction

The previous chapter looked at the early life experiences of participants within the study highlighting the hidden challenges that some young people face in forming secure relationships due to experiences in infancy of failing living arrangements with a variety of family members and there was recognition that experiences differed within sibling groups. The chapter also highlighted the monitoring and surveillance experienced by some families, the levels of adversity, and the impact on child development when needs were not being met in a nurturing, safe and secure environment.

This chapter will follow their journey by looking at how preconceived notions of placements can influence the admission process for some young people. It will explore the importance of routines, structures and practices within placements that are designed to meet the needs of children and young people and show how residential care is experienced by participants. Goffman's theory of stigma will help to illustrate how the legacy of residential care may have an impact on the inner and outer world of those in the study. As we discussed in Chapter six, meaningful relationships are the essence of children and young people's ability to experience positive human development. Participants talk about the impact on relationships with family members and friendships during their group care experience and beyond and the chapter will also explore the relationships developed with staff members highlighting the importance of language in this dynamic. It will conclude by sharing views of the durability and longevity of professional relationships that for many young people continue long after they leave care.

7.2 Urban Myths

The Dickensian image of the Workhouse is not far removed from modern 'urban myths' about residential childcare as was reflected in Amy's account where she described feeling that she was going to get battered and beaten with coat hangers and her way of trying to get control over her life resulted in her refusing to eat (Amy, Interview twelve). Hamish remembers hearing stories when he was young about the 'giant jumper home', he also talked about 'Maggie Murphy's home' for boys who were bad, she would take you in your sleep and eat you (Hamish, Interview nine). These stories are akin to the urban myths about the 'bogeyman'

which exist across time and space and are used by adults to promote conformity and good behaviour in children. Hamish said that these stereotypes were what children in his neighbourhood were threatened with growing up and when he discovered that the second time, he went into care it was because he physically assaulted his stepfather it re-enforced to him that he was a 'bad boy'.

Like Hamish, Kevin, Luna and Liam also spoke about the association between residential care and being 'bad kids'. Liam said it

...came up in a job interview recently...we were a list D school years ago so that was a threat that parents would give their kids if you are a bad boy you're going to (*residential care*). So, it then became associated with bad kids instead of kids that say needed help or were maybe struggling in life. And kids where it wasn't their fault or maybe their parents had issues, which was certainly the case for my part, for most of it anyway...adults themselves portray it as it's just for bad kids rather than it's actually their fault (Liam, Interview ten).

7.3 The Formal Admission Process

Pizzey-Gray, Stack and Puckering (2018) state that the removal of children and young people from their parents' care is one of the greatest challenges any professional will face and any decision to do so will be deemed to be based on the long-term welfare interests in line with legislation. The decision made by the panel is made based on the information that is provided to it so it is imperative that this is comprehensive. Panel members commented on the impact solicitors attending children's hearings can have as they often take the focus away from the needs of the child (Pizzey-Gray, Stack and Puckering, 2018).

Before moving into a residential placement young people who are the subject of compulsory measures of supervision would be required to attend a children's hearing. Eight young people shared their experiences of attendance at these hearings as not always being the supportive child centred forums that they are designed to be. Lisa remembers not attending her hearing and returning from school to find that her bags had been packed and that she was moving from what she thought was a stable foster care placement to a secure care placement. She said that she did not know that a panel was taking place and she was not invited, this is an unusual situation in my experience (Lisa, Interview two). Under the Children's Hearing (Scotland) Act 2011, S73 (3) (b), a young person can be excused from their hearing if it is likely to have a negative impact on their physical, mental, or emotional wellbeing. This may

have been the reason why Lisa was not advised about her children's hearing, but this has to be weighed up against the impact of trusted adults not being honest about this process and potential harm caused to the formed and sustained meaningful relationships.

Tina spoke about her understanding of attendance at hearings as being compulsory and the legislation states that children and relevant people have a 'duty' to attend (Children's Hearing (Scotland) Act 2011). She remembers when she was at school that she was advised that if she did not attend her children's hearing that the police would take her there in handcuffs (Interview eleven). At school she was encouraged to rebel as her peers were keen to see this being acted out, but she said that she was always too scared to let this happen. Despite the duty to attend the panel members can excuse children and young people when they do not attend their children's hearing (SCRA, 2021b). On the rare occasions when young people have not attended because they disagree with the social work department's recommendation, for instance they are going to be admitted, moved, or sent to a secure placement due to their level of risk, a warrant may be issued that could result in a young person arriving at their care placement in handcuffs. In twenty-five years, I have experienced this twice, but this was not the experience of any of the young people in my study, however the knowledge that this could occur appears to have been a significant deterrent for my sample group. This is a very poor start to a placement for any young person and again re-enforces a negative association with residential care, but it also must have a very damaging impact on the relationships young people have with their social workers, I will return to this shortly.

Only Hamish spoke about being admitted to residential care on a voluntary basis, although his reflections suggest that he was not able to provide informed consent. He thought that his mother had put him into residential care but said "it turns out I was in such a state of angst that I didn't realise that I'd signed myself in" (Hamish, Interview nine). A lack of good communication about why young people go into care was shared by more than half of the participants in the study with seven young people either not knowing or being unsure about why they went into care. Some young people were so young when they went into care, three females were babies or infants, that it would have been difficult for the decision making to be shared with them, this could obviously have been explored with them at a later stage. Nine young people went into care when they were entering or in their teens and all these young people had some understanding of why they went into care. Even if this was told to them it was not explained in a way that helped them to make sense of the situation.

The prioritisation of children and young people's needs within the children's panel was reflected in views expressed by Kevin, Hamish and Bruce who stated that they did not want their parents to attend their hearings as their input was detrimental to them. This decision was agreed by the panel members. Liam said his parents rarely attended and he believed that this was because they prioritised their own needs and were focussed on their drugs dependency rather than the needs of their children. Bob felt that his father, who he believed was advocating on his behalf, was not listened to at his children's hearings as he strongly disagreed with the social work department's assessment of him (Bob, Interview thirteen). It was more likely for young men in this study to negatively reflect on their experiences of formal decision making. While I have been unable to source any research that would indicate any reason for this it may result from the earlier discussion about how young men and women deal with stressful situations differently, boys are more likely to externalise (Kort-Butler, 2006). It may also however result from the dominance of patriarchy within our society. Who Cares? Scotland (2016) undertook a review of advocacy provision across Scotland as part of a Scottish Government funded action research. They noted that there was inconsistency in provision despite independent advocacy being viewed as a source for ensuring that children and young people have a voice and control over their lives (Who Cares? Scotland, 2016). Only one of the participants spoke about the importance of their advocate while they were in care (Bob, Interview thirteen).

Only Amy spoke about arriving at the residential placement and her narrative is so strong that it must be included in the study. She said: "it was horrible, like social workers who didn't speak to you or nothing, they didn't explain what was going on and that" (Amy, Interview twelve). She said that she wished people had put themselves in her shoes and broken things down for her so that she knew what was happening. She arrived at the placement late in the evening and she was taken to a dark room, and she was shown a sofa bed. In the morning she was taken to another placement where she ended up living with five other children and young people. The number of children within the placement was mentioned by nine other participants as it was believed that this impacted on staff's ability to meet the individual needs of participants. I will look at this in more detail in the next chapter when looking at how prepared young people were for leaving care.

7.4 Feeling like a Failure

Participants associated a sense of failure with being placed within residential care. Tania spoke about being in three residential placements that encompassed half her life. She said: “I ended up in residential because I was too much for the foster carers or they had an age limit or stuff like that, so I had to move to residential which was actually really hard for me” (Tania, Interview four). A sense that you were to blame because adults could not meet your needs is consistent across the group when experiencing placement breakdown. Luna spoke about how residential care was viewed much more negatively than foster care with perceptions that it was your own fault that you were there, and people thought that you were probably violent (Luna, Interview one). Enell and Wilinska (2020) found that perceptions of children as either dangerous or in danger permeates child welfare provision, particularly where young people are viewed as either a risk to themselves or others. Lisa said people made assumptions that she had committed a crime, possibly even murder, to get put within a secure setting (Lisa, Interview two). This resulted in her sister being bullied in the school that both had previously attended. These negative stereotypes impacted on all but two of the young people within the study with many of them blaming themselves for their situation.

Multiple transitions were experienced by most of the participants with placement moves ranging from 2 – 51 placements as discussed in the previous chapter. Many of the young people transitioned to a new school when they moved placement; this was discussed by Tania, Lisa, Bruce, Mark, Hamish, Liam, and Amy. Six of the participants spent some time in specialist education while seven remained within mainstream secondary education. This would suggest that for just under half of the participant group, their life experiences impacted on their capacity for learning. Hamish said that when he was moved, he went to a much better school in a better area to where he lived with his family. He said that “a lot of the kids were quite wealthy, and they would get to go snowboarding and France and quite fancy things so I used to think that I was missing out because you can’t do that when you have eight other kids to consider” (Hamish, Interview nine). Four of the participants spoke about comparing themselves to their biological brothers and sisters, their peer group at school and the household group that they lived with in residential care (Luna, Lisa, Kevin and Hamish, Interviews one, two, five and nine). Many of the others also compared themselves to one of these groups to a lesser degree and what could be normal sibling rivalry is amplified when you have the added complexity of being a member of multiple comparison groups.

Comparisons between siblings is something Klass (2009) highlights as what parents can tend to do through labelling, such as the clever one or pretty one. Sibling rivalry is viewed as almost universal (Isaacs, 2006), and a valuable developmental opportunity for children to learn how to solve conundrums and manage conflict with most animosity fitting within a normal family functioning range (Klass, 2009). Comparisons between peers were also made and Hamish comparing his life experience with wealthier peers is like comparing chalk with cheese and means his measurement of success during adolescence may be challenging, I will return to this at the end of the chapter. Luna, who did not move, spoke about school with her brother and sister and how emotionally challenging this was. While they were able to walk home to their familial home, she had to get the bus to the children's unit adding to her sense of isolation and a lack of belonging (Luna, Interview one).

7.5 Placement Stability

Family membership is usually through partnership or consanguinity and as a child you learn to assimilate and accommodate based on your experiences with other family members, although this does not mean that your experience will either be one of stability or safety (Ibsen and Klobus, 1972). When you live in a household of individuals who are not related, even when you have been removed from the family home due to your own safety as was the case for five young women in the study, the group care experience can be seen as hostile and uncertain for some children. The Centre for Youth and Criminal Justice's (CYCJ), (renamed the Children and Young People's Centre for Justice in 2021) blog (2019) speaks about how young people in care have no choice about who they live with. Individuals have no control or respite from staff or other young people, and this can cause re-traumatisation when another young person's behaviour is a reminder of historical events. A simple request to take time away from the situation may not be permitted, there may be legitimate reasons for this, but this can impact on the emotional wellbeing of all young people within the group (CYCJ, 2019). Kevin spoke about acting out behaviour in those around him saying I noticed: "people's behaviour being so radical because they were seeking care and attention by doing ridiculous things that was getting them into trouble" (Kevin, Interview five). This would be described by Anglin (2002) as pain-based behaviours, a way for children and young people to express their pain. Kevin also said that within the group living experience his feelings remained hidden and he felt that because he was not acting out or making demands on staff his emotional needs went unmet. He said that young people's mental health was overlooked within the children's home, unless you were self-harming. Johnson, Ferguson and Copley (2017) talk about the

distress self harm causes to self-harmers, staff and other young people within the group, and they note that the prevalence of this behaviour within residential care is much higher than the general population. Sims-Schouten and Hayden (2017) use Department of Education data to reflect that 50% of young people in care for 12 months or more, have some form of problem with their mental health. A reduction in staff availability to others in a group care setting is seen to be a consequence of staff responding to self-harming incidents (Johnson, Ferguson and Copley, 2017).

Luna found it hard not living at home and felt that she matured within her residential placement, largely because she had to. She said: “the unit was a really hard place to live, and I know there are worse places... I was 14 when I moved in, and 18 when I moved out, so it was a big gap of my life and it’s just really hard” (Luna, Interview one). Although she could not quite articulate what ‘hard’ was she felt that she had to grow up in the unit and grow a tougher skin. She needed to hide her emotions and not get bogged down in why she was the only one of the three children in her family who went into care. She struggled to make relationships with other young people in care because of fear that they would be moved. She was scared that if she became close to someone they would leave, and she would have to start again to form new relationships. This was something experienced by other young people in the study.

Kevin said that there was no sense of security when he was in residential care even though he was in the same placement for eight years (Kevin, Interview five). Young people appeared to be so used to other young people coming and going that it made them feel that they could be next. As well as young people moving it seemed to be common for staff to be moved without much consideration. Kevin said that the manager was “the best staff member, she was nurturing, she motivated me, she made sure my wellbeing was looked after, she tried everything she could” (Kevin, Interview five). Despite having a strong bond with Kevin, she was moved to another service leaving him feeling abandoned. A lack of consistency in staffing is something that is reflected within the Care Review (2020).

Three of the young people in the study spoke about the impact of staff working shifts on their experience within the residential house. Within a family setting, children generally must navigate the differing parenting styles of two adults within the home. Within a children’s house there are a group of adults to consider with young people having to learn, understand, support,

and follow a range of what may at times seem like conflicting and changing rules, demands and expectations. Kevin and Hamish spoke about the impact it had on them. Hamish said

...there were constant shift changes as there are in every home. Three changes a day and it was quite disruptive. As much as they are people and it's a job and they have to be on each day and there would be a few days, a few times when I'd go home and they'd be like this staff member is not coming back. So as much as you can, planning for that consistency would be nice (Hamish, Interview nine).

Kevin reiterated this view and said: "staff members are being ripped out and put in other residential homes, that is harsh" (Kevin, Interview five). He spoke about a favourite manager, he was attached to and could confide in, being moved without notice. He was told by a worker that "they are here to give emotional support and not love...people who are meant to be like your parents, they are meant to look after you...so why are they (*the government*) not giving you the same basic needs as everybody else?" (Kevin, Interview five). Kevin also said that he

...was never allowed to be hugged for like pure long durations of time because it would have been seen as grooming...you go through these emotionally traumatic things and like when you are in the residential home not being told you're loved and not being shown affection and nurturing...it's such a cold and hostile place to grow up (Kevin, Interview five).

While none of the participants spoke about experiencing any form of abuse during their time in care, as indicated in Chapter four, most of the reviews particularly of residential childcare have resulted from abuse inquiries (Radford, Dodd, Barter, Stanley and Akhlaq, 2013). With estimated figures of abuse in residential care of 2:100 in Scotland the findings of the study are not surprising (Radford, Dodd, Barter, Stanley and Akhlaq, 2013). The findings in reviews and other studies have undoubtedly impacted on how staff go about their work. A study over a three-year period between 2009 and 2012 found that between 1,100 and 2,500 allegations of abuse are made within residential care across the UK (Biehal, Cusworth, Wade and Clarke, 2014). This equates to 10 – 12 per 100 children, with 250 – 300 substantiated allegations (Biehal, Cusworth, Wade and Clarke, 2014). Figures in Scotland are lower than the rest of the UK, but they remain considerable with 2 children per 100 in residential care said to be experiencing some form of abuse (Radford, Dodd, Barter, Stanley and Akhlaq, 2013). Fear of allegations may undoubtedly impact on a worker's ability to show care and affection.

Bob struggled with the priorities of staff. He said

...like every time I wanted to talk to my keyworker, they would come back with give us half an hour, like they wouldn't come out (*of the office*) because they were too busy like having a cup of tea with each other. So, if...there was something coming up and I wanted to talk to him...I would have to wait for them to come back and say like aye or naw... or for them to contact the social worker (Bob, Interview thirteen).

The earlier discussion around self-harming shows how staff prioritise greater needs and while the meaningful engagement required is reflective of the depth of relationships that are helpful to some it may not be well received by others within the group (Johnson, Ferguson and Copley, 2016). All the young people in the study had formed positive relationships with adults before and during their time in placement. For three young people the strength of these relationships was particularly significant. Liam spoke about the continued support he receives, he said

...I still phone *Andy (residential school day placement keyworker)* when I'm unsure about things now to get his thoughts. Cos *Andy* is very much like a dad to me, he's as close as, to a dad I think I've ever had. He's my sounding board for most things...he was in my life for 11 years just constantly there" sticking with me through thick and thin (Liam, Interview ten).

Tina shared a similar experience with *Mary*, her residential worker of 12 years who she said was like a mother to her (Tina, Interview eleven). Luna also said

...there was one member of staff and I just loved her. She wasn't my key worker or anything but she was like the happiest bubbliest person ever... Whenever I heard that she was on shift I would get all happy because she was just so nice, and she would listen to me and she wouldn't sort of patronise me" (Luna, Interview one).

While Luna remembers personal characteristics about her favourite member of staff it is clear that it is the quality of the relationship that was key to the meaning making: listening, being there, caring, reliable and stable. This is consistent with the findings of Welch et al., 2018). John reflected "some of the staff members I didn't get on with maybe that's a personality thing, maybe it's not, who knows. There were certainly some that I did get on with very well" (John, Interview eight). Hamish and Tina spoke about being able to screen out staff who should not work within that environment. Hamish said he lived in the West End in lovely accommodation

with his own room, his primary care needs were met. However, his father removed him from the placement and took him to live with an aunt, and his father never returned for him. This resulted in him returning to the same residential placement.

Hamish said “there was one staff member took a grudge. I don’t know if she felt I’d betrayed her or abandoned her or whatever, but she was horrible after that...another lassie about a year later had a similar situation...and she got the same treatment” (Hamish, Interview nine). As I mentioned in the introduction to this research project, wounded healers are often found within the social care field. Staff within residential care may not have overcome their own early life experiences and this combined with stresses of the job could impact on relationships (Kilpatrick, Berridge, Sinclair, Larkin, Lucas, Kelly and Geraghty (2008).

Relationships within residential care are complex and ‘blocked care’ is a term used to describe “how stress can suppress a well-meaning parent’s capacity to sustain loving feelings and empathy towards his or her child” (Adapt, 2020). Increasing understanding of the residential workers role as ‘loco parentis’ and the potential for secondary or vicarious trauma when working with young people who have themselves experienced trauma was discussed in Chapter three. This may or may not have been the experience for this staff member. Tina also spoke about staff being screened out of the system. She said

...there are some members of staff that I believe shouldn’t be working there (*the residential house*) that still are today... (*I’d ask*) what did you do before this like what other jobs did you do and I get the journey of all the jobs that they’d do before they got to this one and looking after me. And this member of staff said to me if I could get any other job tomorrow even working in Tesco, I would jump on it. So, it was basically him saying I would rather work in Tesco than look after you and he still works there (Tina, Interview eleven).

Tania spoke about trust and said: “I didn’t trust people because I was always getting told lies...so I didn’t really...build relationships with all the staff” (Tania, Interview four). She said “someone could walk into this (*room*) just now and I could be like I’m not going to get on with them or I kind of push them away. Or I’m like I love you and I want to stay in touch... I could see right through residential workers, and I could see right through foster carers and social workers” (Tania, Interview four). An inability to trust is something Kevin said he continues to experience post care. He said: “even now being surrounded by friends and stuff, it’s like you are so alone still” (Kevin, Interview five). Gabriel, Keller and Bombach (2021) found that

adults within their study displayed both emotional and social scepticism towards both themselves and others, that continued years after they left care.

Lisa said she missed out on the emotional support of having that one person to talk to within group living, that parental figure and stable individual you could tell everything to. Someone “that would cuddle me when I was crying or understand when I was upset” (Lisa, Interview two). For Liam the rituals of regular family life were not experienced until he was placed in a supported carers foster placement. The children’s home, with five other young people, afforded agency and allowed him to opt in or out of these routines. He reflects on missed family experiences such as the “kind of day-to-day life like going home from school and having dinner at the dinner table” (Liam, Interview ten).

The fear of loss had an impact on how Luna formed relationships with her peers within the residential environment. She said “I didn’t want to make friends with people in the unit. I knew that they were going to get moved or I was going to get moved so I had to be mature in that way and try to be a bit more like for myself and not depend on people” (Luna, Interview one). Despite this only Luna, Bruce and Mark spoke about sustained friendships post care with peers from their residential unit. Luna said that despite not being really close she continues to text and go to the cinema with someone from her previous children’s house. It would not be unusual for someone with a limited social support system to continue to have contact with someone with shared experiences. Both Bruce and Mark have also kept in contact with friends in placement which is very challenging within the establishments I have worked in as they do not promote these types of relationships, due to concerns that this will negatively impact on multiple young people’s placements. This view needs to be challenged, as young people without support networks will have less successful transitions out of care, I will revisit this shortly. Tania also spoke about struggling to build relationships and said

...I didn’t form a good circle of friends so I was always going about with the children from the residential unit I was in or if I was in foster then I would be going about with their daughter and her friends... so I found it difficult connecting with people at school, when I was out in the street, in different places” (Tania, Interview four).

7.6 Placement Bureaucracy and Being Institutionalised

Kevin gave three examples of the impact bureaucracy had on his life within the local community. He said: “my friends (*weren’t*) allowed to stay over at my house...when they (*came*) in my house, they (*had*) to sit in a reception room, (*as*) they weren’t allowed to come

through and sit in my bedroom” (Kevin, Interview five). This left Kevin feeling different from his peers as he was allowed to do that at his friend’s house. Practices within residential establishments can be focused on the potential for risk, accountability and blame so decision making around leaving children unsupervised can be immovable.

Kevin also said that

...being in care, I wasn’t given the same opportunities as other kids. My friends went to Ayr beach, and I was like given into so much trouble and there were situations where I was refused money for the train because people were going to be drinking because there was a beach there. Like there was no proof and I actually never touched alcohol until I was 17. I’m not allowed to go to the beach because there’s not an active lifeguard on duty” (Kevin, Interview five).

Reflecting on a friendship Kevin said

...I remember I stayed with a boy once, a friend from school and I was staying overnight and I begged for my residential home to tell his parents that they were just my parents because they had to phone and get information like where did he stay. I said to the care people can you just pretend that you are my mum on the phone just finding out their address of where they stay and contact numbers. They said they can’t do that so they phoned his mum and dad and they said that we are Kevin’s residential staff he stays in a residential home and his mum and dad were like what the hell is going on and why were you lying in the first place, you need to go home” (Kevin, Interview five).

Kevin spoke about becoming “so institutionalised where you predict people’s shifts...you know about fire regulations, you know that people monitor every single moment of every single day...(staff) sat in front of the TV in daily logs...then like you have to sign things off throughout your full life, will you sign this and sign out for your pocket money” (Kevin, Interview five).

Tina also reflected on being institutionalised to the point that her perception of norms was informed by her experiences to such an extent that she thought that someone came to your house to collect a sanitary bin. She also spoke about cupboards containing toiletries and confectionary to monitor eating and manage risks around solvent abuse and self-harm. She found joy in her own tenancy, from using candles that had previously been viewed as a ‘safety

hazard', to not worrying about leaving a razor lying around for fear someone would use it to hurt themselves.

Kevin also spoke about the unjust nature of residential care where "kids weren't going to school and still getting on the PC and I wouldn't get on it at night because there were timetabled schedules" (Kevin, Interview five). Of course, there can be many reasons why a young person may struggle to attend school such as bullying, parental attitudes towards education and feelings of social isolation (Malcom, Wilson, Davidson and Kirk, 2003).

7.7 Lost Childhoods

While four of the participants did not feel they missed out on anything significant, eloquently put by Bob who said "trips abroad aye, there were certain units got the chance to go abroad and other units didn't it was just that type of thing. That was one of the chances that I didn't get but everything that I needed I got" (Bob, Interview thirteen). A few of the young people interviewed felt they had lost out on the importance of everyday ordinary childhood experiences within residential care. Luna spoke about missing family events and of not being thought of as part of the family. She said:

...if I looked on Facebook and my Nana had a barbecue in her back garden but I'd not been invited because either no one really thought to invite me or it was just a spur of the moment thing. Little things like that where people are like oh it's a nice day let's go out the back garden and have a barbecue. It's just little things like that and just little things you don't really think about too much if you are there but if you're not there you kind of miss it because you're like awe that looked like a good day sort of thing" (Luna, Interview one).

Mark said "you can't really do as much in residential as you could outwith so I suppose I missed some things" (Mark, Interview seven). Kevin was less able to articulate what his lost childhood felt like at the time stating he "missed out on everything" (Interview five). He gave many examples where he was not given the same opportunities as his peers who were not looked after, such as normal growing up experiences like train trips with friends for fear he would misuse the money.

Kevin's sense of loss appears to come from the impact his care experience was having on his life now when "your childhood is completely robbed from you. I know now that, I'm only 22

years old (*and*) I don't get to enjoy my life the same as other people do" (Kevin, Interview five). One of the problems with the comparisons made by young people about their lives is similar to the statistical information comparing young people who have experienced residential care with those who have remained within the general population outwith the social work system. We are comparing rich with poor, care experienced with non-care experienced and not comparing a young person who has been accommodated with what their life chances may have been like if they had not gone in to care. Scottish Government (2021c) studies of educational outcomes illustrate that for young people who remain looked after within the family home, their academic attainment is lower than those who have been removed to residential care at level 4 and above although for children who have been placed with a relative or within a foster placement, these outcomes are significantly higher. For five of the young people in this study, they believe they would have died, been in prison or been addicted to or selling substances if they hadn't been in care, although at present this cannot be supported by literature as consistent figures are not captured nationally.

7.8 The Stigma

Bob said: "every time something happened, where the residential unit was situated...the police were up 24/7...it was (*blamed on*) the one's in the unit, definitely there was a stigma" (Bob, Interview thirteen). Stigma is something that was experienced by all but Bruce and Mark, although Mark reflects that on going to college fellow students were curious about why he had been in care. Carol shares a similar experience to other participants in the study and says "just from the public and all that and like your friends... just because we were in care they always think that you are in there just for the one reason and that's just because you've been bad and they don't understand that there's more like to why you are in there" (Carol, Interview three). She felt bullied by her workmates who could not relate to her care experience so she left and returned to college (Carol, Interview three). Studies show that paid employment and volunteering promote self-efficacy and esteem by promoting agency in children and young people (Newman and Blackburn, 2002). However, lower academic achievements and precarious economic situations impact on their stability Garcia-Alba et al., 2021).

Tina was the only participant who spoke about being open about her care identity while she was at school, this experience is not unusual with many care experienced individuals hiding this part of their identity (Paul, 2017). Tina said

...all my year and people who weren't in my year at school they all knew I was care experienced and I lived in a children's unit and stuff like that but some people in the corridor would be like there's big Tina, like big mental Tina. They didn't know me but just had this opinion of me sort of thing that because I was in care I was crazy...but I wouldn't harm a fly" (Interview eleven). She also faced stigma from her family and said "so I felt kind of estranged from them cos they would hold my behaviour against me like the way I worked through my trauma they kind of didn't realise it was because of that and it wasn't just because I was a bad kid so they didn't want to meet me anymore" (Tina, Interview eleven).

After leaving care Tina returned to visit staff who had supported her in the residential house. She describes her experience with a member of the public. She said

...I still go back and visit the unit...and sometimes I'll talk to the nightshift...and sometimes I'll get a taxi home...and they will be like so have you just finished your shift then and I will be like yeah, yeah because I don't want to have to explain the whole palaver sort of thing and then I listen for about ten to fifteen minutes on the journey to my house about how awful kids in care are and are they terrible to work with? He thinks I'm a residential worker and they must be really violent and how his aunties stepbrother knows this guy who was horrible who was in care. And sometimes when I get out of the taxi I say well actually I used to live there and they are like so shocked because they didn't think that someone speaking like me, quite civilly, and that kind of thing could be looked after" (Tina, Interview eleven).

Luna compared her experience of residential care to that of foster care and while experiences can be similar (Avery, 2009), there are differences in that the former is in keeping with the dominant discourse that children should grow up in a family and therefore there is less stigma associated in Scotland with this provision (UNICEF, 2013; Care Review, 2020). She said

I think like when people know that you are in residential care they treat you a bit differently to say if you were in foster care, because I don't know I just feel there's a lot of negative stuff that's associated with residential care. That all the kids have to be violent or have to have done something to get in there...even my mum started to treat me differently from when I was in a foster placement. She started when I was arguing with my brother and sister, she'd say don't be too hard on Luna, she's in a unit now, it's harder for her. And I'm just kind of like well it's all hard (Luna, Interview one).

Tania wanted people to listen and trust her but she stated during the interview that she found it difficult to trust others. This paradox is hardly surprising when early life experiences are damaged as those who should have taken care of her were unable to do so. She said

...don't put care experienced people down as they can achieve anything that any other person or child can do... it's just that we've had a hard background and they might have had a tough background but they don't get stigmatized for it or discriminated against (Tania, Interview four).

Berk (2014) talks of how there is a transition in the meaning of deviance, in this sense what has historically been viewed as juvenile delinquency, from behaviour that individuals engage in, to the status of a group as defined by others, labelling, and Hamish spoke about how his behaviour mirrored people's perceptions of young people who live in residential homes. He said: "I kept lashing out at people as well, so it was a self-fulfilling prophecy" (Hamish, Interview nine). He also spoke about the stigma from schoolmates. He said as: "accommodating as they can be with (*Looked After Children - LAC*) reviews...sometimes it's during class and when they take us out of class (*classmates*) would be just like awe he's a bad guy" (Interview nine).

Hamish shared the same view as a few others within the study and said: "a lot of the stigma that was attached to me came from me and came from a lot of the kids who live in a home, we used to stigmatise each other" (Tina, Interview eleven). Killoh (2018) talks about the need to reframe the narrative around care, not just residential care. She says that no matter what the care setting stigma is overarching and continually re-enforced as there are negative connotations linked to being care experienced (Killoh, 2018).

Goffman differentiates between social identities which are shared - with all of the young people I interviewed, they all spoke of themselves as care experienced - and social alliances. He states that: "the stigmatized individual may exhibit identity ambivalence when he obtains a close sight of his own kind behaving in a stereotyped way" (Goffman, 1963, p.131). Two young people within the study, John and Kevin, spoke about trying to avoid the stigma by keeping as far away from all aspects of it as possible. John said

...I tried to keep as far away from people as I could so that there wouldn't be that stigma because I knew certain young people who didn't have that stigma attached to them... they stigmatise your parents, it could be they stigmatise something you could have done (John, Interview eight).

Similarly, Kevin attempted to avoid stigma by telling 'lies' about himself. He said: "you see so many other people becoming the stigma itself and becoming what people expect... I used to hang around with people who went to private school because it made me feel better than a kid who was in care" (Kevin, Interview five). Kevin spoke about people at school assuming his mother did not love him and that was why he was in a residential home.

Luna also spoke about hiding her reality by making up a narrative that she hoped would avoid some of the stigma associated with care. A shared care experience identity, with the support of the advocacy group, has allowed her to be open and honest and embrace her experience of care. She said that

...by coming to places like (*the Champions Advocacy Service*) and stuff I've sort of found a place where I can talk about this stuff and not make up stories like I used to, saying oh no I'm just living with my auntie because she's not well and I'm looking after her and you know and stuff like that. I can actually just turn around to someone and say, yeah, I was in a unit for four years, and if they ask me why I was there I will tell them why I was there. I'm not sort of ashamed of it anymore...I'm kind of proud...because I just never thought I'd be in a place where I'd just openly talk about it and openly say yes, I'm proud to be care experienced because it's nothing to be ashamed of (Luna, Interview one).

7.9 Support Network

Participants spoke about the support they received through the CAG (*Champions Advocacy Group*), and how no one within the group cared what form of care they had experienced. For John:

...when you come to groups...then of course everyone knows you're care experienced in one way or another whether that be residential care, kinship care, anything along those lines so there's not really a stigma there because you've all got similar experiences. But in school it's a bit different, not everyone understands (John, Interview eight).

Killoh (2018) said that she had to be walked home from school by a teacher due to fears that she would be physically attacked by bullies. The stigma of care placements was so evident that one young person spoke about a Member of Parliament proposing that 'care experience' should be reflected in the Equality Act. He said

I spoke to an MP the other day...who is going to try and pass a private bill for care experienced people to come under the Equality Act and for that to be a term that would be a protected characteristic so that stigma and stuff, it's like LGBTQA stuff. And that was from like me speaking to him and he wrote a tweet that from my full time of being an MP I've never been so impacted by an amazing young man (Kevin, Interview five).

There is increasingly acknowledgement that to address some of the poor outcomes young people experience as a result of being in care, that changes to the systems, processes, culture and law are necessary (Care Review, 2020). But these changes will not happen overnight and are part of a ten-year plan endorsed by the Scottish Government (Care Review, 2021).

Tina recognised that she spoke a different language from her classmates as she had learned social work jargon as part of her care experience. This is an experience shared by many other care experienced young people resulting in the development of a glossary entitled 'Language That Cares' (Jozwiak, 2019; The Adolescent and Children's Trust, 2019). But everyday language such as the use of the term siblings can become institutionalised by individuals and systems when staff use this terminology inappropriately. It would not be unusual for staff to ask children if they were looking forward to '*contact with your siblings*' rather than saying are you looking forward to seeing your brothers and sisters today? That is less about language and more about cultural norms that can re-enforce discrimination. Beveridge (2018) noted that when she asked for access to her care records, the complicated language meant that she needed the narratives translated for her. Tina said

...when I was at school...I would say I can't meet you for lunch today because I need to go to my panel and people went what's a panel. So I realized quite quickly that I was using different words and people don't know what it means and all these social work services, I know all these systems...I remember getting told if I don't go to a panel the police would send out a warrant for my arrest, they'd come to the school and handcuff me and my friends, I remember them going, do it, do it, but that really scared me thinking the police would come to school and take me out of class (Tina, Interview eleven).

It would not be unusual for a child to internalise the language used by those around them in care just as children would do growing up within a family. It is difficult for staff to understand that this is not the child's own language, they are sharing what they have learned from staff.

As well as the barriers posed by language, Kevin spoke about obstacles that can result from a member of staff comparing looked after children to their own. He said

...a lot of kids go straight from school to uni, like that is a fact. So what is it 4% of kids in care go straight from school to university as opposed to 37% of the general population...I think to have a mentality where you are like you've been in residential like you probably will struggle more than other people. It definitely made me think that I'm not good enough for this whereas I got better results than more of my peers who went (Kevin, Interview five).

Tina spoke about her teacher's perception and said "I failed a biology test by a couple of marks...and my teacher she took me out of class and she said is it because you are in care?" (Tina, Interview eleven). It is difficult to imagine how these young people can experience a normative childhood when these situations occur, there is a sense that you are met with obstacles at every turn.

7.10 Experiences: The Good and the Bad

Every participant in this study had experience of group living, twelve lived within residential care and one in secure accommodation. Inherently, secure care results in a loss of liberty as young people are locked within the provision but there were only three expressed differences within interviews outside this detail. These related to the experience of focussed intervention work referred to as 'programmes', having an awareness of how long you would spend within your placement and having control over this. This was described by young people in a study by Gough (2016: 16) as 'doing their time'. A key driver for engagement for one young person was engaging with the process as it was noted that this could result in a reduction of time within the secure setting (Lisa, Interview two). Statistical evidence would support that lengths of time within secure accommodation are considerably lower than time spent within another group care setting (Children's Social Work Statistics, 2021). Whilst 20% of children in residential care remain there for more than 5 years, only 2% of children accommodated within secure care do so for more than one year (Children's Social Work Statistics, 2021). Lisa expected to remain there for a period of up to a year but was released after six months. She said I "did engage in the programmes and done everything that I was asked to do that's why the transition was quicker". For all other participants within the study there was a lack of agency, and sense of helplessness around their situation and the control they had over it as they felt that their fate was in the hands of external agents (Care Review, 2020). Decision making was something raised by Bruce and Bob. When asked if anything could have made

his experience better Bruce said: “I don’t think there’s anything big, I think it’s more the small things like taking too long to make a decision and not communicating effectively, but apart from that no” (Bruce, Interview six).

Mark and John enjoyed their residential care experience with John saying it “was fairly good across the board” (John, Interview eight). This view was shared by Hamish who highlighted it is the people who make the placement important. He said he would

...genuinely struggle to gripe... (*about his residential experience as*) there’s a lot of times where I know care is bad, but people I had in my life tried to take care of me” (Interview 9). He also said “you hear a lot of bad when you are in here (*advocacy group discussions*), you hear a lot of it and you’re like I don’t want to talk about my good things. I mean like maybe they are like me, they had their bits and bobs that were bad but they prefer to dwell on the good. I used to feel guilty telling my mates that I had a good time in care...because they’d all had bad times and it’s only recently me and a few others who have had good times have been able to be like no we’ve had a good time” (Hamish, Interview nine).

Tina also said: “I do feel quite guilty cos I’ve got quite a good experience in the care system and not everyone has that” (Tina, Interview eleven). Few pieces of research highlight the good experiences young people have within residential care (see Forrester, Goodman, Cocker, Binnie and Jensch, 2009 for an exception) as the focus is largely on how to make provision better or as earlier stated to review practice as a result of an inquiry (Shaw, 2007; Care Review, 2020). As we will see in the next chapter, there is also a hierarchy of experiences empowering those with the most traumatic or troublesome time in care to be promoted as advocates for change.

Kevin said that his “care experience was really difficult..., I was always different from the other young people that I lived with, purely because it was a very unsettled environment” (Kevin, Interview five). Othering is something that several people within the study did to disassociate themselves from what they considered to be the poor behaviour of other children within their placement. Kevin saw himself as different to others who acted out as a way of expressing how they were feeling. He also felt that the environment reflected low expectations and aspirations, this experience is supported by other reports (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2011; Care Review, 2020, Scottish Government, 2021c). He said: ...when I was doing well in exams it was always like well-done Kevin and then I was like oh thanks, but the

other boys weren't getting any motivation...and I would feel like why are you not pushing my brother to go and succeed and do well (Kevin, Interview five).

Kevin spoke about seeing young people in the unit struggle when it was time to leave. He said personal characteristics and strengths and the view that education would help him to flourish meant that he would do well in life, but this was tempered by his discussion about beginning counselling to help him come to terms with his experiences.

7.11 Relationships with Other Professionals

Bob discussed other professional relationships he had while in care. He said: "my social worker, I never seen them every two weeks, it was like every month, every two months so it wasn't a good relationship" (Bob, Interview thirteen). The reality is that across local authority areas there is no consistency around a worker's contact with a young person, unless the young person is the subject of child protection or vulnerable young person status. This would result in visits taking place on a weekly basis. Bob described his throughcare worker who visited every two or three months and he had responsibility for all looked after young people within (LA7) (*Local Authority Area 7 of this study*). He spoke about the same worker supporting a young person who currently lives in a residential placement and stated that he is suffering from the same lack of support he experienced several years ago. He contrasted statutory relationships with the positive relationship he had with his advocate. When they met, the advocate said to him "you're my boss so anything you want I will try and get what you want" (Bob, Interview thirteen). Amy also mentioned her through care worker and said: "I was getting to do all the cooking and I was getting taken away to a flat to do cooking lessons and like my own washing and stuff...it was more throughcare and aftercare rather than staff" who sustained a relationship (Amy, Interview twelve). The importance of relationships cuts across all areas of social care and social work practice (Care Review, 2020).

As mentioned earlier, a lack of consistency in the professional social work relationship was highlighted by Lisa and John. John said: "I went through eight social workers in five years which isn't ideal. It's having to get to know someone else, someone else who knows everything about you and someone else making decisions and you probably don't want them making those decisions" (Interview eight). Lisa said she: "had thirteen social workers in four and a half to five years or so it was, I never had that one person I could talk to" (Lisa, Interview two).

Hamish said: "you understand a bit more (*as you get older*) ... you understand why social workers are the way they are. I found out that my last social worker had 28 cases...no wonder

she had such a shit time” (Interview nine). Hamish reflects an understanding that overwork and a high caseload impacted on his social workers ability to support him in the way that he needed. Campbell (2018) shared a similar understanding of his social worker when he spoke about his experience growing up within care in England (Professional Social Work, 2018). This should not be something that children have to consider when they need support and care from professionals.

Like Bob earlier, Luna reflected on her relationship with advocacy services. She said:

...I know I’ve spoken about them twice already but ... *(it)* really is like the place, like the people that helped me do that like not even the staff members...but like the young people here and stuff as well because they all know what you’ve gone through. To be quite frank, no one cares that you are in a unit or foster care or whatever, no one cares because they are like big deal, me too (Interview one).

The levelling within the advocacy service was expressed by John and Hamish and all but Liam mentioned this service as a source of strength and positive identity formation within interviews, his perception of the service was something you used when you needed help. While this can be associated with issues around gender and masculinity there is an emphasis within the Care Review that advocacy should be afforded to all young people as it offers a widened independent network of support for young people in care (Care Review, 2000). The fact that this is highlighted would suggest that it is not always offered. The development of a positive care identity seemed to be at the heart of this experience. Luna said

...I’ve become proud of my care identity, I think because that’s been really hard for me because for ages, I’ve blamed myself, I’ve blamed my mum and all these other people but it’s not really about blame (Luna, Interview one).

7.12 Relationships with Family - Parental and Sibling Contact

Three respondents spoke about their fathers living outside Scotland and only one of these had contact with his father who initially attempted to rescue him from his residential home placement. Hamish had the only father who had unsolicited contact, but this was tainted by him being abandoned. He said

When I was in the children’s home my dad found out about a year and a half later and he came one day and he just demanded that I go and live with him and I didn’t know any different so I went. He left me at my aunts ...and he never came

back. When social work found out they took me back (*to*) my same bed and it was like two months later (Hamish, Interview nine).

Kevin said I

...think social work must have made contact with him (*father*). He came up to visit me like twice which has really damaged me emotionally...My mum, they kind of forced contact with her despite me not wanting it...my brother was going (*to visit*) so they said I think it might be a good thing for you to go and see her. So I went to go and see her for a couple of years but it became far too difficult and I think the unit manager noticed that and she was my kind of go to girl so to speak and I really latched on to her and I ended up not going to see my mum anymore...but she attended my children's panel and I really struggled with that (Kevin, Interview five).

Kevin's lack of paternal contact is another rejection and while his mother played a more major role in his life he had no desire to have an ongoing relationship with either of his parents at this point in his life. Most respondents blamed their mother for being accommodated and they did not want contact with her during their time in care as is reflected in Luna's account

...it's a bit strange...there was people in my unit who never seen their family, their birth family, and... I was really lucky that my mum did try but for me she didn't try hard enough but it was harder than other people's parents and stuff like that. I kind of felt a lot of resentment because it was actually my mum who put me into the care system. So for that I...felt a bit resentful and that sort of made our relationship that little bit harder when I did go into the unit...at that point I was still trying to blame someone and I know it's not really about blame but at that point I was like you know you put me in this situation and now you are trying to wrap me in cotton wool (Luna, Interview one).

Further research is needed to explore the relationship between looked after children and their parents as studies and statistical information reflect that children are more likely to return to the family home on leaving care (Bullock, Litte and Millham, 1993; Duncalf, Hill and McGhee, 2013; SCRA, 2017; Scottish Government, 2017). Tania spoke about current family relationships and contact saying: "I do talk to like my mum and one of my sisters, but I would rather not speak to them. I was obviously taken out on my contact because it was like to see

my family, but I didn't really enjoy it" (Tania, Interview four). For Bruce there was none or difficult family contact. He said of his mum's role while he was in care

apart from making it more difficult... just more pressure on me to make decisions and stuff when making decisions that I did make independently even harder. Like going against them if it didn't suit my mums opinion...over the last few years I've not had any (*contact with my mum*) at all but that's been a choice that I've made (Bruce, Interview six).

Hamish shared a similar memory illustrating the importance of an independent advocate to ensure that children are listened to. He said

...for the first year my mum was invited to every one of my LAC (*Looked After Children*) reviews. Eventually I told her she wasn't allowed to come as it was the only time I seen her. It wasn't her fault but back then I blamed her because she just left me there, there was that whole abandonment thing. So I told the LAC review that I didn't want her there so they stopped her coming (Hamish, Interview nine).

For Liam contact with his parents while he was accommodated was sporadic. They "weren't really a big part of it. They were really kind of in and out. They weren't really consistent in terms of visiting me, I would kind of go and find them" (Liam, Interview ten). Bob also said that following an incident the Children's Hearing stopped family contact for two to three months when the panel members deemed him "a danger to society and...a danger to (*his*) maw and da" (Bob, Interview thirteen).

While most respondents did not want contact with their parents, all of the respondents with siblings wanted contact with their brothers and sisters. Research "suggests that membership of a sibling group is a unique part of the identity of a child or young person and can promote a sense of belonging and promote positive self-esteem and emotional wellbeing" (NICE/SCIE, 2010, p.33). This was something Luna found particularly challenging

One of the hard things for me in the unit was the fact that my brother and my sister were still staying with my mum when I went into care and for me that was really difficult. In a way I started to resent them as well because I felt the whole

why me. Why am I the only one who is in care which then obviously led into me, oh yeah obviously it's my fault, they're not here (Luna, Interview one).

Despite feelings of blame Luna reflected that her brother treated her better because she was accommodated because he missed her so much. She felt that this helped her to manage the situation better. This contrasted with the relationship she had with her slightly older sister who she always had a poor relationship with. She said

...my sister was a little bit jealous about the unit. You know they would like... give us like bursaries for Christmas and money for birthdays and that and she was really jealous of that because she didn't get that stuff and that really annoyed me because I was like well I might have got a new phone and clothes and stuff but you're still living with mum.... I still sort of said yeah I kick off a lot, you know I'm not the most well-behaved person so I sort of deserve this sort of thing (Luna, Interview one).

Luna felt that the one-year age gap between her and her older sister and similarities in their personalities meant that they clashed and the relationship has not improved now she no longer lives in the children's unit. Mark also spoke about how his contact with his brothers and sisters was limited while he was in care, although he spent the least amount of time in care. He said "I only have two brothers and a sister. So, they used to visit me whenever they could. They have their own lives and stuff, which I understood" (Mark, Interview seven). While Hamish did not want his mother to attend his Looked After Children (*LAC*) reviews he was happy enough to have contact with her and said, "I still had contact because I've got two brothers and she didn't want me to stop seeing them, so that was cool" (Hamish, Interview nine). As mentioned in the previous chapter, sibling rivalry is a normative part of growing up for most children with siblings (Isaacs, 2006; Klass, 2009). But there is an added complexity to the relationship when one of the children are 'different' because they are being brought up outwith the family home. The affectional bonds that would naturally develop in relationships will be impaired and as is evident in the narratives of participants, they may be difficult, although not impossible to rebuild (Bowlby, 1979).

Despite earlier negative accounts of social work systems that kept sibling groupings apart within placement, Liam was grateful to social workers for facilitating family contact and said

“my brothers and sisters and stuff I got to visit them. The social work played a big part in making arrangements for visits and things like that” (Liam, Interview ten). The sisterly relationship for Lisa was considerably different from that of Luna’s. A massive family split on the paternal side of her family meant that Lisa, her sister, and grandmother had no extended family and grandmother had considerable health difficulties. She said “me and my sister have quite a good relationship, but she was six years younger...so she didn’t really know what was going on” when I went into care (Lisa, Interview two).

7.13 The Extended Family

Three of the recipients made comments about their extended family. For the first of these it was to rule them out as being a source of support due to family conflict (Lisa, Interview two). John described a significant part of his life as being part of a kinship care arrangement. He lived with his stepsister until the death of his grandmother resulting in both of them being accommodated into care. His half sibling, who had always stayed with his aunt, remained there and he recognized that this was not a viable option for him due to the conflict he had with his sibling as reflected in this account

I did have contact with my sister and my aunt because although I couldn’t have lived with my sister, me and my sister just couldn’t have got along enough to live together because we didn’t from a young age... My sister was an only child and was used to it being that way so it would have just caused too much tension in the household without bringing in two other young people. So, I had contact with my aunt and my sister (John, Interview eight).

For Kevin visits to his aunt were routinised and unnatural. He said: “I went to visit some of my aunts now and again but again there was like no consistency and it was like so monitored and it was routine almost, so I would have to go and see my aunt like every two or four weeks” (Kevin, Interview five).

7.14 Conclusion

This chapter has helped to put residential care into a context with reference to the experiences of young people who spent time there. It highlighted how the urban myths around this form of care is rooted in historical perceptions of the workhouse or orphanage and this legacy has been difficult to shake resulting in young people being fearful when they are told that they are going there to live. These fears are not alleviated by workers transitioning young people to their placement, the decision for most of the participants to be placed in residential care, was made at a children's hearing. The panel members placed them on compulsory measures of supervision although it was noted by almost half of the group that they did not know why they were taken into care.

Young people spoke about the stigma associated with group care as it was viewed as being their fault that they could not live with a family. Two of the participants spoke about creating narratives to hide from others that they were placed in residential care (Luna and Kevin, Interviews one and five). Additionally, two of the young people avoided contact with their peers in a bid to avoid some of the stigma (Kevin and John, Interviews five and eight). This must be a very isolating experience for children and young people, and this is exacerbated by brothers and sisters who continued to remain at home with their family. Out of sight, out of mind was discussed by Luna when she found out that her family enjoyed a barbecue without thinking about inviting her. These everyday memories and experiences were absent for the group leaving participants feeling that they had lost their childhoods. Limited access to the wider family network, for all but John who spent a significant period of his life living with his grandmother, meant that family time was planned and formalized leaving children feeling unwanted (Kevin and Tina, Interviews five and eleven).

Lost childhoods were also linked to bureaucracy within residential care. Activities enjoyed by peers in the general population were obstacles to be overcome within the placement as risk assessments and red tape had to be overcome for simple trips such as a day at the beach or a sleep over with friends. Young people also felt that they had gaps in experiences within placements, and this in part may result from a lack of continuity with family relationships. Instability was a feature for most of the group. Changes within the group setting, staff and young people leaving, and different sets of expectations all left young people feeling a little bit lost (Care Review, 2020). There was a marked difference regarding expectations of duration of placement with a quarter of young people in residential care living there for five years or

more, compared to only 2% for young people placed within secure care (Children's Social Work Statistics, 2021). For many young people in the study they experienced multiple placement moves and unlike those placed within secure care where the duration of the stay allowed for a level of agency, for children in residential care there is a lack of control.

It is noted that 12 out of the 13 participants experienced support from the Champions Advocacy Group. This support network enabled them to talk about their experiences of care although two participants said that they struggled to speak about their positive experiences (Hamish and Tina, Interviews nine and four). There was discussion about a hierarchy of narratives with young people put forward by the Champions Advocacy Group when their stories were viewed as impactful and shocking as it appeared that this was likely to have the greatest effect on changes in policy and practice.

Relationships were explored and all the young people made meaningful relationships with at least one individual. These were formed with various workers including residential staff, social workers, throughcare and teaching staff and the key ingredients to relationships being successful were highlighted. The chapter highlighted many of the challenges young people face as they live apart from their families. It showed that they attempt to make sense of themselves and their multiple identities in a world that may have appeared challenging and perplexing, due in part to a lack of stability and agency or understanding about why they were placed in care.

CHAPTER EIGHT: FROM STATE CARE TO LIVING MORE INDEPENDENTLY

8.1 Introduction

The previous chapter illustrated the complexity of relationships within the group care setting. The importance of non-familial relationships was established, and I will show that these relationships can be crucial when young people move on from care. These informal relationships were discussed and participants described carers that were akin to parental figures who provided nurturing affective support within placements that had been sustained over many years (Ibsen and Klobus, 1972). This chapter will illustrate how a lack of infrastructure within the care leaving system can add to experiences of young people feeling let down and not receiving the emotional support they require when relationships they form continue.

The chapter will also discuss Stein's typology as he has developed a resilience framework which categorises care experienced young people into one of three profiles (Stein, 2006). His typology illustrates that young people transitioning into adulthood can be described as 'moving on', 'survivors' and 'strugglers' and the participant group show that there can be movement between categories as they develop and age (Stein, 2006; Stein and Dumaret, 2011). While this will be explored within the chapter, young people will not be given these labels, given the small sample size, to ensure confidentiality and anonymity is maintained. It also feels inappropriate given that young people identified within Chapter seven that they have been the subject of stigma and labels for most of their lives. However, this typology helps to illustrate that there are consistent experiences across the care experienced population but while there are consistencies within the group of participants, there is also diversity that is evident across and within experiences. The complexity of these experiences helps to show that a one size fits all approach to aftercare provision is fundamentally flawed, even when comparing a relatively small sample size. Trajectories are complex and further qualitative research is needed if we are to continue to develop our understanding in this area (Schoon and Lyons-Amos, 2016; Pinkerton, 2021).

The chapter will conclude by looking at the transition to adulthood which can be viewed as a life stage or a process which is referred to by many as emerging adulthood, a theoretical perspective that reflects the experience of young people aged 18 to 29 years, particularly in industrialised western societies (Arnett, 2007a; Galambos and Martinez, 2007; Zacaes, Serra and Torres, 2015).

8.2 The Reality of Leaving Care and not Home

All the participants in this study left care between the ages of 16 and 21 years of age. For over half of the young people care accounted for more than one third of their lives while for two of the females in the group this was almost their entire life experience to date. This leaving care age is higher than the national average as statistics show that most care leavers are aged between 16 and 18 years old despite the average leaving home age in Scotland being 25 years old (CELCIS, 2015). While it could be assumed that the higher age range of my study group may have resulted from the changes in legislation evident in the Children and Young People (Scotland) Act, 2014 which raised the age for leaving care and ongoing support as outlined in chapter four, none of the participants spoke about receiving formal state support beyond their 21st birthdays.

The Office for National Statistics (2020) shows that 55% of males and 51% of females in the general population continue to live with their parents between the ages of 21 and 30 years old. While no one in the study was afforded this continuity as they had been removed from their parents' or grandparents' care, Lisa returned to live with her mother immediately after being in care as a temporary arrangement to allow the local authority time to secure her permanent accommodation and Bob returned to live with his parents for almost 7 years (Lisa and Bob, Interviews two and thirteen). For Bob this did not immediately follow his care experience and while our interview was several years later, he still found it difficult to understand why he was not allowed to live with his family in the first place especially as he feels it had been successful when he finally returned home, "I was back staying with my parents there for like six or seven years" (Bob, Interview thirteen). A lack of understanding and information around why he was in care appeared to add to this angst and as was highlighted in the previous chapter, this lack of information-sharing and understanding was not an unusual situation.

Bullock's (1993) study of almost 900 children found that most of them returned home to their parents or wider family network after care irrespective of the reason for them being taken into care in the first place and the duration of time they spent away from their family. Subsequent studies have supported this finding although none of the studies relate solely to care leavers (Carlson, Hutton, Preist and Melia, 2019; Neil, Gitsels and Thoburn, 2020). One explanation for Bob's successful return home post-care could be in his ongoing relationship with his family throughout his care experience. This was viewed as one of the indicators for successful reunification (Bullock, 1993; Carlson et. Al, 2019; Neil, Gitsels and Thoburn, 2020). This

research is supported by statistical information although there is an indication that figures are falling. In 2010 62% of young people returned to live with their biological parents post care and this number had reduced to 54% by 2020 (Scottish Government, 2021). This was the case for only 7% in my study, but this may result from the small sample size and the nature of the recruitment process, that involved all but one participant being sourced through an advocacy agency. This is a limitation of this study. It may be that young people who return home do not view ongoing advocacy as crucial to their support system when they leave care, and this was almost the only source of recruitment for candidates in this study. Chakrabarti and Hill (2000, p. 22) found that longer term outcomes were not usually as good “for those young people without supportive families to return to”. I will return to ongoing support systems later in the chapter.

This study reflected that young people have a good understanding of what constitutes leaving care and they appear to use the legal definition of this. Leaving care is formally defined “as the cessation of legal responsibility by the state for young people” (Scottish Government, 2004b, p.9) with the study group appearing to view their removal from a supervision order by the Children’s Hearing system as evidence that they had left care. This meant that for some young people they had left care when they moved on from their residential placement even though they may have moved on to supported accommodation while for others they did not leave care until they moved on from their supported accommodation. Those who moved on from supported accommodation largely felt more equipped for adult life with Bob being the only exception to this (Bob, Interview thirteen).

Before moving on to look at the preparation and planning young people experienced before leaving care it is important to recognise that the impact of the leaving care experience can be hard hitting. Amy described how she felt when she found out she was leaving care. She said

I knew I wasn’t ready as soon as the decision was made but it was what I wanted for so long as soon as I got (into) care I was determined that I was getting out and then it happened. I got out a week after my 16th birthday and I wasn’t ready. I asked to stay an extra night (Amy, Interview twelve).

Amy stated that this was not allowed. Hamish left care at the age of 19 years old having been ‘bin-bagged’, a term used to describe when young people leave care with their belongings in black bin bags. In 2012 The Guardian reported an article written by Stein which spoke about the ‘National Voice’ and their work to end young people leaving care with their belongings in

binbags. In 2005 they had highlighted the experience of fostered young people in their 'This is not a suitcase' campaign (The Guardian, 2012; Children and Young People Now, 2005). A young person reflected that bin bags are for rubbish so it is a poor reflection on how care leavers are viewed (Guardian, 2012). Hamish said, "in fairness they did try to kick me out when I was 16 but my mate fought for me", one of the other young people he lived with advocated on his behalf (Hamish, Interview nine). He believes that decisions are made about young people by the 'high-heid yins' (this is a colloquialism that describes people in charge).

An academic and former residential manager, McPheat speaks about his experience of leadership and management in residential care and reflects on how these services can be overseen by an external manager who may not have worked in the sector, have limited understanding of the service and who do not comprehend some of the decisions that have to be grappled with (Hicks, 2015). Smith (2015) reflects on the changes in the residential sector and the increasing scrutiny and regulation with managers and leaders focussing on the three e's of economy, efficiency, and effectiveness. He stated that there has been a shift from care to corporate concerns as the model of care became more industrial as discussed in Chapter four (Smith, 2015). Whatever the reason Hamish almost left care at 16 years old, moving on three years later with his possessions in rubbish bags is not how any young person should transition out of care services. The next section will look at whether young people felt prepared for this transition and for moving on and taking a step closer to adulthood.

8.3 Preparation and Planning for Moving On

The Pathways handbook describes throughcare as "the ongoing preparation and support of young people who have been looked after and may soon be making the transition to live more independently" (Care Commission, 2009, p. 2). While one young person appeared to have formal preparation for leaving care and another spoke about a plan that he did not see the point in, no one in the study spoke about having had a pathways assessment and pathways plan, despite this process having been part of throughcare preparation providing a framework and handbook enabling social work staff to help support youngsters moving on from care (Scottish Executive, 2004a). Competing pressures and the prioritisation of children seen as more in need or at risk may have impacted on these low figures. Scottish Government (2020) data shows that of the 326 young people who were looked after within residential establishments at the age of 16 years old 266 had a pathways plan with 258 also having a pathways coordinator as described in chapter three, showing an average of 82%. These statistics have improved since 2011 when only 78% of young people looked after outwith their

parental home had pathways plans but the publishing of these statistics seems to have had little impact on local authorities' accountability in this area. For the young people within this study, all of whom would have met the criteria for pathways planning as they were all born after 1988, only 15% discussed plans.

Despite not discussing a 'pathways' plan, Tina said that she was prepared for leaving care and she seems to have experienced a supportive and well-planned transition from her residential home. She was 19 years old when she left her placement and after having been in care for 16 years and experiencing 14 moves in her early years. Quantitative data is not gathered either locally or nationally so there is no way of knowing how unusual this number of placement moves is. Tina remained in a stable residential placement for 12 years, essentially growing up there (Tina, Interview eleven). Her experience highlights best practice within residential care and illustrates what well thought out care can look like when preparing young people for moving on. She said

...when you turned 15 they put you on an independent living plan so for me it was quite gradual ... I first started round about 15 I would tidy my own room, I would do my own washing and I'd get myself up for school, they gave me an alarm clock...When I got a little bit older, so after I'd been doing that for a bit I'd be about 15 and a half - 16, I'd start cooking a couple of meals on my own, ... it was mostly dinners, but as that progressed I would do all my meals and they would take me out shopping... They would give me a specific amount of money so maybe like ten, fifteen pounds and I would go to the shops near my house. They would take me for the first couple of months... and they'd help me cook as well. The cook would tell me how to prepare some meals that I liked that she'd made for me over the years, so she showed me how to make things from scratch and how to eat healthily as well (Tina, Interview eleven).

Lisa and Amy, the youngest care leavers who moved on at the age of 16 years old, felt that they were ready to move on because they had developed practical skills such as cooking and cleaning, but both reflected that they did not know how to pay bills and they needed guidance and emotional support (Lisa and Amy, Interviews two and twelve). This view was echoed by the males who moved on from supported accommodation, aside from Bob who felt neither residential care nor his supported placement prepared him for leaving care, he felt that the second placement was just an extension of the first with no real difference aside from age

(Bob, Interview thirteen). In reality, young people should begin preparation from the beginning of their time in care which appears to have been the case for only one young person within the study (Norrie, 1995; Tina, Interview eleven). Three young people said that supported accommodation gave them the opportunity to gain skills, for Bruce this included door management skills, this enabled Bruce to make judgements about who he let into the house keeping himself and others safe (Bruce, Mark and John, Interviews six, seven and eight). He said “it gave me the right circumstances to do things that I feel necessary. Develop at my own pace and not be as rushed as most people can be especially in care” (Bruce, Interview six).

While most of the young people in the study spoke about feeling prepared with some practical skills, Kevin said that “he didn’t feel like mentally ready to move on” when he left the children’s home and moved in with supported carers (Kevin, Interview five), I will revisit this when discussing ongoing relationships when young people move on from a placement. As previously illustrated in chapter seven and as mentioned by Bruce as an issue when things feel rushed, a balance must be struck between the competing demands of individual young people and the group, eloquently reflected in Kevin’s account in chapter seven where he stated that staff prioritised the most challenging situations to the detriment of others within the group. This appears to be a resource issue as staffing should be reflective of the residential group needs. The Care Inspectorate (2021) have produced guidance for organisations to ensure that staffing levels and young people’s needs are matched. Luna, among others including Liam and Bob felt that staff did not really have the time to prepare her for adulthood. Luna said “like the unit I was in, there was seven other young people, so it was quite a busy unit. But even like that, I think I mean I’m sure they could have done better at like helping me at cooking and (*helping*) me with my laundry and all that sort of stuff” (Luna, Interview one).

John spoke about some of the practical barriers to young people being prepared for leaving care. When talking about how his experiences had prepared him, he said

...probably not the residential care experience but the (*supported accommodation*) experience did more so. You had to budget, you had to pay electricity, you had to pay rent, you had to pay things like that – especially if you were working full time. So those are key life skills you don’t learn in residential care when you’ve got cleaners, you’ve got everything handed to you (John, Interview eight).

John contrasted this account with his experience within a residential setting where he said that he perhaps cooked twice a week or undertook laundry which he believed could be seen as life skills, but there was no preparation in terms of financial management or budgeting. He

feels that there could have been a lot more preparation that might have prepared him more for the shock of moving into the 'real world' (John, Interview eight). Children and young people would not usually hold financial management responsibility for much outside of pocket money, unless they had work such as a paper round. This however gives some opportunity to manage one's own money. Within residential care there is a fear that money will be misused so it is usually held centrally which appears to encourage young people to spend it all at once, to gain some sense of control over it.

Kevin spoke about staff cleaning his room and cooking for him meaning that he missed out on that preparation himself. He said that planning for his future took the form of moving from one situation where he was ill-prepared to another with the only alternative offered to him being his own council flat which he knew he was not ready for. He was also concerned that any council flat he would be offered would take him back to his old community where he felt his opportunities would be greatly reduced and his safety compromised (Kevin, Interview five).

Like many children and young people raised in families where parental drug misuse is an issue that may impact on parenting capacity, Hamish spoke about having developed life skills before he was taken into care (Scottish Executive, 2003; Hamish, Interview nine). However, he stated that the skills he had already developed such as washing, cooking, cleaning, and paying the family rent were lost when he no longer needed to use them after he moved into residential care. He said

...near the end of my time they gave us a budget, a budget to pay for your food, but... being a rebellious wee teenager you go out and drink (*knowing*) that they will feed you anyway. So you don't learn your lesson and then when you leave you are that used to having (*staff*) to fall back on that you end up in the rough. (Hamish, Interview nine)

Like Bruce, Hamish learned door management and staff within his supported accommodation facilitated his attendance at college by waking him when he did not get up with his alarm. He said

I had my own house keys because their (*the Local Authority*) independent living flat was outside the (*children's*) home...we could ask the staff for help if we thought that we weren't going to get up for college and things like that...but most of it was left to us...they tried but there was no real like adulthood there because like if you are an adult when you leave care if you run out of money you can ask social work

and they might give you it but most of the time they will say no (Hamish, Interview nine).

Many residential establishments have associated flats close by designed to help support the development of independent living skills for young people transitioning out of the service. This approach can be viewed as having benefits and drawbacks. It means that the link is not completely severed and provides young people with a form of ongoing support, but it can also lead young people to not differentiate and to continue to rely on the service they had received previously. Its link to the residential house may be a barrier for those it is designed to help as there is a continued safety net, this would be expected if a young person left home. But another barrier may result from the experience shared by John. Although John said that he left care when he moved on from residential care and moved into supported accommodation, he felt that he “could afford to not be working...if (*he*) didn’t want to be working, (*he*) didn’t need to be. In (*supported accommodation he said*) you don’t need to pay rent so (*he*) would have got away with it in a sense” and continued to live there but he recognised that this would not help to prepare him for adult life (John, Interview eight).

Stein and Dumaret (2011) highlighted in 2009 21% of young people left care at the age of 16 which would suggest little or no preparation took place for some of our most vulnerable care leavers, this is also reflected within this study. While most of the young people spoke about having been prepared in small ways, these were confined to practical life skills that may have been taught or developed either as part of the ‘independent living plan’ identified by Tina or as part of the lived experience within supported accommodation. Only Tina said that she felt prepared from her time in residential care but she continues to have the ongoing statutory support of her throughcare worker. As highlighted above with John, many young people use the support system in place to avoid having to accelerate their move to adult life. There was a theme within this study that young people were familiar with the experiences of those who had left care before them and of those who left with them who have not fared as well. This seemed to encourage requesting support when it was needed to prevent the inevitable ‘on your own’ that many young people feel as they do not have either an informal or formal support network that has longevity. This is reflective of young people trying to put the brakes on ending a placement. For other children and young people however it is not until it is too late that this is realised resulting in others experiencing accelerated transitions as was the case for Amy (Interview twelve).

In Scotland, the Children (Scotland) Act 1995 placed a duty on local authorities to prepare young people for leaving care. In 1995 this related to young people of school leaving age but updated legislation in 2014 means that this applies to those who are still looked after at the time of their 16th birthday, so the threshold has been reduced at the lower age level (Norrie, 1995). The pathways plan and assessment is designed to ensure that local authorities identify what is needed to help prepare, guide and support a young person for their transition out of care (Scottish Government, 2015). This again highlights that the structured planning process may be introduced at an age when young people may already have left or be leaving the system, as would have been the case for Amy and Lisa. Despite the participant group being of an older leaving care demographic only two young people mentioned any form of plan and as outlined above Tina's was well supported. Bob however said that

...there was no plan, I didn't see like the benefits of taking a plan on as I wasn't ready to move on to my own accommodation at that time. That's how obviously I went into supported accommodation but there was nothing within the unit to make me be more independent, there was nothing (Bob, Interview thirteen).

Bob rejected the option of a pathways plan, but this could suggest that no one took the time to fully explain the benefits of throughcare preparation. It appears that he equated the need for a plan with moving on to his own tenancy, so he did not engage in the process. When prompted, Kevin said that he had heard of pathways planning and thought it was something to do with 'next steps' (Kevin, Interview five). This would suggest that agencies have some work to do in ensuring that the benefits of this process are understood and communicated effectively with social work staff who hold responsibility for this work. Local authorities are not formally preparing young people in line with legal duties and expectations, although many young people have said that they were prepared informally for practical tasks also referred to as 'independent living skills' such as cooking and cleaning, albeit preparation was linked to their experiences within supported accommodation (Interviews six – ten). Stein (2006) highlights that there is a positive link between successful outcomes for young people and the preparation they received before they moved on from care.

Luna and Liam shared a view that they had a personal deficit that impaired their ability to be prepared for moving on (Luna and Liam, Interviews one and ten). Luna said, "I'm just not very motivated, I think just because I didn't really get that motivation as much as I should have" (Luna, Interview one). This view was shared by Liam who said he "would rather bury his head in the sand than maybe face the reality of it was time to grow up, it was time to be an adult"

(Liam, Interview ten). Unrealistic expectations are placed on care leavers who are left feeling that they should be ready to live an independent life when they leave care. Killoh (2018) states that we need person centred planning and to move away from a 'one size fits all' approach to leaving care. Liam left his supported carers placement at aged 21 years old, and he spoke about how residential care did not prepare him for moving on, but his carers did teach him life skills and basics around looking after a home. Although there was a lot he felt that he had learned he spoke about "not realising what was involved in having (*his*) own house until (*he*) actually moved" (Liam, Interview ten). I will return to this shortly in the next section when we look at emerging adulthood and expectations of this life stage within the care experienced and wider community but for now, I will discuss young people's experience of the actual leaving care transition.

8.4 The Transition Process

The Promise briefing on residential care states that "any transition in a care experienced child's life must be limited, relational, planned and informed" (Care Review, 2020, p. 67). Research would indicate that limiting moves for children, focussing on relationships rather than processes, planning for change and ensuring that young people are integral to and are informed about decision making leads to better outcomes for children and young people. However, this study shows that good outcomes can occur with the absence of most of these factors, with the exception of relationships. All the participants in this study experienced multiple transitions during their time in care; whether these resulted from changes in employees, the movement of residents, shift changes, moves in school provision or placement changes as outlined in previous chapters. The Scottish Government (2013) highlight that those who remain in their care placements longer often have wider support networks and stronger carer relationships than those who do not, this finding was consistent with the experiences of Luna, Carol, Liam, and Tina who all spoke about strong carer relationships. They also stated that those who left care early were more likely to have experienced multiple placements (Scottish Government, 2013). Four young people left care before their 18th birthdays and all but one of these had multiple placements with Tania experiencing 18 moves (Tania, Interview four), suggesting a link between an early exit from care and transitions within care. This is supported by other research findings (Stein, 2006). Whilst the three young women moved into their own tenancies, the only young man moved to a shared student flat as he was attending college (Mark, Interview seven). While Mark spent the briefest period of time in care of all the participants and he enjoyed a secure stable placement, a move on to further group

living may provide an additional safety net for him as he progresses to adulthood (Mark, Interview seven).

Tania's 18 placements equate to one move per year throughout her time in care where she experienced a range of kinship and statutory care placements (Tania, Interview four). It is difficult to see how this young person could have developed any sense of security given the substantial changes she experienced and her lack of understanding of her life experiences to date (Tania, Interview four). Tania was the only young person in the group of early care leavers who was in care for more than five years. While the other three young people experienced between one and six transitions this amounted to between 1 – 5 per year for the females while the male had a stable placement throughout his time in care. Although placement changes are not linear there appears to be a link to a lack of understanding about why a child has been taken into care and the number of care situations they have experienced. Liam appears to have been the only exception within this study. There also appears to be a relationship between leaving care early and entering care at a later age. Given the small sample size of this study further research would help to develop a fuller understanding in this area. Data gathering across the Scottish local authorities could also assist in this process. At the moment this information is not collected consistently and the details of placement moves, particularly within settings, is not always evident in chronologies or statistical data. A lack of data collection in care settings and beyond is a global issue (Parsons et al., 2020; Mendes et al., 2020).

For the eight other participants who left care between the ages of 18 and 21 years old (participant six is excluded here as he could not recall when he went into care), there was considerable variance in transitions ranging from 1 – 51 placements (see Chapter five for further statistical information). As stated elsewhere, there is inconsistent data gathered about placement moves and chronologies would provide insight here, but national data needs to be gathered. Again, when considering the length of time participants spent within care placements this gives a more realistic view of their experiences and speaks to the fear expressed by Kevin in chapter six about the transient nature of the residential care experience. Of these eight participants, two experienced two moves in 12 years, two experienced a transition every three to four years, one experienced a move just under one per year over 16 years, another experienced a move just over one a year for five years, one experienced 1.5 moves per year over ten years and one experienced five moves per year over ten years. I make no assumptions here that these young people were moved systematically 'x' number of

times per year but presenting these figures in this way illustrates the stark nature of the care experiences, illustrating that they are not a homogeneous group with standard experiences. Even with the moves in clusters young people must be ever conscious that their living abode could be short-lived making it difficult to experience consistency, security and stability which are needs recognised in chapter two as fundamental to positive human development (Erikson, 1995; Maslow, 1970). The participants data appears to support the view that those who leave care early are more likely to have experienced multiple placements with three out of the four experiencing more transitions, per se than all in the older age bracket except for Hamish.

Lisa spoke about going “from having everyone around me to no one” (Lisa, Interview two) reflecting the isolation of having her own tenancy and no formal support. She stated it was the small things that she missed such as staff checking on her when she was sleeping. I will return to young people’s experience of loneliness and isolation shortly. This practice appears to have given Lisa a sense of additional security within her placement where staff showed that they were concerned for her by checking to make sure that she slept soundly. This loving gesture is what a parent would do for a child who was poorly or struggled to sleep.

Two of the participants, Liam and Kevin, went to live with supported carers after their time within residential houses, however their experiences were starkly different. Kevin did not appear to get the emotional support that research highlights is needed (Scottish Government, 2013), from his substitute parents who appear to have taken their role as something similar to that of the service to be expected in a B&B. He said

I transitioned into a supported carer before my new flat so my transition was totally different but I think that when I went to my supported carer they done nothing for me either. It was literally just a house I lived in and no one even minded that there was no lock on the door. So that makes me feel at home, again it’s just a placement where they are paid to look after you and they are paid to buy you food and they bought me an Iceland frozen pizza and shit like that. Not to be a pure food snob but you are getting paid like £1200 per month and you are giving me frozen pizza every night (Kevin, Interview five).

Kevin spoke about his carers owning properties and a luxury car, so his perception of their role was one of employment to make additional money. This is not far removed from the discussion in the previous chapter where young people differentiate between those who they feel are engaged in their work ‘for the money’ and those who genuinely care for the young people and work in the sector as a vocation.

In contrast Liam felt that his supported carers prepared him for moving on with life skills and preparing him for what it would be like to manage a house. However, he said

...right up until actually moving out I didn't realise how much of a big deal and how much was actually involved in having my own house... But they were there obviously and they came and helped me through that and all that as well. So, they were always in contact with me in some form (Liam, Interview ten).

Sustained contact post-care would be a usual practice for the service Liam had experienced but this is not always customary practice, and it requires an emotional investment from carers as there is no financial remuneration, I will return to this when discussing professional relationships. Liam also spoke more generally about leaving care, commenting on how you learn mathematics at school but not how to look after yourself in adulthood. He said

...leaving care is a massive issue in Scotland just now between 16 and 22, aye the crucial point for kids. I mean I got help...but I didn't know how to do washings and things like that I always had things done for me in care and I was never really prepared to move on. Like here is how to budget. I was terrible with money, I'm only just really getting a bit better at handling money and even now (*at the age of 27 years old*), I give my money to my missus (Liam, Interview ten).

While other respondents spoke about the lack of preparation for budgeting and paying bills resulting in getting into debt or financial difficulties, Hamish was the only participant who spoke about his experience of homelessness after leaving care when he was unable to pay his rent. Financial difficulties are not unique to young people or care leavers as increasingly literature highlights economics reflective of crisis, flux and austerity (Mizen, 2004; Jones, 2012; Graham, 2019). The Child Poverty Action Group have highlight that we moved from an aim of improving circumstances to one in which food banks and destitution are evident in families where at least one parent works (Graham, 2019). Extensive means testing and delays on benefits, as was the case with Hamish, can leave people feeling undeserving and ashamed (Graham, 2019), and reduce complex social problems to failing of individuals (Jones, 2012).

While walking me out after the interview Hamish said that I had probably heard a lot of bad stories from the young people that I had interviewed and I said that I had been really surprised that I had had no accounts of homelessness or any form of abuse and this surprised me, given abuse inquiries. He said that he experienced guilt when telling his care experienced friends

that he enjoyed care because they spoke about negative experiences but recently, he said “me and a few others who have had good times have been able to be like, no we’ve had a good time” (Hamish, Interview nine). He surmised that good stories were quashed as a lot of bad ones are told, putting those who have had good experiences in a challenging position. He also spoke about campaigning he had been involved in that resulted in legislative changes and how those with the most harrowing accounts spearheaded the campaign (Interview nine). This can serve several functions as extreme experiences can highlight practices that need to change when a system is being reviewed but it can also produce a hierarchy of traumatic experiences that I do not feel is very validating to those young people who have experienced adversity and are trying to come to terms with what has happened to them.

8.5 Educational and Employment Achievements Post Care

Despite an increased understanding of the adversity experienced by care experienced young people, the most recent Scottish Government (2020) figures show that there has been steady progress over the past six years with improvements in looked after children’s educational attainments. Figures reflect that 35% of care leavers move on from school having achieved 1 qualification or more at SCQF level 5 compared to 85% of the general population which is staggeringly troubling despite the number having risen 13% since 2012. When looking specifically at those young people who have resided in residential care the percentage is as low as 27%, although better than the 13% for young people who are on supervision orders and have remained in the care of their parents (Scottish Government, 2020). The government also shows that destinations on leaving school have improved with 81% of young people leaving residential care moving on to employment, further or higher education, training, voluntary work or personal skills development. The national average is 93% improving to 96% 9 months after leaving school while the follow up for residential care youngsters has reduced to 71% when linked to a positive destination (Scottish Government, 2020). These young people are more likely to experience unemployment with almost a quarter experiencing this within 9 months compared to only 5% of the general population (Scottish Government, 2020). Surprisingly, given the economic climate, nobody within this study was unemployed although Hamish did experience this for a period after he left care (Hamish, Interview nine).

While unemployment was not a feature for the group there was diversity in their experiences of education and what they achieved both academically and personally. Amy and Tania discussed their attendance at specialist education provision with smaller class sizes and a

range of academic and vocational qualifications on offer which resulted in them benefitting academically and practically in a way they did not feel they would have if they had continued within mainstream education (Amy and Tania, Interviews four and twelve). Amy spoke about becoming a 'top student' and of being a positive role model for younger peers.

Lisa was a high achiever before going into residential care and she felt her academic education was curtailed during her time in placement. However, she gained vocational experience while there that she viewed as essential for her future career and she was able to return to 7th year, going to the school she previously attended in her home community, due to the ongoing support of a member of teaching staff (Lisa, Interview two). This allowed her to revisit the year that she missed, an opportunity that no one else in the study received and this is a good example of corporate parents taking their responsibility seriously (Scottish Government, 2008).

For most of the group academic qualifications gave them a sense of pride but Kevin said that he achieved educationally on his own merit, not due to the support of those around him. As indicated in the previous chapter he was presented with an award for his academic achievements from his local authority, but he said of this success, "that's me like just being a good statistic for the care system and things like that, I don't think I actually achieved anything in terms of myself personally" (Kevin, Interview five). This relates to the discussion earlier about young people's motivation to succeed. There appears to be a parallel here with being the figurehead associated with the campaign work that Hamish described. It appears that young people with harrowing experiences are encouraged to share their experiences which highlight deficits or practices that need to change but the positive attention that this receives may make others reluctant to share positive experiences.

Hamish said that he had attempted college four times and his application for university through an access route was what he saw as his 'last attempt' to have a university education. He said that he "couldn't deal with authoritative people, especially because of the years (*he*) tried social care and...couldn't deal with an ex social worker talking down to the class" (Interview nine). He spoke about not being in education, employment, and training (NEET) when he left care and said

I left care, no job, I was in college at the time and when I left they got me my own flat and I was on the 'broo'. It was bad...for a while when I tried college again and college fell on its butt so I had to go back on the 'broo' (*welfare benefits*) and

between the gaps you know when they do the registry process you ran up debt on council tax during that process (Hamish, Interview nine).

As Hamish mentioned earlier, care experienced young people can request financial support from the social work department but there is no guarantee that they will receive this. He linked his experience of homelessness with the debt he accrued as a student (Hamish, Interview nine). Tina spoke about being half-way through a university degree, she was taking some time out to work and build up her financial resources as she was worried that she would accrue significant student debt (Tina, Interview eleven). As discussed in chapter four there are financial benefits available to care experienced young people who move on to further or higher education in addition to the council tax exemption mentioned by Tina within her interview (Tina, Interview eleven). Liam left care with few qualifications, but he was able to achieve an SVQ 3 and HNC and to move on to a university course, all paid for by his employer (Interview ten). This is not unusual in his field of work where there are requirements for qualifications through the Scottish Social Services Council. Work facilitated learning opportunities were also discussed by Tania, John, Amy and Lisa and appeared to be viewed as a secure way of engaging in ongoing learning without the stress of worrying about the financial burden. Lisa had put off going to university due to trying to earn an income and overcome financial barriers. Lisa said, “the way my job role works, I’m funded through the government so I wouldn’t be able to get SAACS so I would have to pay for it all myself” so instead she was completing a vocational qualification funded through her work (Lisa, Interview two).

The financial implications were not viewed as a barrier to Kevin who was aware of the financial supports on offer to care experienced young people. A barrier for him resulted from the application process and although he had not always planned to go to university his significant achievements at school left him feeling that this was something that he needed to do (Kevin, Interview five). He got the results necessary for one university, but he decided against going there after having applied on his UCAS application for five different courses at the same university, he did not feel the university was prestigious enough. He said that he had left his application form too late and as he had no experience of the application process and had no guidance, he did not realise that he should have applied to a variety of universities. This is likely to be a barrier for families supporting young people where no one within the family has gone to university before. He did not receive the appropriate guidance which highlights a gap in current provision. He sought advice and a teacher told him about a transition course and on completion it guaranteed you a place at his chosen university. He subsequently achieved a business degree (Interview five). The stability of college and university placements, with

participants changing courses, was a feature for Lisa and three other participants (Interviews three, ten, eleven) and is consistent with experiences of non-care experienced peers (Arnett, 2007; 2010). A longitudinal global study of 310 care leavers shows that 89 of the respondents to a questionnaire were educated to degree level or above (Duncalf, 2010). There was recognition that due to recruitment being online most of the study group were residential care experienced individuals. The research found that many had gone on to fulfil their educational potential at a later point in their life with more than a fifth achieving their degree after the age of 41 years old while 16 achieved their degree when under 40. Similarly, Sacker, Murray, Lacey and Maughan (2021) found that care leavers are more likely to revisit education and achieve additional qualifications in later life.

Bruce, like Liam, left school with few formal qualifications although he said he would go to higher education if the opportunity arose, as he is currently in full-time employment, he did not think this was likely in the foreseeable future, Bruce was the youngest interviewee and having previously attended a fee paying school, he believed that going into care affected his educational achievements (Bruce, Interview six). He was the only participant in the study who had experienced private school which is not surprising given the links made in previous chapters between poverty and experiences of care (Care Review, 2020; Ross, 2019).

There was an explicit awareness with John, Kevin, and Tina that care experienced youngsters achieved poorer educational outcomes, young people spoke about feeling pressure to buck the trend and of the overwhelming sense of failure when they did not achieve what they had hoped. Luna also spoke about not doing “enough in school, school was kind of really hard for me. But then I went to college and got my national qualification” (Luna, Interview one), expressing the pressure to do well. It is unlikely that this pressure is solely about lower attainments, and it is likely to be linked to youth policy and the economic disadvantages associated with this age group around poorer incomes, job instability and austerity (Mizen, 2004; Jones, 2012; Scottish Government, 2020c). Being able to stick in at things when you have experienced years being in care is something that Bob reflected when he said that he had attended college, had numerous jobs, and then went on to study again. He said: “I done a sports coaching course two years ago, but I fell away from it as it was too much for me at that time” (Bob, Interview thirteen).

John went from college to a work-based apprenticeship and this experience was shared by Tania, Lisa and Kevin who were employed as part of a project that was subject to funding by

the government. John said his success came from sustaining his employment as he had only been employed in summer jobs before and he said that he was not very keen on them, although he did not state why. He enjoyed his position and he had been there for a year. He subsequently stated that as the job was an apprenticeship it meant that he was being reinterviewed to remain in his position and this was causing him some anxiety (John, Interview eight). The unemployment rate for 16 – 24-year-olds being around 42% will add to this anxiety (Scottish Government, 2021c). Kevin shared a similar experience and he raised concerns about how he was going to pay his rent if he was not kept on (Kevin, Interview five).

One of the positive destinations identified by the Scottish Government is engaging in voluntary work. Many of the participants were giving back to others through their roles as volunteers or practitioners in social care services. This applied to all but two of the participants which is significantly higher than national statistics which show that 1% of both the care leaving and school leaving population are involved in voluntary work, but this reduces to 1% of care leavers within a year of leaving care. This is not in keeping with the association emerging adulthood has with 'self-focus' as these young people are keen to give something back to others, but I will return to emerging adulthood shortly. John said that he spent

...two and a half years volunteering (*in the third sector*)... working with young people with severe mental health disabilities. So that was a rewarding experience to say the least and then I gave that up not long before moving to my full-time post and I still volunteer here (*the advocacy service*) as well (John, Interview eight).

It is likely that this type of experience would be viewed favourably when seeking employment or education within particular fields. Bob spoke about his job satisfaction from helping others, he said

...everyday I feel successful. Like the job I've got just now it's just a whirlwind of young people. The young people I face daily and when they say something I'm like that's still happening and I will say to them that's what was happening when I was in the system...It's like making myself eager to change that (Bob, Interview thirteen).

8.6 Personal Achievements After Care

Making a difference to other young people's care experiences was something that four of the participants spoke about through work they were involved in after leaving care. Bob said he

played a role in the development of the 2014 childcare legislation that increased the leaving care age and introduced the extended provision of 'continuing care'. Kevin, John, and Hamish also spoke about being involved in the development of the legislation and despite the transformational nature of this change Bob said that he did not feel that he achieved anything other than a few standard grades related to care. He said, "so I was in care but we are just the same as everybody else" but this statement was tempered with him acknowledging that he was "coming out the other end of what was a hard part of (*his*) life but now" and his care experience had given him a focus as he was now able to support and help others who have had similar experiences to himself (Tina, Interview eleven). Hamish spoke about winning a volunteer award and helping to change the law as achievements. He spoke about not being the poster boy for the campaign as other individuals were seen as having more 'powerful' stories to tell (Hamish, Interview nine). This was mentioned earlier and while young people can acknowledge that there are many others worse off than they have been it reflects a pecking order among narratives. This could be soul destroying for children who have experienced adversity, to know that others believe that their stories are less deserving of being told.

As well as making things better for other young people, participants spoke about wanting to make life choices and opportunities ensuring that they made a better life for their own children. Having a child was something that two of the participants in the group experienced. Amy said "it wasn't until I was like 18 I finally got a job and started getting on with things when I had (*my baby*) until I was pregnant that was just a riot" (Amy, Interview twelve). Amy and Liam were both parents at the time of their interviews. Liam said "I feel like I've set up a nice foundation for the future and for my life and for my son's life. I feel like I could have a very nice life going forward...I've kind of turned my life around" (Tina, Interview eleven).

Only Tina spoke about her mother being in residential childcare as a youngster. She spoke about wanting to break the cycle and said "I didn't want to be like a circle, I wanted to be like a triangle or a parallelogram...I wanted it to stop (Tina, Interview eleven). Both her parents experienced alcohol dependency issues and Tina does not drink alcohol, and she is proud of having broken the care cycle and of not being like her parents. She said "I got to university even though...all the statistics say that I'm more likely to see the inside of a prison cell than a university classroom" (Tina, Interview eleven). This view was echoed by a number of young

people who spoke of the pressure of not becoming another statistic, resulting in them putting unnecessary stress on themselves but it was also a motivator as previously identified by Luna.

For Carol care made her a better person and success came from “all the things (*she*) managed to do without living with (*her*) parents” (Carol, Interview three). Luna echoed this view saying “I feel successful because I’ve just not ... crumbled...I’m not saying I’m the strongest person in the world but like being in care I could have just gave up a long time ago” (Luna, Interview one). She felt that having people encouraging her to succeed helped her battle with doubts.

Liam said he

...kind of figured (*things*) out, I found myself a wee bit, like who (*I was*) personality wise. I learned to get more comfortable in my own skin just being a wee bit different. And I think that probably through my entire time in care, no matter what you go through you can come out of the other side...There’s always someone who maybe got a better start than you but you can make the best version of yourself (Liam, Interview ten).

There are parallels between those with care experience and those of other groups who are disadvantaged. While all the young people in my study described themselves as white, Scottish, or British, Stein (2006) states that black and ethnic minority young people have the added complexity of identity problems. Avery states that “for youth of colour, a sense of membership in an ethnic, racial, or cultural group is an underlying issue that pervades and influences progress towards adulthood. In addition, these youth are frequently faced with discriminatory attitudes and evidence of their lower status and power in society which forces them to have to continually negotiate their sense of self in relation to other groups” (Avery, 2007: 403). All the young people within the study spoke about embracing their care experience and this shared identity in part appears to come from not having a real sense of who they are in connection to their family, their wider community and society as a whole.

Luna said that she entered the unit at the age of 14 years old and “it was a big gap of my life and it’s just really hard. Obviously, the fact that I was the youngest when I went in and the oldest when I went out, so I sort of did grow up there” (Luna, Interview one). This appears to support views shared elsewhere relating to differences between the culture of the residential home or care setting and the real world. Fulcher and Ainsworth (2005) illustrate that residential settings have their own social structure, language, norms, and values as discussed in chapters

two and six. There is a suggestion within the narrative that this period of time has been lost or stood still and you cannot get it back, this will be linked to the severed relationships that can result from separation. It may also be the case when young people feel a disconnect between what happens within residential care and what happens in the wider society. One of the participants spoke about having lost four years of her life (Luna, Interview one).

In addition to finding the experience hard and maturing within residential care Luna said that she developed a tougher exterior, a 'shield' where she protected herself from harm. She said

...when you are moved out of your family home and stuff you sort of like have all these questions and for me I sort of started doubting myself, which is why I didn't want to make friends with people in the unit. I know that they....or I was going to get moved so I had to mature in that way...and not depend on people (Luna, Interview one).

8.7 Emotional Wellbeing

Luna was the only participant who spoke about not relying on others. Relationships and emotional wellbeing were crucially important to all of the participants within this study. Lisa spoke about engaging with programmes whilst in care and intense psychological input. Her motivation for engagement was to move on quicker as she said they initially predicted she would spend 9 – 12 months within the service. She spoke of the psychological work in terms of

I probably wouldn't have stuck to that if it wasn't for foster carers and workers saying this is going to help. I know it's not helping right now and it's really traumatic and really hurting you right now, but it is going to help in the future, and I think having people constantly remind me of that I guess was a good thing. Probably made me stronger today (Lisa, Interview two).

Seven years intense work was concluded the year before the interview, and this appeared to make her emotionally strong, and she had a very good understanding of her life and her experiences. Emotional health and wellbeing were issues raised by several respondents while Mark spoke optimistically and said that you need to just keep "looking forward and don't let the bad things get you down" (Mark, Interview seven). This sense of acceptance, of being grateful as things could have been a lot worse, and optimism was more prevalent with the

male participants (Bruce, Mark, John, Hamish and Liam, Interviews six, seven, eight, nine and ten). This may relate to poorer outcomes for males than females on leaving care.

For many young people some measure of success came from the recognition that not everyone in care managed to stay alive (Lisa, Carol and Hamish, Interviews two, three and nine). Amy said: "I'm one of the lucky ones because a lot of people I was in care with aren't here anymore so yeah I definitely feel that I'm successful" (Amy, Interview twelve). She said "I would have been dead cos I was taking a lot of drugs and I was in like situations that were dangerous" (Amy, Interview twelve). She believes that having a baby meant that she had 'someone to fight for'. Lisa recently revisited her residential placement and spent time with her old manager, she enjoyed the visit and the opportunity to show that she had survived and was doing well. She said "it was nice to go and see them and say, look, I am here, and I did make it, and actually look at what I'm doing well. (*I wasn't*) going to be what people are labelling me and I'm not going to end up in prison" (Lisa, Interview two). Lisa was determined that she was going to achieve something in her life and during the visit she was advised that out of the six young people who lived in the home only her and one other person were still alive (Lisa, Interview two). As there is not a national database recording information about care leavers much of what is known results from word of mouth, through visits or telephone contact. Social media also plays a role here as well as young people coming to the attention of the authorities through adult services. This reinforces the need for a national database.

Tina stated that she would have had a poor outcome if she had not gone into care. She said, "I would have been an alcoholic like my mum and dad. I would never have gotten to university" (Tina, Interview eleven). For some young people success was measured through different life choices and lifestyles to family members whilst others used measures of things you are not able to achieve as a child, for instance Mark, Liam and Lisa spoke about successfully passing their driving tests. For Bruce his house, phone and job helped him to feel successful, this was a view of adulthood related to the ability to manage responsibilities. He seemed content and said: "I've achieved the things that I've wanted for a while, that's enough" (Bruce, Interview six). Other practical achievements were mentioned by Hamish and Carol. Hamish said: "I've got a house that I've been in nine years, it's one of those things that you don't think about and then you speak to other care kids and you realise that's a long time" (Hamish, Interview nine). Similarly, Carol had sustained her own tenancy for six years (Carol, Interview three).

8.8 Feeling Safe and Secure

Hamish said “it was nice to have my own house, but I didn’t sleep for the first few days, there was no one there. After five years of knowing someone was there if I got up during the night as much as I might have got into trouble there was somebody in that house and then there was nobody in this flat” (Hamish, Interview nine). Night-time was mentioned by both Lisa and Amy in a similar vein. Amy said: “my friend lived under me and I had to stay with him every night because I couldn’t stay on my own...I just was too scared to be in the house on my own, it was horrible” (Amy, Interview twelve). Avery’s (2009) examination of the experiences of young people aging out of foster care in the US highlighted a likelihood that young people would attach to deviant peer associates because of an inadequate social network and loneliness. Amy also said that she did not like being on her own as she experienced anxiety.

Sims-Schouten and Hayden (2017) highlight the association between the mental health issues resulting from the reception into care and those linked to experiences reflecting the complexity of leaving care. Evidence supports the increased emotional needs of care leavers and the need for supportive relationships and stability (Adley and Jupp Kina, 2017). Kevin spoke about his anxiety and said

I really was adamant that I (*didn’t*) want to go in (*to*) a council flat because I would have been put in some high riser (high rise flat) I would not feel safe, and I just couldn’t imagine myself living in that environment again. After being so scared growing up in it and working so hard and pulling away from it. My boss had to be my guarantor as I don’t have parents to do it for me and reflecting back that is heartbreaking” (Kevin, Interview five).

This is something that should be recognised by corporate parents as a need within the care experienced community as it would be unusual for an employer, particularly when this young person is in insecure work, to support living arrangements. This appears to have been facilitated because of his employers understanding of care leavers needs but it should be more embedded in the system as young people leaving care have a higher likelihood of experiencing homelessness.

Feelings of loneliness and isolation were shared by several participants. Kevin said

I got my exam results there, I got a 2:2 which I was devastated about, which is a reflection of the year that I’ve had and very little support. Like I was split from my supported carers and I was flung into a flat and I felt so alone and isolated as I

never had anyone. But at the same time I was still trying to go through uni because I knew if I never I wouldn't get any financial support (Kevin, Interview five).

Tina tried to overcome her feelings of isolation when she got her own home by having pets. She said she had the practical skills for moving on but when she said "when I moved into my own flat, what I wasn't really prepared for was how it would affect my mental health living on my own" (Tina, Interview eleven). The impact on young people's mental health is hardly surprising given that many young people enter the care system with poor mental health (Goodman and Goodman, 2009; Sempick, 2010). Pecora et al (2005) conducted a study of individuals aged 19 – 30 years old who had left foster placements and found that they demonstrated post-traumatic stress disorder twice that of US war veterans at 25%. As discussed in chapter six, most of the participants of this study also experienced foster care and it is reflected throughout this work that residential childcare outcomes are poorer in all the statistical measures currently used (Children's Social Work Statistics, 2020).

Miller, Wakefield and Sani (2015) in their Scottish study of school children and young people aged 13-17 years old linked good mental health to multiple group identities with the most significant of these family, school and peer group affiliation and they found that 75% of mental health disorders are evident in young people by the time they have reached their 25th birthday. Very few of the young people within this study spoke about positive affiliations with family, the greatest source of support according to research, and only Lisa was provided with ongoing support from her original school, this helped her to return there to complete her studies (Miller, Wakefield and Sani, 2015 and Interview two). Positive school identification was the strongest indicator of good mental health, and it was recognised that not being able to positively identify "with one's family in adolescence is likely to have important implications for mental health" (Miller, Wakefield and Sani, 2015, p. 344). Multiple group membership was viewed as having significant implications when dealing with times of stress as this psychological connectedness is likely to offer a range of support networks that may mitigate and buffer during adversity (Miller, Wakefield and Sani, 2015). When young people leave care, they continue to need multiple group membership as their need for an increased support network will increase.

8.9 After Care Support

Avery (2009) recognises the significant role of the in post-care support and states that "the family of origin functions as a base of operations for the explorations that occur prior to adulthood, both literally (through co-residence in a parental household, parental financial

subsidies, and other material support) and figuratively (through the availability of parents and kin as sources of wisdom and guidance)” (Avery, 2009, p. 401). She stated that “a significant proportion of youth in care (particularly those living in out-of-home care situations such as residential treatment facilities and group homes) have few or no relationships or connections with parents, extended family members, or significant other adults who can provide the needed social support to make a successful transition to adulthood” (Avery, 2009, p. 401). This was the case for Amy who said that she struggled post-care and was disowned by her family for a while due to her risk taking behaviour (Amy, Interview twelve). She said, “I wasn’t doing great because I was spending my money on other things so my mum would have to pay for my shopping and everything” (Amy, Interview twelve). She said “when I was in care I managed to fool the system into thinking that I was doing everything that they wanted but when I got out things got really bad again. I was back in the same situations I was in, if not worse, so it wasn’t until I fell pregnant that things kind of turned” and changed for the better (Amy, Interview twelve). Amy saw this as an opportunity to turn her life around as she had someone else’s needs to consider.

Rather than family relationships and support Tania spoke about the importance of fictive relationships and said that she had formed relationships with three staff within residential care and she felt that was all she achieved while in care, for her this was considerable as she was very suspicious of adults and had experienced multiple relationships with adults (Tania, Interview four). The Independent Care Review (2020) stressed the fundamental importance of relationships in almost every aspect of a care experienced young person’s life and the positive long-term impact they can have in the ability to form other meaningful relationships and an optimism about the future (Independent Care Review, 2020). All but one of the young women in the study spoke about developing positive fictive relationships with staff within their group living placement and two-thirds of these relationships continued post-care. This was particularly noted within local authority children’s home placements and may be part of the whole systems approach to care and support. Despite Lisa saying she had not developed significant relationships within her care setting, she was one of the few young people who spoke about going back to visit her previous placement to check in and say hello, and she spoke about how powerful an experience that was for her as reflected in the previous chapter (Lisa, Interview two). For nine of the thirteen respondents relationships with residential care staff continued after the young people had left care. This contrasted significantly with relationships with throughcare staff with only one young person talking about keeping in touch with theirs and two others saying that they believed that they were no longer ‘under the social

work department' a term used to describe ongoing state support, advice, and guidance, as they had not seen their throughcare worker for a considerable period of time (Kevin and John, Interviews five and eight). It is more difficult for these relationships to have the same depth of meaning to other social work relationships as they are likely to be much shorter in duration, although as the previous chapter indicated for many young people professional relationships can be quite transient due to staffing and placement moves. Nobody within the study spoke about an ongoing relationship post care with their social worker which was somewhat surprising but can be seen in the context of high turnover of staff. Akinsanya (2015) and Daniels and Livingstone (2014) write about maintaining significant relationships with their social workers long after they left care.

Tina maintains irregular contact with her former residential home. She said something

...happened with my dad this morning like a phone call and stuff like that I wanted to phone like the unit but I wasn't sure if (*Mary*) would be on shift or if I could phone her mobile as I have her mobile number, but I wasn't sure if she was busy with something. Cos at the end of last year, and I left in February last year, so like in November, I'd phone up and say like can I come to the unit today and they'd be like no sorry you can't and it took me a minute to realise that I'm not their young person any more, they care for other young people now and I found that really hard to deal with (Tina, Interview eleven).

As mentioned in earlier chapters Tina sustained a twelve years relationship with a staff member and she spoke about how important this was to her. She said that

...I always say that I've been a mum since '97, I'm a mum to my mum and now my dad who I met when I was 17... (*Mary*) would jump in and take that weight off my shoulders and just let me be a young person and no one had ever done that for me before... (*she*) would get quite annoyed (*with my mum*) on my behalf as she treats me like I'm her own daughter (Tina, Interview eleven).

This emotional unpaid labour goes largely unnoticed within social care and social work although 'Keeping the Promise' has brought this onto the agenda highlighting its importance and the relevance of promoting sustained relationships after young people leave care (Care Review, 2021). Systems need to be developed to facilitate this contact as in addition to Tina recognising that Mary has other young people in the care of her worker now, she is providing

invaluable emotional support to her, a young person with limited supportive resources. Tina reflected on how lucky she was and said

I've got my own house, I don't only look after myself I've always got pets so I feel that's responsibility... I kind of got them to combat the loneliness sort of thing...my throughcare worker was in earlier because I was really panicking not having money to tide me over before I get paid for this job but he managed to sort that out...I have more than one key person who really fights for me and helps me with my life, most people don't even have one (Tina, Interview eleven).

Supportive relationships are crucial for a young person's successes in care and beyond but young people also spoke about the impact of having a lack of financial resources and unlike Tina's account above, for some young people they do not have that ongoing support. For many young people budgeting was cited as the biggest barrier to preparation with Tania talking about how she "couldn't afford the bills that (*she*) had to pay so (*she*) was always getting into debt (*with*) people coming to (*her*) door" (Tania, Interview four). Similarly, Kevin spoke about how his earning capacity impacted on his life creating anxiety around whether he was financially able to cope (Kevin, Interview five). Two of the older participants shared their own experiences of being unable to manage financially although Liam was given support through his ongoing professional relationships.

The above account has illustrated that most young people have experienced some challenges moving on from their care placements, for 11 participants this was from group care, while for two it was from supported carers. Stein's resilience framework allows us to view these experiences through his typology of 'moving on', 'survivors' and 'strugglers' although it must be recognised that this is a small sample size and as outlined in the introduction to this chapter it would risk anonymity to specifically categorise the study group (Stein, 2006). Most of the participants fall into the moving on category; they have achieved educational success, they have relatively secure relationships with at least one significant other and although leaving care did not always go to plan there was a level of stability. This is not reflective of the wider research in the residential care field (Stein, 2006; McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham, and Harkin (2014). A couple of the young people would fall into the category of survivor as they experienced more instability post care, even when they may have achieved academically this did not mediate a less than stable existence whether this was due to a lack of stable accommodation or challenges within the labour market. Only one of the candidates would fit with Stein's categorisation of struggler, despite many of the young people in the study having considerable damaged pre-care life experiences, one of the contributing factors in this

category. At the time of his interview this participant had overcome many disadvantages and had moved into the survivor category but as most of the young people are in the young leaving care age bracket there is nothing to suggest that their status will remain stable.

8.10 Preparedness for Adulthood; Emerging Adulthood

Since the 1990's Arnett has argued that there are three markers of the transition to adulthood and as it lasts as long as adolescence it merits a life stage of its own, he refers to this as emerging adulthood (Arnett, 2010). The three markers for his theory were identified as 'financial independence', 'responsibility taking' and 'decision making' and he stated that they have replaced the more traditional markers or rites of passage into adulthood such as having your own home, getting married and becoming a parent (Arnett, 2010).

In addition to what is described as international markers Arnett identifies five main features which he found in his studies in the US emerging adults (Arnett, 2000, 2007a, 2007b). These features are 'identity exploration', 'age of instability', 'self-focus', 'feeling in between' and 'possibilities/optimism' and his findings have been supported in other European studies (Arnett, 2015; Galambos and Martinez, 2007; Zacaes, Serra and Torres, 2015). While many of the studies relate this to the 18 – 25-year-old age group, for many others it is extended to 18 – 29-year-olds which was the main drivers for the selection and parameters of my participant group.

Most of the young people within this study achieved academically with more than half of them progressing to college or university, this is double the amount of care leavers who went on to higher or further education but may be reflective of a different route into education similar to those of more mature students from lower socio-economic groups who are also more likely to remain at home (Scottish Government, 2020; UCAS, 2018). None of the young people went to university straight from school although one young person did undertake a bridging course at college. The high educational attainment of this study group may have an impact on the emerging adulthood findings as most of the research that has been carried out globally has been with college students. This sets my participants as relatively unique as I did not set out to interview high achievers. Other researchers have also highlighted however the dearth of illustration of positive care experiences evidenced in qualitative leaving care research (Duncalf, 2010; Pilkington, 2021).

The participants experiences were consistent to some extent with the five features that Arnett equates with leaving care and emerging adulthood (Arnett, 2007a). While we have touched

on identity earlier and instability throughout, there is evidence that the young people rather than being self-focussed, have been interested in contributing to their wider community through their involvement in voluntary work. For the remainder of this section, I will integrate the five features as well as focussing on the three key tenets of the theory but firstly it may be important to distinguish views on emerging adulthood as a life stage or a process.

Avery (2009) states “that the transition to adulthood is a gradual process for most adolescents, unrelated to a specific nominal age, and that true “adult” functioning in terms of cognitive, behavioral, and social maturity is not achieved for the majority of emerging adults until the third decade of life” (Avery, 2009, p. 400). While her study largely relates to fostered young people as we have previously discussed there are similarities in the outcome findings with residential experienced youngsters. Despite recognition that the leaving care transition should be gradual and not abrupt there was considerable variance in how prepared young people felt when leaving their care placement and in relation to their own sense of being an adult.

Liam spoke about his employer and said: “this is predominantly where I’ve learned to ‘adult’ if you like, this is where I’ve learned to grow up and make mistakes and stuff” (Interview ten). He works for an agency where he had previously received a service and he saw their relationship as mutually beneficial as he had previously been held up as a ‘success story’ in publicity material. This mutuality and reciprocity of the relationship has provided a foundation for Liam to explore the world and to make mistakes, a crucial function of a secure relationship that promotes healthy human development (Ainsworth and Bell, 1970; Bowlby, 1974).

Hamish, at 29 years old, said that his interpretation of what being an adult means has changed over time and that it means something different to him now than what it meant to him when he left care. He said, it meant

...being able to get out and get drunk. Having a job but being able to do what you wanted. When I left care I’d completely forgotten about council tax and how to pay your rent properly and that you had to pay your full rent and you couldn’t pay fractions and I got into a lot of debt. Almost ten years on it means having a job or doing something regularly or having some version of a routine. It doesn’t matter what it is as long as you have something there. Because routine keeps your skull steady. Trying your best to be nice to people and taking care of yourself. That’s it, anything else above and beyond that is fantastic but trying to be nice, trying to keep yourself out of jail, trying to be a decent person (Hamish, Interview nine).

This view illustrates the importance of having a purpose and focus with ambition to realise it as this can impact positively on your mental health: having a routine and a reason to be. Despite their similarities in age Bob's at 27 years old description of adulthood is like what Hamish described as his perspective when he left care. Bob said he moves between the responsibility of adulthood during the week and partying at the weekend. He feels like an adult but also does not feel like an adult and said

well obviously I've got my own house now and I've just moved into it. I was back there staying with my parents there for like six, seven years...I still feel like in my head I'm that daft wee boy...come the weekend that's when the daft wee boy mentality comes out...when I'm with my pals but like during the week my heads down and I'm concentrating on work, got to do what you've got to do to earn money. The adult side of me is coming out" (Bob, Interview thirteen).

Bruce and Mark, two of the youngest participants, both feel like adults having learned independent living skills within their supported accommodation placements. They equate adulthood with increased responsibilities and no longer being in care. Tina shared this view although at 20 years old she does not feel fully adult yet, she has only recently left care. She said

I felt that I was faking it at being an adult for a bit there because I was still in uni and I'm taking a gap year. So, when I was still studying the throughcare department paid money in for me and obviously I've got my council tax exemption because I'm care experienced so I felt as if cos I was only paying like gas and electricity, so I felt as if, I was just floating by and not doing everything properly (*because things were being subsidised*). I kind of think of it as college, some people need that sort of stepping stone sort of thing between school and university so I feel as if that was kind of my college period but because I'm going to start paying my own rent and stuff, I feel as though I'm at university I've taken the next step, I'm actually becoming more of an adult by doing this (Tina, Interview eleven).

Luna another one of the youngest participants, feels that she is not yet an adult (Luna, Interview one). Unlike the other participants she remains within her supported accommodation although she sees herself as having left care. This status reflects that she continues to be supported by social work and would be in 'continuing care'. She said

I think just sort of being able to like be more independent than I am. Sort of be able to you know maybe know how to run a house or not like I wouldn't say not depend on people but like be able to not be very dependent on people. Like I feel like a lot of the time I don't take as much responsibility for stuff as I should and that's why I'm not feeling totally grown-up I guess (Luna, Interview one).

She also said "I think I'm still kind of not immature but just not adult yet. I think I'm still kind of quite teeny" (Luna, Interview one). This view may result from Luna continuing to live in a social work funded resource and having the supports associated with that.

Carol (24) feels like an adult saying "it means being grown-up and taking responsibility, but I've done that. I've taken responsibility, like I'm stuck in the same house that I lived in, so I think I've done pretty good. But I've done that without the help of throughcare cos I still talk to my staff" (Carol, Interview three). Amy, also 24 said I "didn't actually turn out to be an adult until I fell pregnant...I kind of had to grow up and get on with it" (Amy, Interview twelve). At the age of 17 years old she fell pregnant, and she said

...well now it means that it's stressful and there's just always debt and drama. Everything breaking (*like household goods*), no I don't know...it's good because I've got something like I've got a wee girl and stuff now but I would say that back then I was like a kick in the face, nothing like you would expect but...well I kind of always brought myself up but I was in my head always an adult so there (*were*) times (*when*) I was living on my own with my boyfriend at like 14 years old and stuff. Like I was always older than what I thought (Amy, Interview twelve).

While Amy believes she was older than her years, she uses the term boyfriend to describe an adult that she lived with when she was aged 14 years old, this was the catalyst for her being taken into care (Amy, Interview twelve).

Tania (20) said that although she feels like an adult she can be mistaken for a youngster when she revisits residential units as part of her job. She said the staff "find it hard seeing me come in as a colleague and actually talking to them in a professional way instead of (*being*) a young person kicking off all the time" (Tania, Interview four). She said that adulthood means "taking responsibility for all the different things like bills and having your own house. Doing things for yourself" (Tania, Interview four). John (20) also believes being an adult is about facing things you didn't have to worry about as a child. He said "paying rent, paying bills, doing things you don't want to think about as a child. I enjoy working full-time...at the moment it's about being

able to have my own freedom things like that. I've just moved in to my own flat" (John, Interview eight).

Kevin said

...it's difficult being an adult, there is a lot of responsibility comes. You need to pay bills, you need to pay rent and council tax and everything else which is scary but I think the scariest thing is the emotional side of things...I think I'm an adult because I hold all my responsibility to myself, I don't rely on anyone for anything but then that's never really been an option. I've never had support from my leaving care worker. I've seen him twice in the past year despite me having severe anxiety and depression and I've moved house twice and that's really because he sees me as on paper (*as successful*) (Kevin, Interview five).

Kevin helps to illustrate the difference between how success appears and the reality for the young person. He said that he is currently sharing a flat with a lady he found through 'spare room' and it is clear from his presentation that he finds it intolerable that he has to live with a stranger and that no-one from his family has come forward to help look after him. He said despite statistically reflecting success he cannot

...feel successful yet. I feel like anxious that the rug is going to be pulled from under my feet and that my life is going to be flipped upside down because I've never had security...if my contract doesn't get extended how am I paying my rent, If I don't get rid of this anxious feeling where every time I eat something I think I'm going to die", he doesn't know how he will survive (Kevin, Interview five).

He said he felt as though he was 'drowning' with the level of responsibility as he transitioned to adulthood and the level of uncertainty he continues to face. There is an expectation that every decision you now must make for yourself and fundamental needs such as registering for the doctor or dentist is a challenge. He found himself outwith his previous catchment area and he did not know what to do. Responsibility, when used within this study, tended to feel like a burden. Young people within residential care can have limited autonomy, as has been discussed previously, so this is something that needs to develop over time. The reality for the study group is that this may have happened all at once, leaving young people feeling anxious. Bob, however described this in more positive terms when he was balancing work with fun (Bob, Interview thirteen).

Lisa is the only married participant in the study. At 22 years she said

...it's nice to kind of make my own decisions and not have people (*making them for you*)... I've done a lot of growing up really quickly. I've been married for two years..., my sister lives with me full time and I've passed my driving test. Being able to do things that I couldn't have done as a child ... (*she said of her sister that*) she couldn't go and live on her own. I wouldn't do that to her (Lisa, Interview two).

Again, this focus on prioritising the needs of others challenges the perception of emerging adulthood as a time of self-focus, unless of course it is considered in relation to other life stages; in adolescence your interests are enshrined in your peer group and post emerging adulthood you may have family needs to prioritise ahead of your own. Interestingly Lisa did not recognise being in her stable relationship and marriage and taking on the parenting of her younger sibling as an achievement during the interview. This would appear to support Arnett's theory that traditional milestones are not equated with adulthood. She said that it was not something that she gave a second thought to as she did not want her sister to experience the life she had experienced by being taken into care.

Liam (27) spoke about adulthood in a similar way to others in terms of paying bills but also mentioned completing application forms, dealing with letters and 'just having your life together' (Liam, Interview ten). He equated adulthood with responsibilities but also with routine and good respectable citizenship which involved abiding by the law, he felt a predisposition to poorer choices because of the experiences of his family members. Like Amy's experience of being a parent, fatherhood appears to have pushed Liam to move from a life where he was a single man living on his own to someone who puts the needs of others first as he has a house and home to set up (Liam, Interview ten). Parenthood, including the parenthood of one's sister, appeared to be strongly related to a sense of duty and adulthood.

The perspectives participants shared on their sense of adulthood appeared to change as the young people aged, although for two of the young people who had recently left care, they said that they already felt like adults, but this view may change over time as was evident in the experiences of Liam, Bob, and Hamish, the three oldest participants. While Arnett (2007b) views emerging adulthood as a high-risk period for young people who are 'aging out of care' as they are at greater risk of homelessness, substance misuse, prison, mental health difficulties and unemployment these have not been significant features for the young people within this study although Hamish experienced a period of unemployment and homelessness and Tina and Kevin spoke about their emotional wellbeing needs. Instability surrounding

temporary employment has been raised as anxiety provoking as young people expressed fears around their financial security. This will no doubt have had an impact on individual feelings of financial independence with three young people not raising money as an issue although Liam spoke about this less in relation to not having resources and more about his ability to manage what he had effectively. For the young people within the wider emerging adulthood studies being able to rely on the financial resources of parents seems to have largely allowed them to avoid concerns about how they were going to get by (Arnett, 2007b).

8.11 Conclusion

This chapter has used the UNCRC framework on leaving care to illustrate experiences participants have had in relation to preparation and planning, the transition process and post care support. It has illustrated that corporate parents do not take on the same roles that parents have when their children leave home and shows that there is a hasty transition to adulthood as the age that young people leave care continues to be considerably lower than those who leave home within the general population. There was variance on how prepared young people felt for moving on from their residential care placement with many young people not feeling ready to move on and feeling ill equipped to progress to independence as they felt that they did not have the necessary skills or motivation.

Relationships, which are seen as crucially important both in practical and emotional terms, were discussed and only two young people in the study spoke about a supportive family relationship that continued after they left care, one of these young people spent six - seven years post care living with his parents. Most young people within the study spoke about supportive fictive relationships although not all of these relationships continued post care and young people spoke of varying reasons for this. The emotional unpaid labour of workers was highlighted in that even for young people who received ongoing support there was recognition that there were limits to this as the staff now have new young people to care for.

Young people discussed considerable transitions after leaving care not least within education whether this was related to changing courses or institutions. They continued to grapple with what they wanted to do with their lives irrespective of age although most of the participants were drawn to the social care field and one young person had spent a considerable number of years working in this area, he was the only candidate who spoke about being in secure fulltime employment. Most of the other young people within the study, while employed, were engaged in government funded projects resulting in additional pressure to re-apply for positions should funding be extended, or the position become more permanent or

unemployment if tenders were unsuccessful reflecting evidence of the age of instability and a hampered identity exploration due to a lack of identification with colleagues and a secure place of work. As discussed in chapter three, this issue is likely to be further exacerbated by the global economic situation resulting in austerity measures and the impact of COVID-19.

Stein's description of care leavers as fitting into categories for those moving on, surviving, and struggling was a helpful way of viewing how situations can be similar with young people who have shared a number of experiences and this study found that most of the young people sit within the moving on category although it was highlighted that this may change over time as the stability of situations alter. The nuances of experiences however are not captured by categorising these experiences. More positively young people spoke about survival as a strength and something that they were proud of as many young people they had lived through care with were no longer alive.

The interviews show that some young people felt satisfied with their experiences within care as these were largely positive. These would be described as a feature of those described as 'moving on' (Stein, 2006). Other participants felt ill-treated and discussed ongoing poor family relationships, Stein (2006) describes this group as 'survivors'. The final categorisation relates to those who experienced dependency on state welfare and grappled with separations, this group were described as 'strugglers' (Stein, 2006).

All the participants spoke about their sense of identity stemming from their care experience and for all but one of the participants, as discussed in the previous chapter, this shared identity resulted from their membership, voluntary, employed or participatory with the Champions Advocacy Group (CAG). This identity and ongoing support undoubtedly enabled young people to get through their most challenging times and gave them a sense of family, particularly evident in interviews with Luna, Kevin, John, Hamish, and Bob. The chapter touched on the similarity of experience for young people with a shared identity in relation to race.

Experiences within CAG may have had an impact on the group's altruistic tendencies in relation to engagement with voluntary work. While emerging adulthood sees being self-focussed as a key tenet of this life stage this was not the case for the three participants with caring responsibilities and most participants engaged in some form of voluntary work. Arnett found that care leavers were required to be self-focussed irrespective of whether they were ready or willing or not, but my study appears to indicate that the commonality and support from advocacy encourages young people to think collectively rather than individually (Arnett, 2007a).

Individual financial vulnerability was a consistent experience of the young people and as outlined in this chapter, many young people struggled to make ends meet resulting in rent arrears, financial insecurity, and an inability to pay bills. This culminated in homelessness for Hamish and a fear of opening the door for Tania due to concerns it would be people looking for her to repay debt. Only two young people in the study could rely on the support of their parents, knowing that they would be there if they needed financial help. Some young people had to rely on more formal support and while there was evidence, as was the case for Tina, that throughcare assistance was forthcoming, Hamish said you could speak to the social work department if you required financial support, but the likelihood was that the answer would be no, although Kevin spoke about the support he received from his employer. There was a sense from several participants that you would only seek this form of help if you were desperate as social work agency staff had stopped being in contact.

Around one third of participants in the study viewed themselves as adults despite a lack of financial stability and this view was more likely to be held by young people who spent shorter periods of time in care rather than being determined by age although it is also linked to participants experience of preparation in relation to independent living skills. The emotional needs of young people appeared to be linked to duration within the care system, with those in care longer struggling the most with their emotional wellbeing. Many of the participants spoke about how they had not really reached adulthood yet although in some ways they felt that they had. This would be reflective of the nature of being a care leaver where you do not have a choice about whether you leave care or not as you cannot remain there forever. It is also in keeping with Arnett's in between stage of emerging adulthood (Arnett, 2007a).

Finally, all the participants in the study felt a sense of achievement from their care experience with many believing that they would not have survived if they had not been removed from their families. This sense of survival is very strong and there was a real feeling of optimism from most of the young people which opens endless possibilities, the last feature of emerging adulthood, although this was tempered with an inevitability and sense of fate and destiny.

While none of the participants spoke of aspirations, there was a pride in what they had achieved and a sense of looking forward to the future, tempered with concern about secure accommodation and employment. One of the challenges here lies in that only one young person felt that they received the therapeutic interventions necessary for them to come to terms with their experiences illustrating a gap in services across social care and health (Interview two). This is extremely concerning, and while therapeutic input cannot happen in

isolation with young people, if they are to be prepared for the next stage of their life journey work must be done to heal what has gone before. For some young people, there were discussions around having to just get on with it while others grappled with emotional and mental health needs.

The final chapter will conclude this study by highlighting the key findings of this PhD. It will illustrate the core issues that have had an impact on successful transitions to adulthood by drawing out the key themes looking at participants experiences before they went into care, while living in care and on their journey out of and after care. In addition to discussing what has helped young people to achieve better outcomes and to live developmentally healthy lives the chapter will identify several barriers that have impaired experiences and developments. It will conclude by making several recommendations that will be of interest to practitioners, academics, and policy makers and that will hopefully inform practice for years to come.

CHAPTER NINE: DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

9.1 Introduction

The final chapter of this PhD will pull together the learning from this study. Continuing to be located within my field of study has been invaluable as it has allowed me to have daily reflections about my work and to refine my practice in light of research learning. By identifying why the work was crucial in the first place, I will show the research journey taken and illustrate how the historical context is of significance when considering young people's lived care experiences and their subsequent outcomes. Taking a life cycle and holistic approach, I will highlight the before, during and after of residential care experiences, identifying supportive measures that participants describe as having enhanced these experiences, as well as barriers that resulted in them feeling less prepared for adult life. These findings have implications at practice, culture, and policy levels.

The aim of this discussion and conclusion is to illustrate what could be viewed as the social construction of poor outcomes for young people. What has been socially constructed can be socially reconstructed and ultimately provide insight into what is required to enhance looked after children's lives. As I reflected on within the introduction to this PhD there are similarities between experiences of youngsters in care and other forms of discrimination and the parallels between historical perspectives of race and what we see in the epigenetics and the neuroscience research around adversity. However unintentional, this positions social problems as the responsibility of individuals, pathologizing them and their communities instead of locating them in wider discourses about society. Like other movements there are increasingly voices stepping forward to both challenge the science of ACEs and emphasise the link between poverty and socioeconomic position and poorer outcomes (White and Wastell, 2017; Walsh, McCartney, Smith and Armour, 2019; Ross, 2019).

This chapter will illustrate what supports the transition to adulthood for 13 care experienced young people. Despite their differences however, we can learn from participants by illustrating protective and resilience inducing factors that enabled children and young people to develop positively into functioning and successful adults. But before I look at this in more detail I will restate the Scottish context as this specificity lies in one of my original contributions to knowledge.

9.2 The Scottish Context: The need for cohesion and comparative data collection and analysis

There is so much unknown about the experiences of young people who have experienced residential care within Scotland. There is a dearth of research, particularly qualitative research that applies theoretical frameworks but quantitative research largely results from inquiries or re-enforces what is already known. Scotland is viewed as one of the most progressive countries in the world when looking at its approach to the welfare of children and young people, although this is not supported by some evidence that shows they have higher numbers of young people in residential care and the UNCRC places the wider UK 16th out of a possible 29th when comparing child wellbeing indicators across the world's wealthiest countries (Partners in Advocacy, 2020; UNICEF, 2013). While it is argued that comparative studies across the UK is plagued by data collection and analysis challenges (Bywaters, Scourfield, Jones, Sparks, Elliott, Hooper, McCartan, Shapira, Bunting and Daniel, 2018), comprehensive data is not available in Scotland resulting in challenges gathering both qualitative and quantitative national data on the experiences of care leavers (Care Review, 2020).

Scotland's participatory and rights-based approach is embedded in childcare legislation and while this is not cohesive (Care Review, 2020), it is reflected in the Children's Hearing System established in 1971 (Partners in Advocacy, 2020). Mechanisms that promote and support needs and manage risks associated with children who are identified as potentially vulnerable are evident throughout the Scottish system. Scotland's bill adopting the UNCRC into legislation, the Independent Care Review and plans outlined in 'The Promise' and 'Keeping the Promise' help to outline the governments' commitment to making Scotland the best place in the world for children to grow up. This has been a theme in social policy for almost two decades (Care Review, 2020; 2021; Scottish Government, 2008; 2012).

But this is not without its contradictions in relation to holding children and young people accountable for their actions. In 2019 the age of criminal responsibility was increased from 8 to 12 years old meaning that Scotland has continued to lag-behind other countries in the Global North when dealing with children who come into significant conflict with the law (Houses of Parliament, 2018). The Promise has outlined the contradictions and tensions that are evident with Scotland having more than forty pieces of legislation relating to children reflective of inconsistencies in the legal definition of a child which can vary depending on the legislation used. For care experienced children, as discussed in Chapters three and seven, the age definitions used are either sixteen or eighteen years old (Care Review, 2020). The Care Review (2020) proposed that legal differences are addressed to promote consistency

within Scotland, and it has been agreed that this will form part of the next parliamentary session. When Scotland fully embeds the UNCRC bill it will also result in a child being defined as someone under the age of 18 years old (Scottish Parliament, 2021).

In 2020, 14,458 children were looked after by their local authority and 10% of these young people lived within residential care so this study is reflective of around 10% of those placed within group care at any given time in Scotland (Scottish Children's Reporter Administration, 2020). So, while a small-scale study it provides insight into the lives of thirteen young people from similar backgrounds with a range of diverse and individual experiences. Outcomes reflected in other studies that illustrate that young care leavers are more likely to be homeless, unemployed, have higher early mortality rates, poorer mental health, greater involvement in criminal activity, increased risk of early pregnancy and less access to continuing education or training are largely unsupported by this study (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham, and Harkin, 2014; Stein, 2006). This may be in part due to the study's scale but it may also be linked to the recruitment process. All of the participants in this study, with the exception of one, had a connection to an advocacy agency which by its nature promoted ongoing emotional wellbeing support. Fowler, Welch and Plunkett's (2018) literature review highlighted the benefits of paid and unpaid mentors in providing emotional support for care leavers. Adley and Jupp Kina (2017) also speak of the lack of attention to emotional support afforded care leavers. Young people had significant relationships with both peers and organisers within this organisation and spoke about how much the service had impacted on their ability to develop a secure identity. Further research addressing the impact of advocacy services would enhance our understanding of its impact. Other studies also support the need for more qualitative research in the leaving care field, particularly research that uses theoretical frameworks (Pinkerton, 2021; Stein, 2006; Urquhart-Stewart and Wylie, 2021).

9.3 Participants early experiences of poverty and adversity

As illustrated in chapters two and six, healthy child development relies on a secure base where care givers are attuned to the child's needs promoting the formation of secure attachment relationships (Bowlby, 1988; UNICEF, 2010; Sroufe and Sampson). It is widely accepted these needs are likely to be met within a family environment (UNICEF, 2010), although family forms reflect diversity and what constitutes a family has changed over time and space. Despite the prevalence of familial ideology presenting the family as parents and children (McNeill, Blundell and Griffiths, 2003), in 2011, the prevalent household consisted of single adults with families accounting for less than a quarter of households in Scotland (The Scottish Census, 2011;

National Records of Scotland, 2018). While fiscal policy has helped to reduce poverty among the largely aged population, in 2020 the Joseph Rowntree Foundation illustrated that poverty among children, working adults and pensioners has risen over the past five years (Joseph Rowntree Foundation, 2020). Scottish Government (2019) data shows that one in four children, around 260,000 youngsters, live in households that are living below the poverty line and legislation introduced in 2017 to reduce poverty for children is unlikely to meet targets set to lessen poverty (Corlett, 2019).

An emphasis on epigenetics and neuroscience linked to adversity has rendered poverty unfashionable in political discourse within which poor people are being blamed for structural disadvantage (White and Wastell, 2016). Walsh, McCartney, Smith and Armour (2019) also argue that lower socioeconomic position (SEP) in childhood is associated with a greater risk of experiencing adversity and the greater the number of adversities, the poorer that outcomes are likely to be, although it is recognised that impact can be mitigated by a relationship with a trusted adult (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Furnival, 2011).

Most of the young people within this study spoke about their experiences of adversity, including poor carer mental health, familial criminal activity or imprisonment, drugs or alcohol abuse amongst parents, familial violence and issues around neglect or abuse within the family home. The number of adverse experiences were reflective of up to five for the males in the study and between three and four for the female participants. These experiences may be further exacerbated due to inconsistent parenting when young people go into care, due to differences between parental and carer parenting styles as well as the changing nature of care associated with residential care (Porter, Mitchell and Giraldi, 2020).

Additionally, it is widely recognised that parental stress can be linked to experiences of material deprivation (Joseph Rowntree Foundation, 2020; Devaney, Frederick and Spratt, 2020; Independent Care Review, 2020). All these factors can impact on the brain's ability to function effectively (Perry, 2006), and while it has been argued that cognisance of duration and severity should be included in ACEs studies as well as other factors such as familial death, there is evidence that links adversity to poorer long-term outcomes (Anda, Felitti, Bremner, Whitfield, Perry, Dube, Gilles, 2006; Marryat and Frank, 2019). Who caused the adversity, and whether it was experienced across a range of settings, can be mediated by supportive measures, strategies and relationships (Marryat and Frank, 2019). Numbers appear to matter, and adversity was particularly associated with having four or more ACEs, a feature for eight

participants in this group (Marryat and Frank, 2019). Complex trauma can also help us to understand when experiences are more systematic and not an isolated event. Most of the participants did not experience adversity as a one of event, although Mark would be an exception here. These circumstances were experienced by most young people while living within the family home.

A reduction in child poverty is seen as life changing for many children and families due to poverty's association with familial stress potentially being linked with an increased incidence of child abuse and neglect (Bywater, Bunting, Davidson, Hanratty, Mason, McCartan and Steils, 2016). Recognition that while infancy is important, life trajectories can be impacted by development and growth throughout the life span (Newman and Blackburn, 2002; Miller and Baxter, 2019). However, we need to continue to work to develop a better understanding of the relationship between poverty and adversity and to promote strategies that avoid pathologizing individuals and address the root causes of the problem (White and Wastell, 2017; Pysiainen, Halpin and Guilfoyle, (2017).

9.4 Attachments and separations: Young people's experience of being rejected

As well as parental separation, which was experienced by 11 out of the 13 participants, (this is one of the ten original ACEs (Appendix 8)), over one third of the study group experienced changes to their living arrangements on multiple occasions as they were moved between family members or foster carers (Lisa, Carol, Tania, John and Tina, Interviews two, three, four, eight and eleven). Carol spoke about her experience of parental figures as she was moved between her mother and aunt before going into formal state care (Carol, Interview three), while Tania discussed being separated from siblings and then reunited and separated again as agencies tried to secure her adoption (Tania, Interview four).

These transitions faced by young people may affect their ability to form secure and stable trusting relationships with others (Newman and Blackburn, 2002). Bowlby's (1974) shows the interplay between nurture and the environment with the primary attachment relationship seen as changeable from one day to another and across the span of the day but once a secure relationship is created the ability to form these affectional bonds is extended to other relationships. It is also highlighted that when carers do not respond appropriately to signs of distress the child may react as though human contact has no significance and behaviour was modified as they expected subsequent loss but others illustrate that these relationships are multiple (Bowlby, 1974; Mead, 1969; Furnival, 2011). The intensity of the child's reaction was

said to be affected positively by being with a sibling or one replacement carer as was evident initially in John's experience (John, Interview eight) living with his stepsister and grandmother (Bowlby, 1974; 1979). Subsequent research has highlighted that multiple caregivers can provide the nurture that children and young people need (Furnival, 2011; Rutter, 1979; Mead, 1969; Kendrick, 2013), and all of the participants in this study benefited from the care and in some cases love provided by individuals whose job it was to look after them.

In social work and social care, the term 'transition' is used to describe movement from one place to another, from one activity to another and from one state or stage to another and it is clear from young people's accounts that social workers attempted to secure living arrangements within family placements, including with foster carers to minimise placement moves (Smith, 2009). This is also indicative of the discourse around families being the best place for children to grow up, although the composition of the family continues to be contested (UNICEF, 2010; Scottish Government, 2008, 2013). Smart and Digney (2015) highlight that young people go through simultaneous transitions that they do not learn to manage, instead they become desensitized to the experience. This supports my argument, outlined in chapter six, that a more effective term for placement moves is 'rejection', with young people trying to shield themselves from the expected impact of change where a new beginning is not seen as an opportunity but instead is another situation where children 'begin again', reshare their story and are judged about why their previous placement was not a success.

Only two of the young people in the sample were placed within residential care as a first choice. The reluctance to view this form of care positively and as a placement of choice for many children and young people appears to increase the likelihood of more transitions occurring (Porter, Mitchell and Giraldi, 2020; Scottish Parliament, 2008; Interviews five and eight, Kevin and John). Bronfenbrenner (1979) describes an 'ecological transition' reflective of role and behavioural expectation changes. This will have an additional significance when a young person leaves their own system and becomes part of an alternative system that may not initially be connected to their home, family, school and own community. None of the participants spoke about experiences of feeling connected to their former ecological environments suggesting that their statutory carers did not promote ongoing time within local communities or with people known to the children and young people despite legislation and guidance promoting this.

In addition to separations from parents and home communities, Tania spoke about multiple separations from brothers and sisters and of feeling isolated from her family (Tania, Interview

four). Questions have to be asked about permanence and stability and how the system critically reviews placement breakdowns given our understanding of the importance of security and stability to meeting the needs of children (Maslow, 1970; Ainsworth, Salter, and Bell, 1970). Given the small scale of this study further data collection and analysis is required to make more informed hypothesis in this area. It has long been recognised that there is a need for consistent data collection nationally so that placements are open to comparisons and to ensure that the onus does not solely lie with residential care providers to produce evidence of positive outcomes (Care Review, 2020).

Most of the young men in the study were exceptions to multiple placements in the public and private realms, although two had upwards of 15 living arrangements. One participant spoke about spending a brief period of time living with his father. He said his father left him with an aunt and never returned (Hamish, Interview nine) while another male participant said that the social work department contacted his father after he had not seen him for a considerable period of time, he had moved to England. Three of the participants had similar experiences with their fathers, and multiple rejections were viewed as impacting on self-esteem and the ability to form future secure relationships. Kevin described his relationships with others as 'ridiculous' by way of stressing how difficult it was for him to form meaningful relationships (Kevin, Interview five).

9.5 The importance of supportive sustained social networks

In keeping with legal obligations of parental responsibilities it is reasonable for social workers to contact absent fathers but for the young people concerned it appears to have caused a level of harm (Kevin and Hamish, Interviews five and nine). A paradigm shift in society's gendered approach to parenting is needed for parental responsibilities to be equally assumed by both parents as this study found that fathers were absent in the ongoing love and care of their children. Within Scotland, however, there remain legal barriers to this in terms of how fathers obtain parental rights and responsibilities. The Children (Scotland) Act 1995 applied legal rights and responsibilities to fathers who were married to mothers although for those born after the 1st of April 2006 in Scotland, fathers also had rights if they were named on the child's birth certificate because of the Family Law (Scotland) Act, 2006. Young people may benefit from legislative change that instils equal rights to both parents, although as stated earlier it is not the composition of the family that is important but the stability of family makeup (Treanor, 2016). There was a considerable lack of men as role models for the young people within the study with only two participants having contact with their fathers and neither uncles,

or grandfathers were mentioned in relation to nurture or care within the family. This has implications for gender within residential care which must ensure that children and young people experience positive role modelling from men and women when growing up. This responsibility however cannot remain with care agencies.

Remaining in contact with biological parents and communities where young people have grown up was not a feature for most of the participants when they went into care. This, in part, resulted from young people blaming, particularly their mothers, for their reception into care but also appears to result from the complex nature of the extended family relationship dynamics. Half of the young men in the study resented their mother attending their children's hearings and meetings and asked that this was stopped as they felt that she was there to serve her own interests, this may have resulted from parents attempting to address their own experiences of stigma. It was also viewed as painful as mother was not involved in their day-to-day care but wanted to have an input and be involved in decision making, while they were not in her care (Kevin, Bruce and Bob, Interviews five, six and thirteen).

Relationships with brothers and sisters was very different for all of the participants who had a sibling. Nobody who spent time with their brothers and sisters wanted this time to be stopped. Bob returned to live with his parents after care and this may be linked to their ongoing support of him during his twelve years in placement (Bob, Interview thirteen). This would support the view that these relationships are crucial for promoting a secure base in the longer term, in addition to promoting familial identity formation and the development of community ties as he was the only participant to return to his former home and community. This appears to have ensured a longer-term positive outcome in the strength of relationships and should be consistently promoted by social work staff and residential workers when it is appropriate to do so (Bullock, Litte and Millham, 1993; Kendrick, 2013; Winter, 2015).

As touched upon above, the complexity but importance of the extended family cannot be underestimated with just under half of the participants discussing aunts and grandparents, in addition to parents and brothers and sisters. Participants spoke about being parented by grandparents and for John this role was significant as it provided him with a stable base until his grandmother died when he was 12 years old. For other young people not having contact with the extended family when they went into care impacted on their emotional wellbeing. For example, Luna spoke about missing out on family events and reading about them on Facebook and this may have resulted from an oversight as she was not physically within the family environment, so it appears to have been a case of forgetting to include her, although

this assumption cannot be corroborated (Luna, Interview one). Tina also spoke about how her aunt and grandmother stopped including her in family get togethers because she was unable to cope with being the only one of her siblings who did not live within a family. She said that she struggled to 'deal with her trauma' which played out in 'acting out' behaviour as she could not understand this and internalised her feelings of blame (Tina, Interview eleven). This statement would be consistent with findings of the Care Review in relation to language as it sounds like language that a staff member would use, and a child internalise although it is not clear if there is an understanding of what any of these words mean (Care Review, 2020). Roles, functioning, norms, and history can be lost when ongoing contact with people that matter is not maintained, and this can have a lasting impact as workers are left to fill in the gaps. These social consequences are in addition to the emotional impact noted elsewhere. The experience of seeing extended family members was viewed by Kevin as unnatural and all the participants spoke about familial relationship difficulties that were not resolved while they were in care, resulting in a lack of change when young people left care.

Professionals working with children, young people and families should value the importance of these relationships as they are at the core to promoting long-term healthy relationships and positive identity formation. Parent should not solely mean mother and family time should be promoted when it is safe to do so (Bullock, Litte and Millham, 1993; Care Review, 2021). In addition, restoring and repairing relationships among family members appears to be necessary to ensure that individuals can work through feelings of blame and shame.

As outlined previously, many of the participants were placed in a variety of kinship or foster placements before going into care, only Mark and Kevin were exceptions here. Whilst a policy imperative in keeping with the early years and early intervention strategy and minimum intervention principles, this practice can serve to re-enforce to young people that there is something wrong with them as they experience multiple rejections and blame themselves for why they cannot live within a family. It can also impact on a sense of felt security for children and young people as is evident in the number of placement-moves those within the study experienced. Only two participants had experienced two or less placements, and they were the two young people who experienced residential care at the ages of 10 and 14 years old. Less frequent transitions appeared to offer the stability children and young people need although the nature of the relationships for Kevin appeared to impact on his mental health (Kevin and Mark, Interviews five and seven). For the other participants there was significant variance in the number of placements ranging from 3 - 51 with almost a third of the study

group experiencing a dozen or more. This multiplicity was more likely to be experienced within family type environments rather than residential care highlighting the continued view within social work that family placements are best despite evidence within this study reflecting that they are more likely to break down.

In addition to multiple family placements and attachments, separation and loss, young people spoke about the impact going into care had on their sibling relationships with all but one young person having siblings, although half of the remainder came from families where they were the only person to go into care. None of the group remained with brothers or sisters in care despite keeping sibling groups together being one of the many functions of residential care (Shaw, 2007). Research has indicated that membership of a sibling group provides children and young people with a unique identity so the impact of separation cannot be underestimated (NICE/SCIE, 2010). The complexity of sibling relationships was highlighted in chapter six with many participants experiencing a complicated version of sibling rivalry or guilt (Interviews one, four and eleven; five and ten). The Independent Care Review (2020) states that children should remain with their families when it is safe to do so and, when this is not possible, they must stay alongside their brothers and sisters (Keep the Promise, 2020). Safety cannot be the only consideration here though, given the complexity of these relationships discussed in chapter six. Luna's experience highlighted that sibling relationships can be diverse within the one family, she had a positive relationship with her brother and negative one with her sister, that could be described as resentful and envious on both sides (Luna, Interview one). For just under half of the participants their siblings were not in care, unfortunately due to a lack of data collection locally and nationally it is impossible to ascertain if this is a trend. This can lead to projection or internalisation where shame and blame are evident. These feelings were also evident for some of the participants in the next point of the participants care journey, so I will now illustrate views and experiences of group living and residential care.

9.6 An Alternative to Family Placements: Residential Care

The myths around residential care have prevailed for centuries and these are traditionally rooted in the UK with associations with the Poor Law and workhouse and distinctions between deserving and undeserving individuals in need of charitable support (Higginbotham, 2017; Abrams, 1998; Elsley, 2007). This fact, combined with the narrative that only 'bad kids' go to residential care, had an impact on participants experience of stigma, although one participant highlighted that a lot of the stigma comes from themselves or other young people (Hamish, Interview nine). This would be reflective of the self-fulfilling prophecy where children become reflective of the low expectations people have of them. Before arriving at the residential placement young people spoke about feeling anxious and scared of being physically attacked or badly treated, in part resulting from the urban myths and stories passed from generation to generation about institutional care reflected in narratives such as those shared by Hamish about 'Maggie Murphy's' home (Hamish, Interview nine). There were also examples of not being included in the decision-making processes before going to the placement, for Amy this was evident in social work staff not speaking to her or explaining what was about to happen to her (Amy, Interview twelve) while for Lisa it was reflected by her not being advised that she had a children's hearing, so the move was unexpected (Lisa, Interview two). Transparency and clearer communications were also issues in other areas of this study.

Participants associated 'failure' with being placed in residential care due to perceptions of it as a last resort, inferring when other things have failed. Tania verbalised this by saying that foster placements failed when carers could not manage her behaviour among other things (Tania, Interview four). Luna, Tina, and Lisa all spoke about people assuming they were violent because they lived within residential care so there is a view that your behaviour has led to this form of placement and that it is the individual's fault (Luna, Tina and Lisa, Interviews one, two and eleven). This was supported by a Scandinavian study that illustrated the perception of children as either in danger or dangerous (Enell and Wilinska, 2020). Only two out of all the participants did not feel that negative stereotypes were applied to them (Mark and John, Interviews seven and eight).

Community partners, such as the Police, were described as stigmatising. Bob highlighted that the police visited the residential house frequently and every time something happened locally there was an assumption that one of the residents were to blame (Bob, Interview thirteen). Some of the young people attempted to avoid the negative stereotypes by associating with

young people outside the system or by creating narratives to disguise their circumstances (Luna and Kevin, Interviews one and five). Goffman (1963) states that stigmatised people may show identity ambivalence, reflecting a lack of a secure identity formation. This can be a mechanism to avoid being stereotyped and this was clearly the case for Kevin and John (Interviews five and eight). It was more difficult for Luna to distance herself as she continued to attend the same school as her brother and sister despite not living at home. All the other participants transitioned to alternative education provision, which provided smaller class sizes but also a more limited but bespoke curriculum. Luna created the narrative that she was living with another relative to avoid being stigmatised (Luna, Interview one). Moving school was advantageous to some young people who said that they moved to a more affluent area and had better opportunities (Kevin and Hamish, Interviews five and nine). Tina found that she was stigmatised at school because she used a different language to her classmates, because of her knowledge of the social work system and her removal from lessons to attend meetings she referred to as 'panels'. It must be asked if this knowledge and understanding is what gave most of the participants the confidence and social capital to work within the social care field where they are experts and more experienced than others with no experience of the system (Leonard, 2005; Lin, 2001). Tina and Kevin both spoke about low expectations from others for them to succeed because of their care background despite them being the highest academic achievers of the group (Kevin, and Tina, Interviews five and eleven). There was considerable determination from the group to achieve more than was expected from them as young people did not want to be another poor statistic.

The public as well as those in the field need to develop a greater understanding of care and residential care in particular so that we can reconstruct the narrative and disperse the historical perspective that residential care is a 'last resort' for young people. This may help to dispel and overcome some of the stigma associated with this type of care. More positive research in the field can help to share positive outcomes that can be experienced with the right support.

Part of the stigma linked to residential care results from research reflecting that young people from this type of placement will have poorer outcomes than the general population and those who have lived within foster homes (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham and Harkin, 2014; Care Review, 2020; Kendrick, Steckley and Lerpiniere, 2008). Data that reflects those placed in residential care have more complex needs without critically reviewing and analysing their context can add to negative perceptions (Scottish Children's Reporter Administration, 2020). Only two participants were placed in residential care as a first care placement and both experienced good outcomes overall (Interviews five and eight). Most of the participants within

this group could be described as high achievers with one of the official measures of success being educational outcomes. Nine young people within this study experienced college and three experienced university with one of these young people completing a degree (Scottish Government, 2020). This study is unique in that sense as educational attainment was not a criterion for participation.

Expectations that residential care placements alone can overcome a lifetime of adversity and in many cases, trauma are unrealistic when many of the young people experienced multiple family breakdowns both outwith and within the care system (Interviews two, three, four, six, eight, nine, ten and twelve). An understanding of young people's experiences is needed by both workers and the young people themselves and the importance of chronologies and professional therapeutic input has to be highlighted here. Surprisingly, only one young person within this study spoke about receiving therapeutic interventions; this lasted seven years and continued post-care but helped her to come to terms with her life experiences (Lisa, Interview two). Liam also highlighted the importance of support not just being made available to him but to parents too (Liam, Interview ten). This recommendation is supported by the findings of the Care Review (Care Review, 2020).

If all young people in residential care have a chronology it would help to maximise their understanding of their experience and provide the depth of information necessary for professionals to critically analyse the data and its impact on the child. Chronology training is widely available to social care and social work staff through local authorities. Access to therapeutic support should be offered to anyone who needs this as well as an opportunity to engage in work that allows young people to process their life story. Kevin and Tina (Interviews five and eleven) spoke about seeking out counselling when they left care, a time when they are under additional pressure as they have less of a support network. Support for families may also help to improve understanding and familial relationships and potentially prevent other siblings from going into care.

Young people need to better understand their circumstances and process experiences in a meaningful way that reflects that being in care is not their fault. Young people expressed shame and blame for being in care, and residential care in particular. Without this support well-meaning staff can transfer the blame for individual circumstances onto family members. Tina spoke about how she had blamed herself for going into care, but her supportive staff member explained it was her mothers fault (Tina, Interview eleven). This can impact on the restoration of relationships and is an unintended consequence of a staff members attempt to

help. Although just under two thirds of participants said that they knew why they went into care in the first place only one participant appeared to have a balanced understanding of their situation. This may result from placement transitions that may not be linked to the original set of family circumstances (Liam, Interview ten). Liam was one of only two participants who were in full-time secure employment and his experience working in the social care sector and two supportive fictive kin relationships appear to have enabled him to see matters from both a structural perspective and individual perspective. He said that his parents were not able to meet his needs, but he was able to have them met by adults looking after him within the care system (Liam, Interview ten). This provided him with the secure base and support he needed when things went wrong.

Two of the younger participants who had different experiences despite having long standing supportive fictive relationships, spoke about their ongoing mental health needs and difficulties they had receiving services that helped them to come to terms with the impact of being in care (Kevin and Tina, Interviews five and eleven). A lack of mental health support services for children and young people is a policy issue that has also been highlighted elsewhere (Audit Scotland, 2018), while Miller, Wakefield and Sani (2015) linked good mental health to multiple group identities such as family, peer, school. Few participants had positive affiliations in these areas, this is not a surprising finding given that they moved away from their family, their peer group and for all but one, their local school. A positive association with school was seen as the strongest indicator of good mental health for 13–17-year-olds (Miller, Wakefield and Sani, 2015). The absence of multiple group membership affects how individuals cope in times of stress (Miller, Wakefield and Sani, 2015). The Scottish Governments mental health strategy highlights the need to develop more supports for children and young people (Scottish Government, 2017).

The strong fictive relationships described by Liam were also evident in Tina's account supporting the importance of the residential care workers relationships with young people (Ibsen and Klobus, 1972). Tina spoke about loving her care worker who was like a mother to her (Tina, Interview eleven). There were many positive stories about strong relationships with residential workers, not always the keyworker, and many of these relationships continued post care. Everyone except from Lisa felt that they had developed positive relationships with staff in placement, although Lisa said that she felt that she missed out on that one significant person, in a family this would be a parent, who would look out for you and support and nurture you, so she felt that she had missed out in group care (Lisa, Interview two). Despite this she

revisited her placement after leaving and maintains contact with some of the staff (Lisa, Interview two).

Continued relationships were discussed by nine out of the thirteen respondents but there were barriers to visits as staff were now looking after different young people and much of the additional support that these staff members provide is unpaid labour that goes largely unrecognised. Tina found it difficult that her staff members had moved on to new relationships. As would be expected young people wanted to visit those who they connected with while in care however, Tina, Kevin, Bob, and John suggested that some residential staff should not be working with children as they didn't have the right attitude. In *Keeping the Promise* (2020) the importance of staff values is highlighted rather than qualifications as this was also a finding of the *Independent Care Review* (2018). Residential workers continue to be seen as the poor relatives of social work with qualification requirements and salary lower than for qualified social workers.

Relationships with social work professionals were more ambivalent than the experiences participants shared about residential childcare workers. Participants spoke about social work professionals not being in contact enough (Bob, Interview thirteen) or of a lack of stability due to staffing changes with John experiencing eight new workers in five years (John, Interview eight) while Lisa had thirteen social workers in less than five years (Lisa, Interview two). Nobody kept in touch with their social worker post-care but this is unsurprising, given that they are fundamental in decision making for young people going in to care and their role is not one of care giver, unlike the residential worker who may have daily contact with the young people. Further research is needed into the effect of instability within social work and social care staffing for young people who experience services. The *Care Review* (2020) has highlighted that there are limited mechanisms for promoting ongoing contact when children leave care and staff wanting to continue contact can be met with suspicion. This area will be developed as part of the ten-year plan (*Care Review*, 2021).

9.7 The Residential Effect

The instability of social workers was not the only experience of precariousness participants discussed. Unlike secure care, which is legislatively time constrained, young people can be placed within residential care for an indefinite period. The uncertainty of their situation appears to impact on their sense of agency as they have no control over their circumstances; in secure care young people are placed there as they are a danger to themselves or others so a reduction in risk will impact on them being released (Nolan, 2019).

A lack of understanding about long-term living arrangements appears to have caused participants a great deal of anxiety. Kevin spoke about not having a sense of security within residential care despite being in the same placement for eight years (Interview five). This was linked to his view that young people came and went so he had a sense that he could be next. Staff movement, without any explanation, exacerbated this insecurity, with loved staff members moved without warning. Luna spoke about being fearful of forming friendships for the same reason, she was scared that either her or her friend would be moved (Interview one). Despite this anxiety she was one of only three participants who formed friendships within the group care setting that continued post-care (Luna, Bruce and Mark, Interviews one, six and seven).

Three participants spoke of how shift-working affected their residential experience. When you live with parents you learn how to respond to different parenting styles but for children with multiple care givers there is a complex array of relationships, rules, demands and expectations to navigate. Hamish found this experience disruptive and inconsistent (Hamish, Interview nine). Rules also differed depending on the local authority area where the young person lived, with one authority said to have a policy against hugs (Kevin, Interview five). Being institutionalised was something described by Kevin who spoke about familiarity with fire regulations and signing for pocket money as well as needing permission to go out with friends or have sleepovers or to experience other childhood events such as trips to the beach. This meant that some young people felt that their childhood was impaired (Kevin and John, Interviews five and eight). A lack of individualised care was also evident in Tina's account where she shared her experience of confectionary, deodorant and razors being locked away because that they were a risk to some of the other residents (Tina, Interview eleven). This may be a barrier in larger scale houses, I will return to other obstacles when looking at preparation for leaving. In effect, these experiences reflect how processes and practices designed to promote safe childhoods impair development and experiences of childhood.

The behaviour of others within the placement can be triggering and remind young people of historical events. Kevin spoke of an escalation in pain-based behaviours as a way for other residents to get attention from staff and he believed that because he did not 'act out' his emotional needs were overlooked in group care (Kevin, Interview five). Bob also spoke about staff but from the point of view of priorities - staff were in the office when you needed them or they would ask you to wait, and he could not understand the legitimacy of this, but it appears that they had competing priorities (Bob, Interview thirteen). Regulatory requirements of record keeping can result in staff struggling to juggle their administrative role and direct care role

(Green, 2005). Luna spoke about having to mature quickly within residential care and keeping her emotions in check, she said it was a hard place for her to live (Luna, Interview one). All the young people, except Bob, shared positive experiences of their time in group care and two of these spoke about feelings of guilt due to the good experience as they were aware of others who did not have the same experience. Hamish spoke about how he did not want to speak about his good life stories when he was with other care experienced youngsters, and he has only recently been able to speak up. This is concerning as it means that a balanced view of residential care experiences is less likely to be heard but it can be set in the context of the earlier discussion around a perceived hierarchy of stories with the most harrowing having currency. This is deserving of further investigation.

9.8 Leaving Care and Living More Independently

Chapter eight highlighted that those leaving care do so at a much younger age than those in the general population with current statistics reflecting that over 50% of both male and female young adults continue to live with their parents between the ages of 21 and 30 years old (Office for National Statistics, 2020), whereas care leavers in this study left their placement between the ages of 16 and 21 years old. The framework from the 'United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child' for leaving alternative care guidance was used to show how participants experienced 'preparation and planning', the 'transition process' and 'aftercare support' (Munro et. al., 2011). I highlighted that there is no accountability for those countries who do not adhere to guidance suggesting it is persuasive guidance rather than a mechanism for holding states accountable.

Young people in Scotland's understanding of leaving care appears to follow the legal definition which is "the legal cessation of legal responsibility by the state for young people" (Scottish Government, 2004b, p. 9) which usually results from a children's hearing removing a young person's supervision order, this cannot remain in place when a child turns 18 years old. Many young people realise when it is too late that they are not ready to leave care and Amy spoke of knowing this after she turned 16 and was leaving her placement (Amy, Interview twelve). Hamish also spoke about what he considered to be those in charge of residential houses in his local authority area wanting him to leave when he turned 16 although the decision was not formally made until he was 19 years old when he left with his belongings in bin bags, a practice that was highlighted in various campaigns as very poor practice (A National Voice, 2005).

There is a formal preparation process in place in Scotland that was introduced in 2004, Pathways Planning, where a young person is assessed, and a plan put in place to prepare

them for leaving care and live more independently (Scottish Government, 2004a). Data from the Scottish Government in 2020 reflects that 266 of 326 residential care experience young people had a pathways plan (Scottish Government, 2020). Within this study nobody had a plan although from Bob's account it appears that a lack of plan could be associated with an unreadiness to move on. He said that as he was not ready to move on, he did not see any benefits in having a plan (Bob, Interview thirteen). Figures consistently show that around 82% of those leaving residential care have a pathways plan and it is crucial that this figure is increased as it promotes good practice and a mechanism for a holistic assessment of readiness. Practical preparation and planning can be put in place to manage this transition sensitively, but this does not equate to young care leavers being afforded the same opportunity as their non-care experienced peers. Equating corporate parenting with natural parenting could help to move away from the age distinction associated with maturity for care leavers.

Only Tina could be considered to have experienced a well thought out preparation and planning process while she was in her residential placement (Tina, Interview eleven). She said that her preparation started when she was 15 years old when an independent living plan was put in place. Her transition was gradual and began with tidying her bedroom, doing laundry and setting her own alarm for school and this developed to budgeting, shopping and cooking healthy meals after a year (Tina, Interview eleven). She was supported by the cook in her house and staff so it appears to have been a whole team approach and this would be recognised as best practice. Mendes et al. (2020) state that good transition planning for care leavers should happen between the ages of 12 and 15 years old and a holistic approach to preparation should be taken.

A barrier to preparation within residential care was seen as the number of young people to staff ratio within the placement, most of the houses had between six and 16 residents, so young people found it difficult to get the quality time needed with staff for preparation to be meaningful due to competing demands on staff (Tina and Bob, Interviews eleven and thirteen). Luna lived in a house with seven other young people and said that staff could have done better (Luna, Interview one). Small changes to residential care placements, such as smaller numbers of young people and higher staff ratios could ensure that they are better able to meet the longer-term needs of children and young people. All young people could be prepared gradually for the time when they are no longer in care.

These practical skills learned by Tina were also discussed by some of the participants who moved onto supported accommodation placements although the depth and consistency of preparation varied (Lisa, Bruce, John and Amy, Interviews two, six, seven, eight and twelve). In addition, supported accommodation was viewed as allowing young people to move at their own pace and gain additional skills such as door management (Bruce and John, Interviews six and eight). Learning to pay electricity and rent were viewed positively by some participants as preparation for the real world (John, Interview eight) but for others there was a feeling that the safety net of the staff provided an unrealistic cushion that would not be experienced when you lived on your own (Hamish, Interview nine).

Luna and Liam described personal deficits that they believed they had that impaired their readiness for more independent life (Luna and Liam, Interviews one and ten). They were not able to see that their accelerated transition to adulthood was unrealistic, particularly given their previous life experiences. Both young people felt that it was their fault as they lacked motivation and that was why they did not have the necessary adult life skills. Unrealistic expectations are not only set by government and professionals, but they can be endorsed by young people themselves putting them under even more pressure. While participants spoke about a range of practical skills they possessed, like Luna and Liam emotional resilience was not something that any of the young people spoke about having after leaving care.

Feelings of loneliness and isolation were shared by several participants with some extreme examples of how this affected them. Lisa felt that she went from intense support to nothing (Lisa, Interview two). Hamish enjoyed securing his own house but spoke about not being able to sleep initially because he was the only one there (Hamish, Interview nine). Amy also spoke about being too scared to stay alone (Amy, Interview twelve). In Avery's (2009) study of foster care experienced youth in the United States, she found that there was a risk of young people associating with what she described as 'deviant' peers due to inadequate social networks and loneliness. Except for Hamish, young people within the study did not develop a wider social support network while they were in care, outside their direct care workers. Feelings of isolation and loneliness were described as a result, this area for development would benefit from additional research. Most of the study group benefitted from advocacy and mentoring support from a specialist agency and this appeared to support a more successful transition to adulthood.

9.9 Measures of Success

Earlier in this chapter I highlighted that the participant group were high achievers as most of them achieved well academically. Mark enjoyed further education at college and was able to avoid loneliness by living in a shared flat with fellow students. The high rate of participants attending college and university illustrates that this is an unusual sample group as government figures show that only 27% of young people who lived in residential care achieved one qualification or more at SCQF level 5 compared to 85% of the general population (Scottish Government, 2020). While the government use educational attainment as a measure of success this was approached differently by young people. Most of participants took advantage of the financial support available to care leavers, this support is available up to the age of 26 years old. The group also spoke about feeling under pressure to do well educationally to prove the statistics wrong. When young people did not achieve what they hoped they spoke about an overwhelming sense of failure which is likely to be linked to how individuals over time have perceived residential care experienced young people in the first place (Luna and Kevin, Interviews one and five). Supports for young people to the age of 26 years does not support those who are late bloomers such as myself. Financial support to attend education over the life span would be more in keeping with effective parenting.

Employment for the participant group was largely precarious with only one young person being in stable secure employment which had lasted for more than ten years (Liam, Interview ten). Despite the unstable nature of work, which is indicative of the financial situation more generally and this is likely to get worse as the economy recovers from the effects of COVID-19, young people spoke about job satisfaction through helping others (Carol and Bob, Interviews three and thirteen).

Success was measured by participants in terms of becoming better people because they were removed from their parents, increasing strength in the face of adversity and in growing up and figuring things out despite their life experiences (Luna, Carol and Liam, Interviews one, three and ten). For some other participants measures of success resulted from knowing that not everyone makes it post-care, young people spoke about feeling lucky to be alive or grateful not to be in prison or addicted to substances like other family members (Lisa, Carol, Hamish, Liam and Amy, Interviews two, three, nine, ten and twelve). When she visited her previous placement, Lisa discovered that only two young people had survived from the group of six that lived in the house (Lisa, Interview two).

Being able to stand on their own two feet by living in a tenancy was a significant measure for Hamish and Carol who had sustained her own house for six years (Hamish and Carol, Interviews nine and three). Both Hamish and Tania spoke about financial challenges post care and for Hamish this resulted in a period of homelessness (Hamish and Tania, Interviews nine and four). Only two participants could rely on financial support from family members and one participant required a guarantor to secure a flat and his employer supported this (Kevin, Interview five). Corporate parents should assume this responsibility as research suggests that people are unlikely to get on the property ladder without the support of parents and young people do not lose the need for parental support due to their age (Kandiah, 2020; Scottish Care Leavers Covenant, 2015). Financial precarity and budgeting were described as the biggest barrier to those young people who lived independently. Panicking about not having enough money and not being able to open the door because you cannot afford to pay bills was experienced by Tania, Kevin, and Bruce (Interviews four, five and six). A revision of corporate parenting responsibilities that could support young people leaving care in the longer term may ensure that care experienced adults receive the practical support necessary into adulthood.

Stein's (2006) resilience framework, used in the previous chapter, helped to identify most of the study group as 'moving on' as they had achieved educational success, had secure attachment relationships with at least one other person and they experienced some level of stability through housing, training or work. What this typology highlighted is that care leavers status can change over time. Only one participant could be categorised as a 'struggler' and his situation had changed over a decade providing him with a sense of purpose and security he did not have during his early care leaving experience. Two other participants would be described as 'survivors' due to being less secure post-care. Ward and Stein (2020) highlight that only a small group fit this stereotype, reflective of poorer outcomes, post care. Academic achievements did not mitigate unstable accommodation or employment opportunities. As most of the young people studied fall within the lower leaving care age bracket their stability over time cannot be known. A follow up longitudinal study would give greater insight in this area.

9.10 Emerging Adulthood and Preparedness for Adulthood

This study looked at emerging adulthood to ascertain whether transitions to adulthood experienced in other populations was experienced by residential care leavers in Scotland. Arnett (2010) has described three markers that set emerging adulthood apart from other life stages: financial independence, responsibility taking and decision making. These three

aspects are viewed as replacing more traditional features of adulthood, such as marriage, having your own home and being a parent (Arnett, 2010). Further studies also identified five international markers described as identity exploration, age of instability, self-focus, feeling in between and optimism in 18–29-year-olds (Arnett, 2015; Galambos and Martinez, 2007; Zacaes, Serra and Torres, 2015). Identity exploration was evident within the study group as all but one of the participants spent time with other care experienced young people exploring their group identity as they attempted to make sense of their life experiences.

My study would suggest that young people's transition to adulthood is a process rather than a life stage with a destination, this was also the experience of Avery (2007) in her study of foster care experienced young people. Schoon and Lyons-Amos (2016) challenge the assumption of emerging adulthood as a new life stage as it does not take into account the diverse nature of transitions experienced by young people. Hamish spoke about how his perception of what it means to be an adult has changed over time and whereas it meant that he was able to make his own decisions and take responsibility for his actions when he first left care and wanted to socialise, it now means having a job or something that provides him with a structure and routine, irrespective of what it is as routine keeps you mentally well. Being nice to others and being a good person as well as complying with the law were other measures of adulthood (Hamish, Interview nine).

Despite similarities in age, Liam and Bob had very different views of adulthood. Liam spoke about opportunities he had to make mistakes while growing into being an adult as he had a supportive employer and relationships, but he said he was not financially independent although he was the only individual in secure employment. He saw adulthood as linked to his role as a parent and having his own house, the traditional markers of adulthood (Liam, Interview ten).

Bob's experience, however, was more akin to what Hamish reflected on when he first left care. He said he moves between the responsibility of adulthood which for him is tied to being in employment and his partying lifestyle he lives at the weekend. He has recently left home and moved into his own house but feels that he has still not grown up yet (Bob, Interview thirteen).

The youngest participants were more likely to view themselves as adults and this appeared to be linked to the status afforded care leavers when they reach the age of 18 years old as they are no longer legally viewed as children. Around one third of participants viewed themselves as adults despite not having financial stability, this view was less linked to age and more

related to how long the young people had been in care, the shorter the period in care, the more like an adult they saw themselves. Many of the young people felt that they were at the in-between stage.

While emerging adulthood may not be indicative of a new life stage and there are no biological markers that reflect this transition into adulthood it can serve as a useful indicator of the circumstances we should have aspirations of for our care experienced young people. Opportunities to return home, lifelong opportunities for education and financial support from corporate parents when young people need a guarantor or to supplement their income and a safety net for when young people need that bit of support. These are afforded those who are fortunate enough to experience emerging adulthood so these opportunities should be afforded to others.

9.11 My original contribution to knowledge

This qualitative piece of research is unique in Scotland as it has been carried out by a practitioner in the field of study who has a shared knowledge and understanding of the topic having worked in residential child for more than 25 years. Lyotard (1984) argues that experts have limited knowledge and understanding but I hope that this work has shown that expertise in the field of study can enhance the depth of development over what is known. Taylor and White (2001) state that practice in residential care can lack analysis and theoretical base but this study challenges this. I have added to the dearth of qualitative research into the residential care journey and the transition to adulthood and applied the theoretical framework of social constructionism.

By applying social constructionism, I have illustrated the significant impact that dominant discourses have on individual experiences as was reflected in deserving and undeserving, perceptions of gender, power and agency associated with age and stage, economic circumstances and opportunities and perceptions about the best place for children to grow up irrespective of their experiences.

Other researchers have experienced barriers in the recruitment process due to a lack of access to participants engaging in their field of study. I nurtured a relationship with a colleague for ten years that enabled me to utilise them as a gatekeeper, without whom it is difficult to see how this research would have been a success. Others have illustrated the importance of a gatekeeper as they can help, hinder or stop research (McFadyen and Rankin, 2016). My own conduit worked tirelessly supporting my project engaging colleagues and young people

so that I could gain access to as many participants as were willing to take part. Overcoming this barrier cannot be underestimated.

The significance of the findings to my original contribution is firstly evident in the research taking a holistic life cycle approach and looked at the totality of the journey into care by exploring the before, during and after of the care experience. Most research looks at an element of care or experience therein so this adds to my unique contribution. It highlights that outcomes cannot be viewed in isolation as factors that contribute to success or otherwise are multi-faceted and complex.

Practice and policy developments relevant to residential care have been illustrated throughout this study and as a practitioner-researcher-academic I have been able to highlight what participants have stated is needed to change the experience for children living away from home. Rarely does practice development of this nature come from within the field.

Quantitative research into leaving care highlights a mixture of poor outcomes for young people (McGhee, Lerpiniere, Wetch, Graham, and Harkin (2014); MacDonald, Cruikshank and Ray, 2013). as well as positive measures of success in terms of employment, housing and educational attainment (Duncalf, 2010; Stein, 2006). My research has illustrated that while young people recognise some of the sociological markers of success such as secure employment and having enough money, for the majority of participants success was measured in terms of being alive, not being the same as one's parents or not being in prison. Low expectations were inherent in young people's experiences and this study illustrates some of the barriers that need to be overcome if young people are to overcome stigma, blame and shame.

9.12 Future research

This study adds to the increasing body of research that looks at the experiences of care leavers, but it does so through the lens of a practitioner, researcher and academic by exploring the entire care journey. By using the framework from a social constructionist perspective there is an eclectic social science theoretical approach to the work and further research applying a different perspective would be beneficial and help to increase our understanding in the field.

Outcomes for the thirteen young participants were largely positive; they achieved well academically although this did not always translate into secure employment. While this is reflective of the wider economic climate other young people in the general population have a wider social support system to draw both financial and emotional support from. The

significantly high proportion of participants who attended college or university would indicate that research would benefit from a longitudinal study to ascertain whether care leavers are more likely to attend further education at a later stage in their lives, as is the case for mature students from lower socioeconomic groups. Legislation supporting young care leavers up to the age of 26 years old is admirable and the age is higher than it is in other parts of the UK for residential care leavers, but it is insufficient to meet the longer term needs of this demographic group. A change to legislation would be welcomed as your children never stop being your children so this should apply to the children of corporate parents. In addition, a national database should record the outcomes for care experienced individuals so that we can monitor, evaluate and learn from the data although this would need to ensure that anonymity was maintained.

The narratives provided by participants reflected experiences that were free from abuse in care although some young people did discuss what could be described as poor practice issues. Hamish spoke about how he was reluctant to speak about his positive experiences within care amongst care experienced peers as others tended to focus on poor experiences and he felt guilty, leading to him remaining silent (Hamish, Interview nine). There was also discussions that reflect a 'hierarchy' of experiences with the most harrowing stories gaining status when voices need to be heard that will change policy or practice (Kevin and Hamish, Interviews five and nine), while others commented on the fact that no one who attended the advocacy group events cared about where you had lived or what you may have done or experienced as there was a shared identity that engendered a sense of belonging and acceptance (All interviews except Tina's). This must be acknowledged as one of the limitations of this study is all but one of the young people received advocacy support. Young people's access to this resource may be indicative of their status as being in employment or training so it may not be typical of the care experienced population or reflective of other findings.

If national data was gathered, we may have a clearer understanding of the lives of care experienced young people when they move on from their placements. Both quantitative and qualitative statistical information could inform practice and policy development. While this study has added to the qualitative research that applies theoretical frameworks to leaving care and transitions studies, the field would benefit from more studies of this nature. Longitudinal studies would help to gather information over time as now it is difficult to ascertain whether short term barriers to progression towards adulthood are overcome in the longer term.

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APPENDIX 1

Information sheet for participants

Thanks for agreeing to take part in this study, your involvement is very much appreciated.

The purpose of the research:

The aim of the study is to highlight what factors support the successful transition from adolescence to adulthood for care leavers who have lived in residential care in Scotland. The purpose of the study is to gain valuable insight into care leavers experiences by looking at developmental life stage theory. For almost two decades researchers have debated a new life stage, 'emerging adulthood', as reflecting the experiences of 18 – 30 year olds in modern western societies. This study will look at whether this theory relates to the experiences of care experienced young people in Scotland and look at the implications this may have for policy and practice. I recognize that speaking about your experiences may be upsetting as I am asking you to share your care histories. Should you need any additional support following discussions you can contact other resources, see below, or we can discuss alternatives.

Confidentiality:

Any information that is shared by you will remain confidential within the group. I will use pseudonyms to ensure you remain anonymous and if you wish to do so you can choose your own.

If you decide that you do not want to be included after you have provided data for this study you can contact me on [REDACTED] and your data will be removed and deleted. You will receive the £10 voucher whether we include your data or not.

Should you be unhappy with any aspect of the research you can contact my research supervisor

[REDACTED]

Prof Colin Clark
University of the West of Scotland
L119, Elles Building East
High Street
Paisley
PA1 2BE

Personal data withheld.

Final report:

Please let me know if you would like to receive a copy of my research findings or my final report.

Useful contacts:

Who Cares, Scotland	0141 226 4441
The Samaritans	116 123
In Care Survivors	0800 121 6027
Scottish Throughcare and Aftercare Forum	0141 465 7511
Childline	0800 1111
Parentline	08000 28 22 33
Scottish Association for Mental Health	0141 530 100

APPENDIX 2

Gatekeeper letter

Ruby V Whitelaw
Paisley
PA2 ORE
Renfrewshire

Billy (pseudonym)
Champions Advocacy Group

27th May 2016

Dear Billy

I am currently undertaking a PhD at the University of the West of Scotland and completing a piece of research looking at 'What factors support the successful transition from adolescence to adulthood for care leavers who have resided in residential care in Scotland?' I have identified that there is a gap in current research that takes a life stage developmental approach to this transition so this is the focus of my study. I hope that this research will inform future practice and policy within Scotland.

I am writing, following our email correspondence, to ask if you would be able to support my recruitment of participants from CAG...

I have included the participants' information letter, poster, information sheet and focus group details. I am hoping to complete the research between January and March 2017 but will take the lead from you as to whether another time would be more appropriate. I am able to make myself available so that young people can ask for additional information prior to agreeing to take part in the study, again I am happy for you to guide me on this. Interviews and focus group sessions will last no more than an hour and I'm delighted that you have agreed that your premises can be used for this work. I will ensure that any disruption to your resource would be kept to a minimum.

I hope that you still find the study of interest and I look forward to working with you on this. Please contact me if there is anything you need clarified. Alternatively, you can contact my university director of studies [REDACTED]

Yours sincerely

Ruby V Whitelaw

Personal data withheld.

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

APPENDIX 3

RESEARCH STUDY THAT COULD IMPACT ON THE LIVES OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN RESIDENTIAL CARE

The transition from adolescence to adulthood for young people who have experienced residential care can be a challenging time. Finding out what supports successful transitions is the aim of this research.....

Volunteers!

My name is Ruby and I have worked in residential care for twenty years. I'm keen to make the experience better for young people so if you can spare an hour between January and December 2017 please let me know. I'm looking to conduct individual interviews and group sessions talking about your experience. You can text me on [REDACTED].

Alternatively, you can let Billy know you are interested.
You will receive a £10 voucher for taking part.

Personal data withheld.

APPENDIX 4

Letter to participants

My name is Ruby Whitelaw and I have worked in residential care for 20 years. This research will look at what factors support the successful transition from adolescence to adulthood for those who have experienced residential care in Scotland, something I have always been interested in. I hope to gain valuable insight into care leavers experiences by looking at life stage theory. For nearly 20 years' researchers have debated a new life stage, 'emerging adulthood' believing this reflects the experiences of 18 – 30 year olds in western society. This study will look at whether this theory relates to the lives of care experienced young people in Scotland and will look at the implications of this for policy and practice. As this study forms the basis for my PhD, I am undertaking at the University of the West of Scotland, it is likely to be printed in a variety of publications.

I am looking for young people and adults who have experience of living within residential care, and who are aged 18 – 30 years. If this applies to you and you are interested in informing future practice and policy for other care leavers this research is for you. The study will take place between January and December 2017.

There are two parts to this research and you can take part in one or both of these. Prior to taking part I will be asking you to complete a one-page questionnaire so that I have basic information. I am looking for volunteers to take part in individual interviews so that I can reflect on real life care experiences. Interviews will take no more than an hour and I am looking for up to eight people to take part in this research.

I'm also looking for up to 30 individuals to take part in focus groups consisting of 6 – 8 people. This means meeting with others and sharing your care experiences while I facilitate the group.

You will be asked a series of questions so that I can gather information about your care experience but you can get involved in discussions about any or all of the questions and you won't be expected to discuss anything you don't feel comfortable with. An example of the questions, include 'did you feel ready to leave care' and 'how did you know you were ready'. The groups will be recorded and if you give permission for me to do so I'd also like to video record the meetings. This will ensure I have an accurate record of what occurs. The meeting will last no longer than an hour.

Once I write up what has been said recordings will be deleted and any identifying information will be removed to ensure that your information is anonymous. All data will be stored in a locked cabinet. You will receive a £10 voucher in recognition of the time you have given up to take part in the research. Alternatively, I can arrange snacks and soft drinks while we chat.

You have the right to withdraw your consent at any time if you do not want your information to be included and you do not need to answer any questions you don't want to. If something is discussed that means someone may be at significant risk of harm I may have to share this information to ensure individuals safety. In the event that something is discussed that causes distress we will identify appropriate support so you have someone to talk to.

If you are interested in taking part in the study you can contact me at [REDACTED]. Alternatively, you can reach me through Billy. I look forward to hearing from you.

Personal data withheld.

Interview questions

1. Did you feel ready to leave care?
2. How did you know you were ready?
3. Did your experience of residential care help to prepare you for the transition to adulthood?
4. In what way?
5. What does being an adult mean to you? If necessary, prompt re role transitions, responsibility taking, decision making.
6. At what age did you feel like an adult?
7. Did you feel that you were supported if things didn't go to plan?
8. How and who provided you with support?
9. What role did your family play in your care experience?
10. Did you feel there was a stigma of being in residential care?
11. Why do you think that is?
12. Did you leave care with qualifications? What were they?
13. Have you revisited formal education since leaving care, if so at what age?
14. Do you feel that you've achieved successful outcomes? What does successful outcomes mean to you.
15. What successful outcomes have been important to you?
16. Is there anything you feel you missed out on?
17. What could people have done to make your experience better?
18. Is there anything else you'd like to say?

APPENDIX 6

Consent form

This research will look at what factors support the successful transitions from adolescence to adulthood for care leavers who have resided in residential care in Scotland.

I _____ understand the purpose of this research and have been given enough information to give my informed consent. I have been able to ask questions and know that I can withdraw my consent at any time and I will still receive a £10 voucher. I will not be identifiable within the research which may be published in a variety of ways. I am happy to take part in this study and understand that I do not need to answer any of the questions, if I don't want to.

If you would like to select the name you'd like to be identified within the research as please let me know, otherwise I will select a name for you.

	Yes	No
I would like to complete the questionnaire	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would like to take part in the interview	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would like to take part in a focus group	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name _____

Signature _____

Date _____

Name you would like to be known as within the research _____

APPENDIX 7

Research Questionnaire

Age:	Gender:	Ethnicity:
What age were you when you first went into care: _____		What age were you when you left care: _____
Were you ever in residential care?		
YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
How many placements did you have: _____		
Did you have a good relationship with anyone during your time in care?		
YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
If yes, who was this with: _____ _____		
Did this relationship continue when you left care?		
YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
If no, why not: _____ _____		
Did anyone explain why you were in care?		
YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
Did you know before this?		
YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
Can you remember what was said? _____ _____		
What local authority were you from? _____		

Redaction due to copyright restrictions. Original questionnaire can be found at miami.edu.

[Adverse Childhood Experiences \(ACEs\) Questionnaire \(miami.edu\)](http://miami.edu) (Accessed 11.1.2022)